

**BUNDESMINISTERIUM
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Report 2009

**Trends and Sources of
Zoonoses and Zoonotic Agents
in Humans, Foodstuffs, Animals and
Feedingstuffs**

Austria

**Including information on foodborne outbreaks,
antimicrobial resistance in zoonotic agents and some
pathogenic microbiological agents**

AUSTRIA

The Report referred to in Article 9 of Directive 2003/99/EC

**TRENDS AND SOURCES OF ZONOSSES AND ZONOTIC AGENTS
IN HUMANS, FOODSTUFFS, ANIMALS AND FEEDINGSTUFFS**

**Including information on foodborne outbreaks, antimicrobial
resistance in zoonotic agents and some pathogenic microbiological
agents**

IN 2009

1. Information on the Reporting and Monitoring System

Country: Austria

Reporting Year: 2009

Institutions and laboratories involved in monitoring

Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
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Authorities

Central Veterinary Services	Federal Ministry of Health	Data concerning notifiable zoonoses in animals; Revision of the draft of the Trend Report; Approval of the Trend Report for Submission
Food Office	Federal Ministry of Health	Revision of the draft of the Trend Report
DG Public Health	Federal Ministry of Health	Data concerning notifiable zoonoses in humans and food borne outbreaks; revision of the draft of the Trend Report
Feed Office	Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry, the Environment and Watermanagement	Revision of the draft of the Trend Report
Provincial Veterinary Services	9 provinces, one Veterinary Service per province	Data concerning notifiable zoonoses in animals
Local/District health authorities	Part of each local administration authority ("Bezirksverwaltungsbehörde"), one physician per district	Collection of the data concerning notifiable zoonoses in humans and food borne outbreaks

Institutes

Statistics Austria	The independent and non-profit-making federal institution, Statistics Austria, provides data on the economy, demography, environment and social and cultural situation in Austria to federal bodies. Federal agencies can then implement controlling measures in the scientific community, business and public institutions.	Demographic and livestock census data
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Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
Competence Centre for Infectious Disease Epidemiology (CC-INFE)	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Compilation, validation, data entry and submission of the Zoonoses Trend Report
Data, Statistics and Risk Assessment	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Analysis of laboratory results for antimicrobial resistance of <i>Campylobacter</i> spp. <i>Enterococcus faecalis/faecium</i> and <i>E. coli</i>

Human Medicine

National Reference Centre for Salmonella Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning salmonellosis in feedingstuff, animals, foodstuff and humans
National Reference Laboratory for <i>Campylobacter</i> , Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning campylobacteriosis in humans
National Reference Laboratory for Antimicrobial resistance, Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning antimicrobial resistance testing of isolates from humans, food and animals
National Reference Centre for Tuberculosis, Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Vienna	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning mycobacteriosis in humans
National Reference Center for EHEC (VTEC) Department of Hygiene, Microbiology and Social Medicine, Division of Hygiene & Medical Microbiology	Innsbruck Medical University	Data concerning VTEC and listeriosis in humans
National Reference Centre for Listeria Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Vienna	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning listeriosis in humans
National Reference Laboratory for Yersinia, analyse BioLab limited company (GmbH)	Limited Liability Corporation of Elisabethinen Linz, MBB BioLab limited company (GmbH) and AGES	Data concerning yersiniosis in humans

Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
National Reference Laboratory for Toxoplasmosis, Echinococcosis, Toxocarosis and other Parasitic Diseases, Clinical Institute for Hygiene and Medical Microbiology	Medical University of Vienna	Data concerning parasitic diseases in humans
National Reference Laboratory for Brucellosis, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control, (IVET), Moedling	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning brucellosis in animals and humans

Food Control Institutes

Official Food Control Laboratories (ILMU)	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES; Laboratories in Graz, Innsbruck, Linz, Salzburg and Vienna	Data concerning investigations in foodstuffs
Food Safety Department of the City of Vienna	Regional Food Laboratory	Data concerning investigations in foodstuffs
Institute for Environment and Food Safety of the State of Vorarlberg	Regional Food Laboratory	Data concerning investigations in foodstuffs
Carinthian Institute for Food Analysis and Quality Control	Regional Food Laboratory	Data concerning investigations in foodstuffs

Veterinary Medicine

National Reference Laboratory for Tuberculosis in Animals, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control, Moedling	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning tuberculosis in animals
National Reference Laboratory for Trichinellosis in Animals, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control, (IVET), Innsbruck	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning trichinellosis in animals
Institutes for Veterinary Disease Control (IVET)	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES; Laboratories in Graz, Innsbruck, Linz and Moedling	Data concerning investigations in animals; bacteriological investigation in slaughtered animals

Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
National Reference Laboratory for Rabies, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control, Moedling	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning rabies in animals
Carinthian Institute for Veterinary Disease Control, Ehrental	Regional Veterinary Laboratory	Data concerning investigations in animals
Austrian Poultry Health Service (QGV)	Association installed by law, running different programs e.g. salmonella control and hygiene programs, Control of veterinarians and poultry farmers	Data concerning the Austrian poultry industry

Feed Control Institute

Institute for Agricultural Analysis, Linz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning feeding stuff
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PREFACE

This report is submitted to the European Commission in accordance with Article 9 of Council Directive 2003/99/EC1. The information has also been forwarded to the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA).

The report contains information on trends and sources of zoonoses and zoonotic agents in Austria during the year 2009. The information covers the occurrence of these diseases and agents in humans, animals, foodstuffs and in some cases also in feedingstuffs. In addition the report includes data on antimicrobial resistance in some zoonotic agents and commensal bacteria as well as information on epidemiological investigations of foodborne outbreaks. Complementary data on susceptible animal populations in the country is also given.

The information given covers both zoonoses that are important for the public health in the whole European Community as well as zoonoses, which are relevant on the basis of the national epidemiological situation.

The report describes the monitoring systems in place and the prevention and control strategies applied in the country. For some zoonoses this monitoring is based on legal requirements laid down by the Community Legislation, while for the other zoonoses national approaches are applied.

The report presents the results of the examinations carried out in the reporting year. A national evaluation of the epidemiological situation, with special reference to trends and sources of zoonotic infections, is given. Whenever possible, the relevance of findings in foodstuffs and animals to zoonoses cases in humans is evaluated.

The information covered by this report is used in the annual Community Summary Report on zoonoses that is published each year by EFSA.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AGES	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety
BMG	Federal Ministry of Health
BMSK	Federal Ministry for Social Security, Generations and Consumer Protection
CC-INFE	Competence Centre for Infectious Disease Epidemiology
EHEC	Enterohemorrhagic E. coli
EFSA	European Food Safety Authority
EMS	Epidemiological Notification System for human notifiable diseases ("epidemiologisches Meldesystem")
ILMU	Official Food Control Laboratories, AGES
IMED	Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, AGES
IVET	Institute for Veterinary Disease Control, AGES
NRC	National Reference Centre
NRL	National Reference Laboratory
OIE	World organisation for animal health
TESSy	The European Surveillance System
VIS	Veterinary Information System
VTEC	Verocytotoxic E. coli

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3. Animal Populations

3.1. Information on susceptible animal population

Sources of information

The independent and non-profit-making federal institution, Statistics Austria, provides data on the economy, demography, environment and social and cultural situation in Austria to federal bodies. Federal agencies can then implement controlling measures in the scientific community, business and public institutions. The data for this report are available from an online database established by Statistics Austria.

Herds, flocks, holdings, stocks

Cattle: The number of holdings and animals is based on the official database for cattle.

Equids, Pigs, Sheep, Goats and Farmed Deer: The number of holdings and animals is based on the yearly full survey of the Veterinary Information System (VIS).

Poultry: The number of holdings and animals is based on a random sample survey performed by Statistics Austria (farm structure survey). The last random sample survey was performed 2007.

Slaughters

Cattle, Equids: The number of slaughters is based on a monthly/yearly statistic of all examined slaughters (reported by veterinarians), performed by Statistics Austria.

Pigs: The number of slaughters is based on a monthly/yearly statistic of all examined slaughters (reported by veterinarians), combined with not-examined slaughters (out of pig-random-sample-surveys) performed by Statistics Austria.

Sheep & Goats: The number of slaughters is based on an expert-model carried out by Statistics Austria.

Poultry: The number of slaughters is based on a monthly/yearly full survey in poultry-slaughterhouses (only) performed by Statistics Austria.

Dates the figures relate to and the content of the figures

Data are received from Statistics Austria, only poultry data from QGV.

Definitions used for different types of animals, herds, flocks and holdings as well as the types covered by the information

Cattle: BGBl. II Nr. 147/2009 (Statistiken über den Viehbestand)

Swine, Sheep and Goats: BGBl. II Nr. 291/2009 (Tierkennzeichnungs- und Regestrierungsverordnung 2009)

Poultry: BGBl. II Nr. 310/2007 (Erstellung der Statistik über die Agrarstruktur und den Viehbestand im Jahr 2007); BGBl. II Nr. 356/2003 (Erhebung der Geflügelschlachtungen in Betrieben mit min. 5000 Vorjahres-Geflügelschlachtungen)

Geographical distribution and size distribution of the herds, flocks and holdings

Pigs: 96,95 % of all pigs are kept in 84,34 % of the holdings that are located in the 4 provinces Carinthia, Lower Austria, Upper Austria and Styria;

Sheep: 72,95 % of the sheep holdings are located in the 4 provinces Lower Austria, Upper Austria, Styria and the Tyrol; 74,85 % of the sheep are kept there.

Goats: 71,62 % of the goat holdings are located in the 4 provinces Lower Austria, Upper Austria, Styria and the Tyrol; 78,52 % of the goats are kept there.

Additional information

Nil

Table 1 Susceptible animal populations: number of herds and holdings rearing animals

Animal species	Category of animals	Number of holdings		Livestock numbers (live animals)		Number of slaughtered animals	
			Year*		Year*		Year*
Bovine animals	In total	73466	01.12.2009	2026260	01.12.2009	699783	2009
	LS: cattle under one year (incl. calves for slaughter) (slaughterings: calves only)	n.a.	01.12.2009	643441	01.12.2009	80166	2009
	Cows and heifers not for slaughtering purposes	n.a.	01.12.2009	1097486	01.12.2009	619617	2009
	(mostly) Meat production animals (not incl. calves for slaughter)	n.a.	01.12.2009	285333	01.12.2009		
	Mixed herds						
Sheep	In total	15633	01.04.2009	405365	01.04.2009	290088	2009
	Milk ewes	975	01.04.2009	21826	01.04.2009		
	Meat production animals						
	Animals over 1 year (slaughtered as: sheep)	15659	01.04.2009	233430	01.04.2009	59977	2009
	Animals under 1 year (slaughtered as: lambs)	13825	01.04.2009	172434	01.04.2009	230111	2009
	Mixed herds						
Goats	In total	10528	01.04.2009	84840	01.04.2009	41276	2009
	Milk goats	2921	01.04.2009	26232	01.04.2009		
	Meat production animals						
	Animals over 1 year (slaughtered as: goats)	10516	01.04.2009	56384	01.04.2009	9894	2009
	Animals under 1 year (slaughtered as: kids)	4892	01.04.2009	28461	01.04.2009	31382	2009
	Mixed herds						
Pigs	In total	36680	01.04.2009	3143509	01.04.2009	5597387	2009
	Sows and gilts (slaughterings: sows only)	8596	01.04.2009	293250	01.04.2009	102028	2009
	Fattening pigs	27688	01.04.2009	1127650	01.04.2009	5495359	2009
	Breeding animals						
	Multiplication animals						
	Mixed herds						
Gallus gallus	In total (slaughterings: in major slaughterhouses only)					70330516	2009
	Breeding animals in total						

Animal Populations

Animal species	Category of animals	Number of holdings		Livestock numbers (live animals)		Number of slaughtered animals	
			Year*		Year*		Year*
	Breeding animals for egg production line in total						
	Breeding animals for meat production line in total						
	Elite birds in total	0		0		0	
	Elite birds for egg production line						
	Elite birds for meat production line						
	Grandparent birds in total	0		0		0	
	Grandparent birds for egg production line						
	Grandparent birds for meat production line						
	Parent birds in total	82					
	Parent birds for egg production line			221668			
	Parent birds for meat production line			774572			
	Laying hens	1677		5348103			
	Broilers	470		56211083			
	Mixed flocks/ holdings			221668			
Turkey	In total (slaughters: in slaughterhouses only)					protected	2009
	Breeding animals in total	0		0		0	
	Elite birds	0		0		0	
	Grandparent birds	0		0		0	
	Parent birds	0		0		0	
	Meat production birds	140		2137367			
	Mixed flocks/ holdings						
Geese	In total (slaughters: in slaughterhouses only; incl. ducks)					protected	2009
	Breeding animals in total						
	Elite birds	0		0		0	
	Grandparent birds	0		0		0	
	Parent birds	0		0		0	
	Meat production animals						
	Mixed flocks/ holdings	11					

Animal Populations

Animal species	Category of animals	Number of holdings		Livestock numbers (live animals)		Number of slaughtered animals	
			Year*		Year*		Year*
Ducks	In total (slaughters: part of geese)					protected	2009
	Breeding animals in total						
	Elite birds	0		0		0	
	Grandparent birds	0		0		0	
	Parent birds	0		0		0	
	Meat production animals						
	Mixed flocks/ holdings						
Equids		15370	01.04.2009	70427	01.04.2009	978	2009
Farmed deer		1571	01.04.2009	35065	01.04.2009	n.a.	2009
Farmed reindeers							
Farmed wild boars							

4. Information on Specific Zoonoses and Zoonotic Agents

The World Health Organization defines zoonoses as “those diseases and infections which are naturally transmitted between vertebrate animals and man.” Foodstuffs often serve as vehicles of zoonotic infections. Zoonotic agents include viruses, bacteria, fungi, parasites or other biological entities that are likely to cause zoonoses.

Collection of human cases

Numbers of human cases were reported or notified by different data-collection systems in Austria:

Aggregated notified cases on a monthly basis: In Austria, physicians reported until 31. December 2009 all notifiable infectious diseases to the appropriate authorities. Reported cases were collected nationwide and published monthly by the Federal Ministry of Health online on the BMG-homepage: (<http://www.bmg.gv.at/cms/site/thema.html?channel=CH0745>). Although the preliminary case numbers are available all year, they must be validated before the final report is published. These data only contained month and province of a notified case, no information is given concerning age and sex of the patient, or results of the differentiation of the causative agent (species or serotype etc.).

Primary isolates from patients typed in the national reference centres: The responsible reference centres published the numbers of microbiologically confirmed cases; these figures may also differ from the case numbers notified to the Federal Ministry.

Starting with 1. January 2009 a new reporting system which incorporates data sources, the **epidemiological notification system** (epidemiologisches Meldesystem, EMS) has been put in operation. The physicians report all notifiable diseases (case based) to the local health authorities which are part of the local administration authorities (“Bezirksverwaltungsbehörde”). The physicians working at the official local health authorities have to enter the data of the human cases of all notifiable diseases in the data base EMS including all relevant variables and laboratory results (case based). In the near future laboratories (including national reference centres) will enter the results of their laboratory work in EMS via a gateway to streamline the process. As EMS is (starting with 1. January 2009) the one and only database for notifiable diseases this system is also the source and gateway for reporting to ECDC (upload of data from EMS to the European Surveillance System (TESSy) or if necessary to WHO. A short report is also extracted and compiled using EMS which is published nationwide monthly by the Federal Ministry of Health online on the BMG-homepage: (<http://www.bmg.gv.at/cms/site/thema.html?channel=CH0745>). These tables contain only month and province of a notified case, no information is given concerning age and sex of the patient, or results of differentiation of the causative agent (species or serotype etc.).

In this report it is indicated which data source has been used for the reporting of human cases for each respective zoonosis (all data were collected from the national reference centres/laboratories with the exception of the number of notified campylobacteriosis cases).

General Information about the Food Sampling Strategy

Foodstuff was sampled according to the decree „Revisions- und Probenplan für das Jahr 2009 gemäß §31 LMSVG; Richtlinien über die Vollziehung der Überwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Berichtsschema 2008“ (BMGFJ – 75500/0332-IV/B/7/2008) of the Federal Ministry of

Health. This “Revisions- und Probenplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2007-2010) according to Art. 41 ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004.

The Revision-Plan determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be sampled and tested randomly according to the number of food enterprises per province. Every food business within Austria has to be sampled at least once per year. The inspection can comprise sampling, hygienic investigations of the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes etc.

In 2009, approximately 40,000 samples were planned to be tested in Austria. About 60% (24,000) of these are planned samples (surveillance) and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). These planned samples either consist of samples of the yearly sampling plan which determines the number of samples of each food category that have to be investigated randomly, e.g. raw meat (fresh or frozen); sausages; cheeses; milk; preserved food etc. There are different sampling stages where food samples are taken: e.g. from retail, processing plant, primary production.

In addition there is a monitoring plan for food items (40-45 campaigns per year). In the course of these programs food items of special interest for defined parameters – amongst others zoonotic agents – are investigated. The sampling takes place during a given period of time. In 2009, seven food campaign programs were conducted throughout Austria dealing with zoonotic agents (Schwerpunktprogramm 2009 BMGFJ-75500/0242-IV/B/7/2008). Details and results of these campaigns can be found in the respective chapters.

4.1. Salmonellosis

4.1.1. General evaluation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Human salmonellosis remains a major health problem in Austria. In 2009, the number of notified salmonellosis cases was the second highest reported pathogen after campylobacteriosis.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The incidence of human salmonellosis has significantly declined since the peak in 1998/1999. The salmonella-contamination of raw poultry meat has declined from 30% in 1999 to less than 4.6% in 2009. The consumption of eggs that are contaminated with Salmonella is presently the main source of human infection.

The number of salmonellosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of primary human isolates and respectively the number of laboratory confirmed cases sent to the National Reference Centre for Salmonella, n = 2,829. This number shows again a reduction compared to the year 2008 and reflects the success of interventions aimed at combating salmonella. According to the Federal Ministry of Health, the official number of notified cases is 2,539 (aggregated cases, vorläufiger Jahresausweis über angezeigte Fälle übertragbarer Krankheiten 2009, status quo 28.01.2010).

As compared to the number of notified cases of campylobacteriosis (see chapter campylobacteriosis), salmonella is the second most important cause for enteric diseases in Austria.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

In 2009, data from feedingstuffs indicate that the prevalence of salmonella (1.5%) remains very low. The number of cases which test positive for Salmonella is highest in poultry. Therefore, poultry is considered the main source for human infection. Although none of the tested table eggs (55 samples) were positive for salmonella, infected eggs pose the main source of human infections.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

There were various programs implemented to control the contamination of Salmonella in poultry, most programs involved meat and egg production. The main effort of the intervention is directed toward improving the sanitation of breeding flocks and laying flocks according to EU legislation.

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Continue the efforts already started, especially to improve harmonization of monitoring and control programs along the food chain.

4.1.2. Salmonellosis in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

The number of salmonellosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of primary human isolates and respectively the number of laboratory confirmed cases sent to the National Reference Centre for Salmonella.

Case definition

Clinical picture compatible with salmonellosis, e. g. diarrhoea, abdominal pain, nausea and sometimes vomiting. The organism may cause extraintestinal infections.

Laboratory criteria for diagnosis: Isolation of *Salmonella* spp. (non-typhi, non-paratyphi) from a clinical specimen.

Case classification

- Probable case: A laboratory confirmed isolate without clinical information or, a case with clinical symptoms that has an epidemiological link
- Confirmed case: A clinically compatible case that is laboratory confirmed

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Bacteriology: Sample material is processed as described in Richtlinien für die Diagnostik von Salmonellen (Anonymus: Standardisierung und Qualitätssicherung in der mikrobiologischen Diagnostik. Richtlinien. Bundesministerium für Soziale Sicherheit und Generationen. ISBN 3-84123-126-0, Wien, 2001, pg. 11-12).

At the National Reference Centre for Salmonella (NRC Salmonella), all isolates are serotyped according to the Kauffmann-White-Scheme. And further all *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are phage typed according to the methods used by HPA, Colindale, UK. Additionally the antimicrobial resistance testing by disk diffusion method is performed with each isolate.

Notification system in place

Notification of salmonellosis according to the epidemic act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): The attending physicians and the laboratories have to notify.

The number of salmonellosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of primary human isolates and respectively the number of laboratory confirmed cases sent to the National Reference Centre for Salmonella.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

In 1989 and 1990, human infections with salmonella increased markedly in Austria. After a peak in 1992, the incidence of salmonella illness decreased, but the number of infections has remained at a high level until 2002. Since that year the number of laboratory confirmed cases of human *Salmonella* infections has decreased by 66% (2002: 8,405 primary isolates, 2009: 2,829 primary isolates).

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2009, the number of laboratory confirmed cases of human *Salmonella* infections again decreased compared to the year before.

The proportion of *S. Enteritidis*, out of all *Salmonella* isolates, decreased in 2009 slightly to 65.1% (compared to 68.5% in 2008). The order of the three most common phage types changed in 2009: The most frequently identified phage type was PT8 (37%), PT4 (27%); less common detected were PT 21 (10%) and PT6 (9%). In 2008: PT4 has been the most frequently (35%) identified, followed by PT8 (24%) and PT21 (19%). In 2008, the two most common phage types account for 64% of all *S. Enteritidis* cases. The number of *S. Typhimurium* cases reported increased in absolute numbers (n=482; in 2008 n=374) and in relative numbers: 17.4% compared to 11.7% in 2008. The increase of *S. Typhimurium* is due to a food borne outbreak in a military base that affected 183 soldiers.

Table eggs are probably still the main source of human infections of *S. Enteritidis*.

Relevance as zoonotic disease

In 2009, the number of notified human cases of campylobacteriosis again exceeded the number of salmonellosis cases. It is believed that the reduction in the number of human salmonellosis cases is due to EU wide control programs and establishment of goals for the reduction of prevalences of salmonella in laying hen flocks and broilers.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Annual report of the National Reference Center:

http://www.bmg.gv.at/cms/site/attachments/0/6/6/CH0954/CMS1268584751914/jb_salmonellen_2009.pdf

Data Source of Tables 2 to 4: Primary isolates from patients typed in the national reference centre for salmonella

Table 2 Salmonellosis cases in humans - species/serotype distribution

	Cases	Incidence/ 100,000	Imported cases	Unknown status
Salmonellosis	2775	33.2	67	
S. Enteritidis	1,807	21.6	34	
S. Typhimurium	482	5.8	4	
S. enterica monophasic	64	0.8	1	
S. Infantis	57	0.7	-	
S. Saintpaul	27	0.3	3	
S. Hadar	22	0.3	1	
S. Virchow	19	0.2	1	
S. Agona	14	0.2	-	
S. Paratyphi B var. L(+) tartrate+	15	0.2	1	
S. Abony	12	0.1	-	
S. Muenchen	10	0.1	-	
S. Newport	11	0.1	1	
S. Thompson	10	0.1	-	
S. Bovismorbificans	9	0.1	-	
S. Heidelberg	9	0.1	-	
S. Kentucky	12	0.1	3	
S. Stanley	11	0.1	2	
S. Brandenburg	8	0.1	-	
S. Corvallis	9	0.1	1	
S. Kottbus	8	0.1	1	
S. London	7	0.1	-	
S. Montevideo	7	0.1	1	
S. Braenderup	6	0.1	1	
S. Bredeney	5	0.1	-	
S. Derby	5	0.1	-	
S. Mbandaka	5	0.1	-	
S. Potsdam	5	0.1	-	
Other serotypes	119		12	

Table 3 Salmonellosis cases in humans - age distribution

age group	Salmonella spp			S. Enteritidis			S. Typhimurium			S. enterica monophasic			S. Infantis			other serotypes		
	all	M	F	all	M	F	all	M	F	all	M	F	all	M	F	all	M	F
< 1 year	83	39	44	30	15	15	17	9	8	2	2		7	4	3	27	9	18
1 to 4 years	380	208	172	261	152	109	65	27	38	11	5	6	2	1	1	41	23	18
5 to 14 years	476	252	224	339	176	163	71	37	34	18	12	6	5	4	1	43	23	20
15 to 24 years	445	291	154	235	115	120	140	127	13	6	4	2	12	7	5	52	38	14
25 to 44 years	544	291	253	348	176	172	79	52	27	11	4	7	13	7	6	93	52	41
45 to 64 years	449	210	239	306	138	168	58	29	29	12	6	6	8	4	4	65	33	32
> 65 years	354	150	204	261	117	144	41	12	29	4	3	1	8	4	4	40	14	26
unknown	44	24	20	27	14	13	11	6	5	0			2	1	1	4	3	1
	2,775	1,465	1,310	1,807	903	904	482	299	183	64	36	28	57	32	25	365	195	170

Table 4 Salmonellosis cases in humans – seasonal distribution

month	Salmonella spp			S. Enteritidis			S. Typhimurium			S. enterica monophasic			S. Infantis			other serotypes		
	all	M	F	all	M	F	all	M	F	all	M	F	all	M	F	all	M	F
Jan	104	53	51	80	43	37	13	5	8	2	2		0			9	3	6
Feb	99	47	52	60	31	29	13	4	9	2	1	1	0			24	11	13
Mar	137	59	78	77	31	46	16	9	7	7	3	4	5	4	1	32	12	20
Apr	197	110	87	105	55	50	53	29	24	12	9	3	4	2	2	23	15	8
Mai	184	104	80	118	69	49	27	13	14	6	2	4	8	6	2	25	14	11
Jun	297	193	104	138	67	71	131	110	21	5	3	2	2	1	1	21	12	9
Jul	264	128	136	164	78	86	46	24	22	7	2	5	5		5	42	24	18
Aug	336	155	181	251	116	135	31	10	21	7	3	4	8	4	4	39	22	17
Sep	505	265	240	369	179	190	66	47	19	5	5		5	2	3	60	32	28
Oct	291	156	135	185	97	88	47	28	19	8	3	5	7	5	2	44	23	21
Nov	205	109	96	146	78	68	24	10	14	2	2		9	5	4	24	14	10
Dec	156	86	70	114	59	55	15	10	5	1	1		4	3	1	22	13	9
	2,775	1,465	1,310	1,807	903	904	482	299	183	64	36	28	57	32	25	365	195	170

4.1.3. Salmonella spp. in foodstuffs

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Foodstuff was sampled according to the ordinance „Revisions- und Probenplan für das Jahr 2009 gemäß §31 LMSVG; Richtlinien über die Vollziehung der Überwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Berichtsschema 2008“ (BMGFJ – 75500/0332-IV/B/7/2008) from the Federal Ministry of Health. This “Revisions- und Probenplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2007-2010) according to Art. 41 ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004.

The Revision-Plan determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be sampled and tested randomly according to the number of food enterprises per province. Every business within Austria has to be sampled at least once per year. The inspection can comprise sampling, hygienic investigations of the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes etc.

In 2009, approximately 40,000 samples were planned to be tested in Austria. About 60% (24,000) of these are planned samples (surveillance) and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). These planned samples either consist of samples of the yearly sampling plan which determines the number of samples of each food category that have to be investigated randomly, e.g. raw meat (fresh or frozen); sausages; cheeses; milk; preserved food etc. There are different sampling stages where food samples are taken: e.g. from retail, processing plant, primary production.

In addition there is a monitoring plan for food items (40-45 campaigns per year). In the course of these programs food items of special interest for defined parameters – amongst others zoonotic agents – are investigated. The sampling takes place during a fixed period of time in order to gain in-depth information. In 2009, seven relevant food campaign programs were conducted throughout Austria (Schwerpunktprogramm 2009 BMGFJ-75500/0242-IV/B/7/2008). Details and results of these campaigns can be found in the respective chapters.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Campaign A-004-09: Salmonella spp. in food – Infant formula - at retail - Surveillance - official controls - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: January – March

Type of specimen taken

Infant formulas

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of Salmonella spp. in 25g

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up surveillance programs

Results of the investigation

43 samples tested, 0-times positive for Salmonella spp.

Additional information

Samples were also tested for Cronobacter

Campaign A-012-09: Salmonella spp. in food - peanut butter/peanut pasta and products thereof - at retail - Surveillance - official controls - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: January – February

Type of specimen taken

Peanut butter/peanut pasta and products thereof

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of Salmonella spp. in 25g

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up surveillance programs

Results of the investigation

33 samples tested, 0-times positive for Salmonella spp.

Campaign A-801-09: Salmonella spp. in food - Meat from farmed game- land mammals – meat products – fermented sausages - at retail - Surveillance - official controls - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: October – December

Type of specimen taken

Meat from farmed game – fermented sausages

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of Salmonella spp. in 25g

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up surveillance programs

Results of the investigation

85 samples tested, 1-time positive (S. Newport) for Salmonella spp.

Additional information

Samples were also tested for STEC and Listeria monocytogenes

Campaign A-802-09: Salmonella spp. in food - Milk - raw - intended for direct human consumption - at farm (unpasteurised milk vending machine) - Surveillance - official controls - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: April - June

Type of specimen taken

Milk - raw - intended for direct human consumption

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of Salmonella spp. in 25g

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up surveillance programs

Results of the investigation

71 samples tested, 0-time positive for Salmonella spp.

Additional information

Samples were also tested for thermotolerant Campylobacter, STEC and Listeria monocytogenes

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

According to ISO 6579: 1999, with modifications: After preenrichment, selective enrichment in modified semisolid Rappaport-Vassiliadis or Diasalm, 18-24 hours at 42°C. Subsequently plating on XLD agar, Brilliant green-Phenolred-Lactose-Saccharose agar (BPLS), Salmonella Detection and Identification Medium (SMID) or Rambach agar.

25 g of raw material for egg products or 25 g of pooled content of 5 table eggs are either incubated directly or preenriched in peptone water. Further steps are performed as described above.

All isolates are sent to the NRL Salmonella and serotyped according to the Kauffmann-White-Scheme. All *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are phage-typed according to the methods used by HPA, Colindale, UK.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infections:

Salmonella spp. was detected in fresh single broiler meat samples in 3.8 % (4 out of 106), in 11% of fresh turkey meat samples (5/47), and in 3 out of 190 samples (1.57 %) of intended to be eaten cooked meat from broilers. None of the tested bovine meat samples (0/125) tested positive. In all the pig meat samples (fresh and cooked), three of the 1,329 tested single samples (0.2%) were found positive. In fermented sausages from game meat 1 of the 86 samples tested (1.2%) was found positive (Campaign A-801-09).

In 2009, 790 samples from milk, milk products and cheeses (all from cows', sheeps' or goats' milk) were tested for *Salmonella* spp. and no sample was found positive as in the years 2007 and 2008.

Out of the 55 sample units, each containing 25g of table eggs that were sampled and examined at packing centres or at retail level, no sample was tested positive for salmonella.

Table 5 *Salmonella* spp. in poultry meat and meat products

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	S. Bredeney	S. Enteritidis	S. Infantis	S. Indiana	S. Montevideo	S. Newport	S. Saintpaul	S. Tennessee	S. Typhimurium	S. Hadar	S. Virchow	<i>Salmonella</i> spp., unspecified
Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - carcasses		single	25g	212	10		1	5				2		1	1		
Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - fresh	at catering	single	25g	7	0												
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	39	1					1							
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	44	0												
	at retail - imported	single	25g	16	3	1		2									
Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat		single	25g	1	0												
Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked		single	10g	190	3						1	1				1	
Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked		single	10g	5	0												
Meat from poultry, unspecified - fresh	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	24	1										1		
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked	at catering	single	10g	19	0												
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	10g	17	0												
	at retail - domestic production	single	10g	50	1											1	
	at retail - imported	single	10g	11	1		1										
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	15	0												
	at retail - imported	single	25g	7	0												
Meat from turkey - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked		single	10g	1	0												
Meat from turkey - fresh	at catering	single	25g	4	0												
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	13	1							1					
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	30	4							3	1				
Meat from ducks and products thereof		single	10g	1	1				1								
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products	at processing plant - imported	single	25g	3	0												
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	1	0												

Table 6 Salmonella spp. in red meat and products thereof

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Units tested	Total units positive for Salmonella spp.	S. Infantis	S. Typhimurium	S. Newport
Meat from bovine animals - fresh	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	4	0			
	at retail - domestic production	single	10g	17	0			
Meat from bovine animals - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked		single	25g	11	0			
	at catering	single	25g	2	0			
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	10g	18	0			
Meat from bovine animals - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw	at retail - domestic production	single	10g	10	0			
	at catering	single	10g	19	0			
Meat from bovine animals - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	2	0			
	at retail - domestic production	single	10g	20	0			
Meat from bovine animals - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	at retail - domestic production	single	10g	19	0			
	at catering	single	25g	3	0			
Meat from deer (venison) - meat preparation	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	1	0			
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	2	0			
Meat from deer (venison) - meat products	at catering	single	25g	1	0			
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	1	0			
Meat from other animal species or not specified	at retail - domestic production	single	10g	15	0			
	at retail - imported	single	10g	4	0			
	at catering	single	10g	6	0			
	at retail - domestic production	single	10g	20	0			
Meat from pig - fresh		single	25g	23	0			
	at catering	single	10g	3	0			
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	10g	25	0			
Meat from pig - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked	at retail - domestic production	single	10g	117	0			
	at catering	single	10g	9	0			
	at retail	single	10g	185	1		1	
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	16	0			
Meat from pig - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	33	0			
	at catering	single	10g	387	1	1		
	at catering	single	25g	17	0			
Meat from pig - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked		single	10g	5	0			
Meat from pig - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	18	0			
Meat from pig - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked	at retail - domestic production	single	10g	470	1	1		
Meat from pig meat products raw ham		single	25g	1	0			
Meat from sheep - meat preparation	at processing plant - domestic production	single	10g	2	0			
	at retail - domestic production	single	10g	2	0			
Meat from sheep - fresh		single	10g	6	0			
Meat, mixed meat - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked	at retail - domestic production	single	10g	86	0			
Meat, mixed meat - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked frozen		single	25g	3	0			
Meat, mixed meat meat products cooked, ready-to-eat chilled		single	25g	1	0			
Meat, mixed meat minced meat intended to be eaten cooked chilled		single	10g	9	0			
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - fermented sausages	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	18	0			
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	27	0			
Meat from farmed game - land animals - meat products	at game handling establishment	single	25g	8	0			
Meat from wild game - land mammals meat products fermented sausages		single	25g	10	0			
Meat from wild game - land mammals meat products fermented sausages (Campaign A-801-09)	at retail	single	25g	86	1			1
Meat from wild game - land mammals meat products cooked, ready-to-eat chilled		single	25g	1	0			

Table 7 Salmonella spp. in milk and dairy products

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Units tested	Total units positive for Salmonella spp.
Cheeses made from cows' milk - unspecified - made from pasteurised milk	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	45	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	12	0
	at catering	single	25g	22	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - unspecified - made from soft and semi-soft		single	25g	3	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - unspecified - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	45	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	23	0
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - unspecified - made from pasteurised milk	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	22	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	6	0
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - unspecified - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	14	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	3	0
Cheeses, made from goat milk - unspecified (and sheep milk)		single	25g	13	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - butter	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	10	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	6	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - butter made from raw or low heat-treated milk		single	25g	4	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy desserts	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	7	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy products, not specified	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	44	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	12	0
	at catering	single	25g	19	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - ice-cream	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	171	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	47	0
	at catering	single	25g	41	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - cream made from pasteurised milk	at catering	single	25g	66	0
Milk, cows' - pasteurised milk	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	30	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	6	0
Milk, cows' - raw	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	11	0
	at farm	single	25g	15	0
Milk, cows' - raw milk for manufacture - intended for manufacture of raw or low heat-treated products	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	11	0
Milk - raw - intended for direct human consumption (Campaign A-802-09)	at farm (unpasteurised milk vending machine)	single	25g	71	0
Milk, sheep's - raw (and goat)	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	4	0
Chocolate	at retail	single	25g	7	0

Table 8 Salmonella spp. in other food

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling unit	Sample weight	nicht nachweisbar	Units tested	Total units positive for Salmonella spp.
Bakery products - cakes	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	37	37	0
	at catering	single	25g	10	10	0
Bakery products - pastry	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	88	88	0
	at catering	single	25g	13	13	0
Chocolate	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	2	2	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	10	10	0
Cocoa and cocoa preparations, coffee and tea	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	14	14	0
Crustaceans	at retail - imported	single	25g	5	5	0
Egg products	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	1	1	0
	at retail - imported	single	25g	1	1	0
Egg products - dried	at retail - imported	single	25g	2	2	0
Egg products - liquid	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	16	16	0
	at retail - imported	single	25g	8	8	0
Eggs - table eggs	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	28	28	0
	at catering	single	25g	2	2	0
	at packing centre	single	25g	25	25	0
Fishery products, unspecified	at retail - domestic production	single	10g	11	11	0
Fishery products - cooked		single	25g	3	3	0
Foodstuffs intended for special nutritional uses	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	6	6	0
Fruits - products	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	4	4	0
Fruits products - fruit purée	at catering	single	25g	1	1	0
Fruits pre-cut ready-to-eat	at catering	single	25g	7	7	0
Infant formula	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	4	4	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	38	38	0
Infant formula - (Campaign A-004-09)	at retail	single	25g	43	43	0
Juice - fruit juice	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	16	16	0
Juice - fruit juice - unpasteurised	at catering	single	25g	10	10	0
Juice - vegetable juice - unpasteurised	at catering	single	25g	5	5	0
Juice - mixed juice - unpasteurised	at catering	single	25g	3	3	0
Mushrooms	at catering	single	25g	8	8	0
Nuts and nut products	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	14	14	0
Peanut butter/Peanut pasta and products thereof (Campaign A-012-09)	at retail	single	25g	33	33	0
Other food	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	63	63	0
	at retail	single	10g	26	26	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	89	89	0
	at retail - imported	single	25g	30	30	0
	at catering	single	25g	448	448	0
Other food of non-animal origin		single	50g	91	91	0
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	14	14	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	16	16	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - pasta	at catering	single	25g	4	4	0
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	39	39	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - containing raw egg	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	30	30	0
Ready-to-eat salads	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	19	19	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	21	21	0
	at catering	single	25g	29	29	0
Sauces and dressings	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	3	3	0
	at catering	single	25g	3	3	0
Soups	at catering	single	50g	2	2	0
Spices and herbs	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	24	24	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	32	32	0
	at retail - imported	single	25g	45	45	0
	at catering	single	25g	5	5	0
Sweets	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	3	3	0
Vegetables	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	7	7	0
	at retail - imported	single	25g	7	7	0
	at catering	single	25g	3	3	0
Vegetables - products	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	4	4	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	7	7	0
	at catering	single	25g	7	7	0
Vegetables - products dried	at catering	single	25g	1	1	0

4.1.4. Salmonella spp. in animals

A. Salmonella spp. in Gallus gallus - breeding flocks

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

There are only parent flocks in Austria. The permanent monitoring plan performed by a national program takes place at hatcheries; each flock is tested regularly as well by the farmer as by the Veterinary Authorities.

If *S. Enteritidis*, *S. Typhimurium*, *S. Infantis*, *S. Hadar* and *S. Virchow* or *S. Pullorum Gallinarum* is isolated from breeding flocks at the hatchery the flock is banned and a sample of 20 birds at random from within the incriminated flock has to be taken. The inner organs, such as ovaries, liver and the intestinal content are investigated.

If a parent flock tests positive for other salmonellas, official veterinarians are required to take pooled faeces samples from the flock being investigated. In the event of a second positive result for *Salmonella* spp. within a two week period, then organs from a minimum of 20 chickens must be tested.

Frequency of the sampling

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Day-old chicks

Other: Not applicable. There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks! Every flock is tested at day one

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Rearing period

Other: Not applicable. There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

1. Routine testing: Every flock is tested at the age of 4 and 12 weeks and 2 weeks before the laying period starts.

2. Confirmation: If routine testing reveals positive *Salmonella* test results then follow-up test must be performed from the identical flock.

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Production period

Other: Not applicable. There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

Monitoring by national program, takes place at hatchery, each flock is tested every two weeks at hatch by the farmer, and every 16 weeks by the Veterinary Authorities; additionally each flock is tested every 4 weeks by the farmer by boot swabs.

Type of specimen taken

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Day-old chicks

Other: Not applicable. There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks! Visibly soiled hatcher basket liners, dead chicks if available

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Rearing period

Other: Not applicable. There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!
Routine testing: drag swabs, pooled faeces. For confirmation: organs as ovaries, liver and intestinal content from a minimum of 20 chickens.

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Production period

Other: Not applicable. There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!
Routine testing: Drag swabs, pooled faeces and dust in the hatchery, meconium, broken eggshells and hatched eggs. For confirmation: 300 faeces samples and up to inner organs of 5 chickens or intestinal content of 5 chickens were pooled.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Day-old chicks

Not applicable. There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks! Visibly soiled hatcher basket liners, dead chicks if available

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Rearing period

Not applicable. There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks! Routine testing: 60 pooled droppings a 1gram per flock, collection of dust. For confirmation: Diagnostically killing of 20 random chickens from within the incriminated flock

Breeding flocks: Production period

Not applicable. There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!
Routine testing: 1 drag swab, pooled faeces, collection of dust. For confirmation: Diagnostically killing of 20 random chickens from within the incriminated flock

Case definition

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Day-old chicks

Not applicable. There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!
Routine testing: Salmonella spp. isolated from hatcher basket liners

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Rearing period

Not applicable. There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!
Salmonella spp. isolated from inner organs or from content of intestines of chickens killed for diagnosis

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Production period

Not applicable. There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!
Salmonella spp. isolated from inner organs or from content of intestines of chicken

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Day-old chicks

Other: Not applicable. There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!
Sample material is incubated in liquid medium. Modification of ISO 6579 (2002), where a semi solid medium (MSRV) is used as the single selective enrichment medium. The semi solid medium is incubated at 41.5+/- 1°C for 2-times 24 hours. Suspected samples are subcultured on solid media like xld or sm2. All isolates are sent to the NRL Salmonella and serotyped according to the Kauffmann-White-Scheme. All S.

Enteritidis and S. Typhimurium isolates are lysotyped according to the methods used by HPA, Colindale, UK.

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Rearing period

Other: See day old chicks

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Production period

Other: See day old chicks

Vaccination policy

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Not applicable. There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks! The national program for parent flocks made vaccination against Salmonella Enteritidis mandatory for all flocks

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Nil

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Not applicable. There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks! The Austrian control program is conducted according to the National Poultry Hygiene Regulation (BGBl. I Nr. 6/2007, Geflügelhygieneverordnung 2007 as amended). The Austrian program for monitoring and eradication of Salmonella in breeding flocks of poultry was again (already since 2000) approved for the year 2006 by Commission Decision 2005/887/EG of 12 December 2005.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Not applicable. There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

Measures according to the National Poultry Hygiene Regulation:

- Banning of the incriminated sector of the holding
- Culling of the infected flock
- Disposal of the hatched eggs
- Abolishing of the restriction after cleaning and disinfection
- If necessary prescriptions of GMP to prevent re-infection

Notification system in place

All positive results from parent flocks must be reported to the local authorities and via the Austrian Poultry Health Service to the Federal Ministry of Health (BMG).

Results of the investigation

See table

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2009, out of the five relevant serotypes only one flock positive for *S. Enteritidis* was detected (< 1%) and the flock was culled. This flock was also positive for *S. Montevideo*. Another flock was positive for *S. Rissen*; a strict hygiene program was conducted and the serotype could not be found any more.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

B. *Salmonella* spp. in *Gallus gallus* - flocks of laying hens

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Laying hens flocks

At the earliest 3 weeks prior to slaughter, two pairs of boot swabs must be taken from each flock. Since May 2007, every flock has been tested in accordance to regulation 1168/2006.

Frequency of the sampling

Laying hens: Day-old chicks

Other: No legal requirements, e.g. at day one of each flock

Laying hens: Rearing period

3 times at day one, week 8 to 12 and 2 weeks before the laying period start

Laying hens: Production period

Each flock is tested every 15 weeks with two pairs of boot swabs; an official veterinarian is testing every flock once a year according to regulation 1168/2006.

Laying hens: Before slaughter at farm

Other: 3 weeks before slaughter at farm with two pairs of boot swabs

Laying hens: At slaughter

Other: Not applicable. no sampling

Eggs at packing centre (flock based approach)

Other: according to the program of the cooperatives voluntary surface swabs (e.g. every eight weeks)

Type of specimen taken

Laying hens: Day-old chicks

Other: no legal requirements, e.g. visibly soiled hatcher basket liners

Laying hens: Rearing period

Other: no legal requirements, e.g. pooled feces

Laying hens: Production period

Other: no legal requirements, e.g. pooled feces or drag swabs

Laying hens: Before slaughter at farm

Other: two pairs of boot swabs per flock

Laying hens: At slaughter

Other: no sampling

Eggs at packing centre (flock based approach)

Other: Voluntary e.g. surface swabs

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Laying hens: Day-old chicks

No legal requirements, e.g. visibly soiled hatcher basket liners

Laying hens: Rearing period

2 pair of boot swabs per flock

Laying hens: Production period

2 pair of boot swabs per flock

Laying hens: Before slaughter at farm

Two pairs of boot swabs per flock

Laying hens: At slaughter

No sampling

Eggs at packing centre (flock based approach)

No legal requirements, e.g. surface swabs

Case definition

Laying hens: Day-old chicks

No legal requirements, e.g. Salmonella spp. isolated from hatcher basket liners

Laying hens: Rearing period

No legal requirements

Laying hens: Production period

No legal requirements

Laying hens: Before slaughter at farm

Salmonella spp. isolated from boot swabs

Laying hens: At slaughter

No sampling

Eggs at packing centre (flock based approach)

Salmonella spp. isolated from surface swabs

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Laying hens: Day-old chicks

Other: Sample material is incubated in liquid medium. Modification of ISO 6579 (2002), where a semi solid medium (MSRV) is used as the single selective enrichment medium. The semi solid medium is incubated at 41.5 +/- 1 °C for 2-times 24 hours. Suspected samples are subcultured on solid media like xld or sm2. All isolates are sent to the NRL Salmonella and serotyped according to the Kauffmann-White-Scheme. All S.

Enteritidis and S. Typhimurium isolates are lysotyped according to the methods used by HPA, Colindale, UK.

Laying hens: Rearing period

Other: See laying hens, day old chicks.

Laying hens: Production period

Other: See laying hens, day old chicks.

Laying hens: Before slaughter at farm

Other: See laying hens, day old chicks.

Laying hens: At slaughter

Other: no testing

Eggs at packing centre (flock based approach)

Other: See laying hens, day old chicks.

Vaccination policy

Laying hens flocks

The national program made vaccination against Salmonella Enteritidis mandatory for all flocks

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Laying hens flocks

Nil

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Laying hens flocks

The Austrian control program is conducted according to the National Poultry Hygiene Regulation (BGBl. I Nr. 6/2007, Geflügelhygieneverordnung 2007 as amended).

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

All actions according to EU- and national legislation

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Laying hens flocks

No class A eggs or culling in case of association with a food borne outbreak

Notification system in place

All positive results from parent flocks must be reported to the local authorities and via the Austrian Poultry Health Service to the Federal Ministry of Health (BMG).

Results of the investigation

See table

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2009, *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* were detected in 64 flocks (2.5 %). The excellent result from the previous year 2008 (< 2 %) could not be reached in 2009.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

C. *Salmonella* spp. in *Gallus gallus* - broiler flocks

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Broiler flocks

Earliest 3 weeks prior to slaughter boot swabs have to be taken. Other programs are not foreseen, only voluntary sampling by the farmer or sampling according to private cooperatives is performed.

Frequency of the sampling

Broiler flocks: Day-old chicks

Other: no legal requirements, e.g. at day one each flock

Broiler flocks: Rearing period

Other: no legal requirements

Broiler flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Other: 3 weeks before slaughter at farm 2 pairs of boot swabs 10 % of the flocks by competent authority, Regulation EU 646/2007 is in force since 01.01.2009

Broiler flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

Other: No sampling

Type of specimen taken

Broiler flocks: Day-old chicks

Other: no legal requirements, e.g. visibly soiled hatcher basket liners

Broiler flocks: Rearing period

Other: no legal requirements, e.g. pooled feces

Broiler flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Other: two pairs of boot swabs per flock; 10 % of the flocks sampled by competent authority, Regulation EU 646/2007 is in force since 01.01.2009

Broiler flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

Other: No sampling

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Broiler flocks: Day-old chicks

No legal requirements, e.g. visibly soiled hatcher basket liners

Broiler flocks: Rearing period

Other: no legal requirements, e.g. pooled faeces

Broiler flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Other: two pairs of boot swabs per flock; 10 % of the flocks sampled by competent authority, Regulation EU 646/2007 is in force since 01.01.2009

Broiler flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

No sampling

Case definition

Broiler flocks: Day-old chicks

No legal requirements

Broiler flocks: Rearing period

No legal requirements

Broiler flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Salmonella spp. isolated from boot swabs

Broiler flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

No sampling

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Broiler flocks: Day-old chicks

Other: Sample material is incubated in liquid medium. Modification of ISO 6579 (2002), where a semi solid medium (MSRV) is used as the single selective enrichment medium. The semi solid medium is incubated at 41.5 +/- 1 °C for 2-times 24 hours. Suspected samples are subcultured on solid media like xld or sm2. All isolates are sent to the NRL Salmonella and serotyped according to the Kauffmann-White-Scheme. All S. Enteritidis and S. Typhimurium isolates are lysotyped according to the methods used by HPA, Colindale, UK.

Broiler flocks: Rearing period

Other: See day-old chicks

Broiler flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Other: See day-old chicks

Broiler flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

Other: no testing

Vaccination policy

Broiler flocks

Neither legal requirements nor recommendations

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Broiler flocks

Nil

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Broiler flocks

The Austrian control program is conducted according to the National Poultry Hygiene Regulation (BGBl. I Nr. 6/2007, Geflügelhygieneverordnung 2007 as amended)

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Broiler flocks: Day-old chicks

Competitive exclusion strategies takes place.

Broiler flocks: Rearing period

Competitive exclusion strategies takes place.

Broiler flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Competitive exclusion strategies takes place. Logistic Slaughtering is permitted for Salmonella spp. positive flocks

Broiler flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

No testing

Notification system in place

All positive findings in parent flocks had to be notified to the local authority and via the Austrian Poultry Health Service to the Federal Ministry of Health.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2009, S. Enteritidis or S. Typhimurium was detected in 35 flocks (1.1 %) flocks. The target set in COMMISSION REGULATION (EC) No 646/2007 (a reduction of the maximum percentage of flocks of broilers remaining positive of S. Enteritidis and S. Typhimurium to 1 % or less by 31 December 2011) was already achieved in 2009.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

D. Salmonella spp. in turkey - meat production flocks

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Meat production flocks

Earliest 3 weeks prior to slaughter boot swabs have to be taken. Other programs are not foreseen, only voluntary sampling by the farmer or sampling according to private cooperatives is performed.

Frequency of the sampling

Meat production flocks: Day-old chicks

Other: no legal requirements, e.g. at day one each flock

Meat production flocks: Rearing period

Other: no legal requirements

Meat production flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Other: 3 weeks before slaughter at farm

Meat production flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

Other: No sampling

Type of specimen taken

Meat production flocks: Day-old chicks

Other: no legal requirements, e.g. visibly soiled hatcher basket liners

Meat production flocks: Rearing period

Other: no legal requirements, e.g. pooled feces

Meat production flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Other: two pairs of boot swabs per flock

Meat production flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

Other: no sampling

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Meat production flocks: Day-old chicks

No sampling

Meat production flocks: Rearing period

No legal requirements

Meat production flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Two pairs of boot swabs per flock

Meat production flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

No sampling

Case definition

Meat production flocks: Day-old chicks

No legal requirements

Meat production flocks: Rearing period

No legal requirements

Meat production flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Salmonella spp. isolated from boot swabs

Meat production flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

No sampling

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Meat production flocks: Day-old chicks

Other: Sample material is incubated in liquid medium. Modification of ISO 6579 (2002), where a semi solid medium (MSRV) is used as the single selective enrichment medium. The semi solid medium is incubated at 41.5 +/- 1 °C for 2-times 24 hours. Suspected samples are subcultured on solid media like xld or sm2. All

isolates are sent to the NRL Salmonella and serotyped according to the Kauffmann-White-Scheme. All *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are lysotyped according to the methods used by HPA, Colindale, UK.

Meat production flocks: Rearing period

Other: see day-old chicks

Meat production flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Other: see day-old chicks

Meat production flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

Other: see day-old chicks

Vaccination policy

Meat production flocks

Neither legal requirements nor recommendations

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Meat production flocks

Nil

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Meat production flocks

The Austrian control program is conducted according to the National Poultry Hygiene Regulation (BGBl. I Nr. 6/2007, Geflügelhygieneverordnung 2007 as amended).

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Notification not mandatory

Notification system in place

Notification not mandatory

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Low prevalence of *S. Enteritidis* or *S. Typhimurium* (0%) in met production turkey flocks

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

In 2009 *S. Enteritidis* or *S. Typhimurium* was not detected in turkey flocks in control program (before slaughter), therefor the relevance seems to be low.

Table 9 Salmonella spp. in Poultry breeding flocks (*Gallus gallus*)

Animal species	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Sampling Details	Source of information	Sampling unit	Number of existing flocks	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<i>S. Enteritidis</i>	<i>S. Typhimurium</i>	<i>S. Hadar</i>	<i>S. Infantis</i>	<i>S. Virchow</i>	<i>S. Montevideo</i>	<i>S. Rissen</i>
Egg production line															
Breeding flocks															
	Elite														
	Grandparents														
	Parents														
	Day-old chicks														
	Rearing period	at farm - animal sample - faeces	control or eradication programmes - cofinanced by Community - official and industry sampling	QGV	flock	6	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Production period	at farm - animal sample - faeces	control or eradication programmes - cofinanced by Community - official and industry sampling	QGV	flock	30	30	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Meat production line															
Breeding flocks															
	Elite														
	Grandparents														
	Parents														
	Day-old chicks														
	Rearing period	at farm - animal sample - faeces	control or eradication programmes - cofinanced by Community - official and industry sampling	QGV	flock	45	45	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Production period	at farm - animal sample - faeces	control or eradication programmes - cofinanced by Community - official and industry sampling	QGV	flock	90	90	1*	1	0	0	0	0	1	0

QGV = Austrian Health Poultry Service

* two different serotypes in the flock

Table 10 Salmonella spp. in other commercial poultry

Animal species	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Source of information	Sampling unit	Numbr of existing flocks	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<i>S. Enteritidis</i>	<i>S. Typhimurium</i>	<i>S. Abony</i>	<i>S. Agona</i>	<i>S. Bovismorbificans</i>	<i>S. Braenderup</i>	<i>S. Gera</i>	<i>S. Hadar</i>	<i>S. Heidelberg</i>	<i>S. Indiana</i>	<i>S. Infantis</i>	<i>S. Kentucky</i>	<i>S. Lexington</i>	<i>S. Livingstone</i>	<i>S. Mbandaka</i>	<i>S. Meleagridis</i>	Monophasische Salmonella der C2-Gruppe 6,8 : e,h : -	Monophasische Salmonella der B-Gruppe 1,4,5,12 : i : -	Monophasische Stamm der E1-Gruppe 3,10 : y : -	Monophasische Stamm der E1-Gruppe 3,15 : y : -	<i>S. Montevideo</i>	<i>S. Newport</i>	<i>S. Isangi</i>	<i>S. Rissen</i>	<i>S. Saintpaul</i>	<i>S. Senftenberg</i>	<i>S. Thomson</i>	<i>S. Worthington</i>	<i>S. IlIb 38 : r : z (diarizonae)</i>	Salmonella spp. unspecified		
Gallus gallus (fowl)																																							
Rearing period	At farm		QGV	flock	466	466	7				1		1			2	2																						
Production period	At farm	control or eradication programme – official and industry sampling	QGV	flock	2578	2578	86	47	17		1		2	2	1		1	5	1		2	1		1					1	2			2	3	2				
Production period	At farm	control or eradication programme – sampling by industry – census sampling	QGV	flock	2578	2254	34	19	5				1	1	1		1	3			3			1					1	1			1	1					
Production period	At farm	control or eradication programme – official sampling – objective sampling	QGV	flock	2578	1501	46	22	11		1		1	1				3	1							1				1			1	2	2				
Production period	At farm	control or eradication programme – official sampling – suspective sampling	QGV	flock	2578	56	18	16	2																														
Broiler																																							
Rearing period	At farm	control or eradication programme – official and industry sampling	QGV	flock	3302	3302	112	24	11			1		1	1		2	5	5	1		2	3		1		1	46				1	1						
Turkey																																							
Meat production flocks	At farm	control or eradication programme – official and industry sampling	QGV	flock	353	353	25			1	2				1		1		5				1				1	1					11					1	
Ducks																																							
Meat production flocks	At farm	control or eradication programme – official and industry sampling	QGV	flock		30	5									2							1			1												1	
Geese																																							
Meat production flocks	At farm	control or eradication programme – official and industry sampling	QGV	flock		3	1																													1			

Table 11 Salmonella in other animals

Animal Species	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Units tested	Total units positive	S. Abony	S. Agona	S. Apapa	S. Brandenburg	S. Choleraesuis	S. Derby	S. Dublin	S. Enteritidis	S. Hadar	S. II 30 : l,z28 : z6	S. IIIb 61 : k : 1,5,7	S. Indiana	S. Tennessee	S. Thompson	S. Typhimurium	S. Weltevreden	Salmonellen IIIb
Bison	at farm - animal sample - organs	clinical investigation	1	1															1		
Boar	at farm - animal sample - organs	clinical investigation	4	2					2												
Budgerigar	at farm - animal sample - organs	clinical investigation	2	1																	
Canary	at farm - animal sample - organs	clinical investigation	7	1															1		
Capricorn	at farm - animal sample - organs	clinical investigation	1	0																	
Cat	at farm - animal sample	clinical investigation	1	0																	
	at farm - animal sample - faeces	clinical investigation	9	0																	
	at farm - animal sample - organs	clinical investigation	34	2								1									1
Cattle	at farm - animal sample	clinical investigation	18	0																	
	at farm - animal sample - faeces	clinical investigation	69	0																	
	at farm - animal sample - organs	clinical investigation	192	4							4										
	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - carcass swab	clinical investigation	11	0																	
	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - organs	clinical investigation	2747	8				1			3									4	
Deer	at farm - animal sample - organs	clinical investigation	23	1																1	
	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - organs	clinical investigation	1	0																	
Dog	at farm - animal sample	clinical investigation	3	0																	
	at farm - animal sample - faeces	clinical investigation	13	0																	
	at farm - animal sample - organs	clinical investigation	19	0																	
Duck	at farm - animal sample	clinical investigation	2	2								1								1	
	at farm - animal sample - faeces	clinical investigation	2	1								1									
	at farm - animal sample - organs	clinical investigation	9	0																	
Eagle	at farm - animal sample - faeces	clinical investigation	1	0																	
	at farm - animal sample - organs	clinical investigation	1	0																	
Finch	at farm - animal sample - organs	clinical investigation	4	1																1	
Fox	at farm - animal sample	clinical investigation	16	4									2							2	

Salmonellosis

Animal Species	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Units tested	Total units positive																		
				S. Abony	S. Agona	S. Apapa	S. Brandenburg	S. Choleraesuis	S. Derby	S. Dublin	S. Enteritidis	S. Hadar	S. II 30 : l,z28 : z6	S. IIIb 61 : k : 1,5,7	S. Indiana	S. Tennessee	S. Thompson	S. Typhimurium	S. Weltevreden	Salmonellen IIIb		
	at farm - animal sample - organs	clinical investigation	53	1																		
Rat	at farm - animal sample - organs	clinical investigation	1	0																		
Red deer	at farm - animal sample - organs	clinical investigation	3	0																		
Sheep	at farm - animal sample	clinical investigation	1	0																		
	at farm - animal sample - faeces	clinical investigation	4	0																		
	at farm - animal sample - organs	clinical investigation	78	12									2								10	
	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - carcass swab	clinical investigation	5	0																		
	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - organs	clinical investigation	2	0																		
Starling	at farm - animal sample - organs	clinical investigation	1	0																		
Turtle	at farm - animal sample - organs	clinical investigation	1	0																		
Wildcat	at farm - animal sample - organs	clinical investigation	1	0																		
Wild bird	at farm - animal sample	clinical investigation	6	1																	1	
	at farm - animal sample - faeces	clinical investigation	8	6			5														1	
	at farm - animal sample - organs	clinical investigation	37	2												1					1	
Peafowl	at farm - animal sample - organs	clinical investigation	6	0																		
Reptile	at farm - animal sample	clinical investigation	2	0																		
	at farm - animal sample - faeces	clinical investigation	4	2									1									1

4.1.5. Salmonella spp. in feedstuffs

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Official monitoring based on risk assessment, own check programme by the industry based on HACCP.

Frequency of the sampling

Domestic feed material of plant origin

Assigned sampling plan, random samples are collected based on an official surveillance programme.

Domestic feed material of animal origin

Other: See above

Imported feed material of plant origin

Other: See above

Imported feed material of animal origin

Other: See above

Process control in feed mills

Other: See above

Compound feeding stuffs

Other: See above

Type of specimen taken

Domestic feed material of plant origin

Feed material of cereal grain and oil seed or fruit origin

Domestic feed material of animal origin

Fish meal, dried animal by-products for pets

Imported feed material of plant origin

Oil seed meals and cakes

Imported feed material of animal origin

Fish meal, dried animal by-products for pets

Process control in feed mills

Not applicable (n. a.)

Compound feeding stuffs

Feed for poultry

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Domestic feed material of plant origin

Sampling is performed according EC-Directive 76/371/EEC applying special hygiene requirements or sampling of original packaged products.

Domestic feed material of animal origin

See above

Imported feed material of plant origin

See above

Imported feed material of animal origin

See above

Process control in feed mills

See above

Compound feeding stuffs

See above

Definition of positive finding

Domestic feed material of plant origin

Salmonella spp. isolated from the sample

Domestic feed material of animal origin

Salmonella spp. isolated from the sample

Imported feed material of plant origin

Salmonella spp. isolated from the sample

Imported feed material of animal origin

Salmonella spp. isolated from the sample

Process control in feed mills

Salmonella spp. isolated from the sample

Compound feeding stuffs

Salmonella spp. isolated from the sample

Diagnostic/analytical methods used**Domestic feed material of plant origin**

Bacteriological method: ISO 6579:2002; sample weight: 50 g; all isolates are sent to the NRL Salmonella and are serotyped according to the Kauffmann-White-Scheme. All *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are lysotyped according to the methods used by HPA, Colindale, UK.

Domestic feed material of animal origin

Other: as above

Imported feed material of plant animal

Other: as above

Imported feed material of animal origin

Other: as above

Process control in feed mills

Other: as above

Compound feeding stuffs

Other: as above

Control program/mechanisms**The control program/strategies in place**

National legislation: BGBl. Nr. 139/1999 (Futtermittelgesetz 1999, § 3) and BGBl. Nr. 93/2000 (Futtermittelverordnung 2000, as amended) containing general requirements for feedingstuffs and BGBl. II Nr. 243/2000 (Geflügelhygieneverordnung 2000).
EC: VO (EG) 1831/2003 (Futtermittelhygieneverordnung) and VO (EG) 853/2004 (Kontrollverordnung) with regard to salmonella monitoring, general requirements for feed material and compound feed, coordinated annual control program

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings**Domestic feed material of plant origin**

In the event of a positive result, the notification results in the confiscation of the infected feedingstuffs according to official measures. This includes the withdrawal of the feedingstuffs from the market, the recall of feed, decontamination of the feed, disposal or other use of the feed, exploration and elimination of the sources of contamination and operational measures to prevent future contaminations.

Domestic feed material of animal origin

See above

Imported feed material of plant origin

See above

Imported feed material of animal origin

See above

Process control in feed mills

See above

Compound feeding stuffs

See above

Notification system in place

The Rapid Alert System for Food and Feed (RASFF) notifies the local authorities and the system has been in place since 1979. The legal basis of the RASFF is Regulation EC/178/2002.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In the last 20 years, the quality of feed has improved due to the increase of numbers of farms, processing plants and retailer using HACCP concepts, traceability of contaminated feed/components of feed and palletizing feed/contaminated feed.

Additional information

Nil

Table 12 Salmonella spp. in feed material of animal origin

Feed	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	source of information	sample unit	sample weight	Units tested	Total units positive for Salmonella spp.
Feed material of land animal origin - blood products	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	1	0
Feed material of marine animal origin - fish meal	at processing plant	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	5	0
	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	5	0
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	7	0
	at retail - imported	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	2	0
Feed material of marine animal origin - fish oil	at processing plant	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	1	0
	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	1	0

*) Compulsory monitoring programmes (Futtermittel-Gesetz 1999), AGES Institute for Agricultural Analysis Linz

Table 13 Salmonella spp. in compound feeding stuff

Feed	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	source of information	sample unit	sample weight	Units tested	Total units positive for Salmonella spp.	S. Agona	S. New port	S. Typhimurium	S. Weltevreden
Compound feedingstuffs for fish - final product - non-pelleted/meal	at farm - feed sample	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	1	0				
	at farm - feed sample	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	2	0				
Compound feedingstuffs for pigs - final product - non-pelleted/meal	at feed mill - domestic production	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	3	0				
	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	3	0				
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	10	0				
	at retail - imported	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	3	0				
Compound feedingstuffs for pigs - final product - pelleted	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	1	0				
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry - broilers - final product - non-pelleted/meal	at farm - feed sample	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	3	0				
	at feed mill - domestic production	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	1	0				
	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	1	0				
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	3	0				
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry - broilers - final product - pelleted	at farm - feed sample	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	5	0				
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	3	0				
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry - laying hens final product - non-pelleted/meal	at farm - feed sample	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	19	0				
	at feed mill - domestic production	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	3	0				
	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	2	0				
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry - laying hens final product - pelleted	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	5	0				
	at farm - feed sample	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	1	0				
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry (non specified) - final product - non-pelleted/meal	at farm - feed sample	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	8	0				
	at feed mill - domestic production	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	2	0				
	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	3	0				
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	4	0				
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry (non specified) - final product - pelleted	at farm - feed sample	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	1	0				
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	1	0				
Compound feedingstuffs, not specified - final product - non-pelleted/meal	at farm - feed sample	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	1	0				
	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	2	1	1			
Pet food - dog snacks (pig ears, chewing bones)	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	33	1			1	
	at retail - imported	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	7	2**	1	1		1
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	5	0				
Pet food - final product - non-pelleted/meal	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	5	0				
	at retail - imported	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	1	0				

*) Compulsory monitoring programmes (Futtermittel-Gesetz 1999), AGES Institute for Agricultural Analysis Linz

***) two different serotypes in one sample

Table 14 Salmonella spp. in other feed matter

Feed	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	source of information	sample unit	sample weight	Units tested	Total units positive for Salmonella spp.
Complementary feedingstuffs - final product - non-pelleted/meal	at farm - feed sample	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	18	0
	at feed mill - domestic production	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	1	0
	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	6	0
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	18	0
	at retail - imported	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	3	0
Complementary feedingstuffs - final product - pelleted	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	3	0
Feed material of cereal grain origin	at farm - feed sample	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	1	0
Feed material of cereal grain origin - wheat derived	at farm - feed sample	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	1	0
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin - linseed derived	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	2	0
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin - other	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	1	0
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin - other oil seeds derived	at processing plant	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	1	0
	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	1	0
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	1	0
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin - rape seed derived	at farm - feed sample	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	3	0
	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	3	0
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	12	0
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin - soya (bean) derived	at farm - feed sample	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	6	0
	at feed mill - domestic production	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	1	0
	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	2	0
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	23	0
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin - sunflower seed derived	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	3	0
Premixtures - final product - non-pelleted/meal	at processing plant - domestic production	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	1	0
	at retail - domestic production	Surveillance - official control - objective sampling	*	batch	50 g	1	0

* Compulsory monitoring programmes (Futtermittel-Gesetz 1999), AGES Institute for Agricultural Analysis Linz

4.1.6. Salmonella serovars and phage type distribution

The methods of collecting, isolating and testing of the Salmonella isolates are described in the chapters above respectively for each animal species, foodstuffs and in humans. The serotype and phage type distributions can be used to investigate the sources of the Salmonella infections in humans. Findings of same serovars and phagetypes in human cases and in foodstuffs or animals may indicate that the food category or animal species in question serves as a source of human infections. However, as information is not available from all potential sources of infections, conclusions have to be made with caution.

Table 15 Salmonella serovars in humans, food and animals (alphabetical order)

Serotype	human	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus)	Beef	Pork	Tturkey meat	Gallus gallus, fowl	Cattle	Pigs	Turkey
total	2775	52	2	1	27	673	15	38	174
S. Abony	12	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Adelaide	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Agama	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Agona	14	-	-	-	-	3	-	1	12
S. Albany	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Altona	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Anatum	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Anecho	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Bareilly	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Berta	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Bispebjerg	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Blockley	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Bovismorbificans	9	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-
S. Braenderup	6	-	-	-	-	4	-	-	-
S. Brandenburg	8	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-
S. Bredeney	5	1	-	-	-	9	-	-	-
S. Brunei	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Cerro	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Choleraesuis	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Coeln	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Colindale	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Concord	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Corvallis	9	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Cotham	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Derby	5	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	-
S. Dublin	-	-	-	-	-	-	7	-	-
S. Duesseldorf	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Ekotedo	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. enterica monophasic	64	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Enteritidis	1807	3	-	-	-	238	1	1	1
S. Ferruch	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Serotype	human	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus)	Beef	Pork	Tturkey meat	Gallus gallus, fowl	Cattle	Pigs	Turkey
S. Fluntern	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Gallinarum	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-
S. Georgia	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Gera	-	-	-	-	-	5	-	-	-
S. Give	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Hadar	22	1	-	-	4	22	-	1	9
S. Haifa	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Havana	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Heidelberg	9	-	-	-	-	3	-	-	-
S. Idikan	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Illb 38 : r : z	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-
S. Indiana	-	1	-	-	-	13	-	-	-
S. Infantis	57	25	-	-	1	138	-	-	4
S. Isangi	1	-	-	-	-	6	-	-	-
S. Jangwani	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Javiana	4	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Kentucky	12	-	-	-	-	15	-	-	-
S. Kottbus	8	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	11
S. Lattenkamp	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Lexington	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-
S. Litchfield	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Liverpool	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Livingstone	4	-	-	-	-	3	-	1	-
S. London	7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Marina	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Mbandaka	5	1	-	-	-	5	-	-	2
S. Meleagridis	2	-	-	-	-	5	-	-	-
S. Mikawasima	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Mishmarhaemek	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. monophasic Group B (1,4,12 : d : -)	-	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. monophasic Group B (1,4,5,12 : i : -)	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-
S. monophasic Group C2 (6,8 : e,h : -)	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	1
S. monophasic Group E1 (3,10 : y : -)	-	-	-	-	-	2	-	-	-
S. monophasic S. Group E1 (3,15 : y : -)	-	-	-	-	-	2	-	-	-
S. Monschau	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Montevideo	7	1	-	-	-	65	-	-	2
S. Muenchen	10	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-
S. Muenster	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Napoli	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Nchanga	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Newport	11	-	-	-	4	4	-	-	13
S. Ohio	2	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	3

Serotype	human	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus)	Beef	Pork	Tturkey meat	Gallus gallus, fowl	Cattle	Pigs	Turkey
S. Oranienburg	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Orion	1	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-
S. Oslo	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Overschie	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Panama	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Paratyphi B var. Java	-	-	-	-	-	2	-	-	-
S. Paratyphi B var. L(+) tartrate+	15	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Poona	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Potsdam	5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Reading	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Regent	-	-	-	-	-	2	-	-	-
S. Richmond	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Rissen	4	-	-	-	-	4	-	9	1
S. Saintpaul	27	8	2	-	15	15	1	-	111
S. Sandiego	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Schwarzengrund	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Senftenberg	3	1	-	-	-	12	-	3	3
S. Stanley	11	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Subspl	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. SubsplIIIa	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. SubsplIIIb	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. SubsplIV	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Teitelkebir	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Tennessee	4	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-
S. Thompson	10	-	-	-	-	16	1	-	-
S. Typhimurium	482	5	-	1	1	68	4	20	1
S. Uganda	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Urbana	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Veneziana	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Virchow	19	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Weltevreden	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Worthington	-	-	-	-	-	4	-	-	-

Table 16 S. Enteritidis phage types in humans, food and animals

SE phage type	Human	Broiler meat (gallus gallus)	Beef	Pork	Turkey meat	Gallus gallus (fowl)	Cattle	Pigs	Turkey
total	1829	3	0	0	0	238	1	1	1
PT1	65	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
PT11	5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
PT12	4	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
PT13	34	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
PT13a	15	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-
PT14b	20	-	-	-	-	4	-	-	-
PT14c	8	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
PT15	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
PT15a	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
PT19	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
PT1b	1	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-
PT1d	8	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
PT2	8	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
PT21	182	-	-	-	-	11	-	-	-
PT21c	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
PT22	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
PT23	4	-	-	-	-	10	-	-	-
PT27	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
PT29	5	-	-	-	-	26	-	-	-
PT3	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
PT34	1	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-
PT35	6	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
PT3a	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
PT4	493	2	-	-	-	44	-	-	1
PT47	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
PT4b	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
PT5	20	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-
PT51	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
PT5a	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
PT5c	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
PT6	157	-	-	-	-	19	-	-	-
PT6a	12	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
PT7	6	-	-	-	-	10	-	-	-
PT8	670	-	-	-	-	109	1	-	-
RDNC	53	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-
U	29	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-

Table 17 S. Typhimurium definitive types in humans, food and animals

ST definitive type	Human	Broiler meat (gallus gallus)	Beef	Pork	Turkey meat	Gallus gallus (fowl)	Cattle	Pigs	Turkey
total	500	5	0	1	1	68	4	20	1
DT1	9	1	-	-	-	7	-	-	-
DT104H	8	-	-	-	-	12	-	-	-
DT104L	40	-	-	1	1	4	2	19	-
DT12	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT120	68	-	-	-	-	4	-	1	-
DT125	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT135	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT141	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT16	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT193	142	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-
DT193A	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT2	5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT3	17	-	-	-	-	3	-	-	-
DT30	2	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-
DT41	14	-	-	-	-	15	-	-	1
DT46	11	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-
DT46A	2	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT8	7	-	-	-	-	6	-	-	-
DT85	7	-	-	-	-	2	-	-	-
DT92	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT99	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
RDNC	65	3	-	-	-	9	-	-	-
U	5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
U277	1	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-
U291	1	-	-	-	-	2	-	-	-
U302	5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
U310	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
U311	73	-	-	-	-	-	2	-	-

4.1.7. Antimicrobial resistance in Salmonella spp. isolates

Antimicrobial resistance is the ability of certain microorganisms to survive or grow in the presence of a given concentration of antimicrobial agent that usually would kill or inhibit the microorganism species in

question. Antimicrobial resistant Salmonella strains may be transferred from animals or foodstuffs to humans.

A. Antimicrobial resistance of Salmonella spp. in humans

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

The overall resistance-rates against antibiotics remained stable over the past years.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Apart from a decrease of resistance against nalidixic acid, the resistancerates remained stable. High level resistances against ciprofloxacin and third generation cephalosporins (cefotaxime) were still extremely rare in comparison to rates reported within the EU.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Additional information

Annual publication of the results in the NRL-S Report and the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria (AURES)

B. Antimicrobial resistance of Salmonella spp. in animals and food

Sampling strategy used in monitoring

Frequency of the sampling

There currently is no monitoring program in Austria but all Salmonella spp. isolated in veterinary and food laboratories, as well as all primary isolates from humans were sent to the NRC-S where the susceptibility testing was performed using the disk diffusion method.

Salmonella isolates from the two control programmes in laying hens and broilers although are subjected to MIC-testing; all unique strains isolated from one epidemiological unit in the course of the control programmes.

Type of specimen taken

Clinical samples from humans; for animals and food see chapters Salmonella spp. in animal species and Salmonella spp. in food.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Clinical samples from humans; for animals and food see chapters Salmonella spp. in animal species and Salmonella spp. in food.

Procedures for the selection of isolates for antimicrobial testing

All Salmonella spp. isolated in veterinary and food laboratories, as well as all primary isolates from humans were sent to the NRC-S where the susceptibility testing was performed using the disk diffusion method.

All unique strains isolated in the course of the control programm (identical strains from one epidemiological unit only once) are used.

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

See chapter salmonellosis in humans; for the MIC testing CLSI standards are used, applying EUCAST cut-off values.

Laboratory used for detection of resistance

National Reference Centre for Salmonella, AGES Graz

Antimicrobials included in monitoring

All Salmonella isolates were susceptibility tested (disc diffusion) according to CLSI. Isolates obtained in course of the control programs for laying hens and broilers are tested according CD Nr. 2007/407/EC. See corresponding tables! Number of fully-susceptible and number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 or >4 antimicrobials of different classes, excluding cross-resistance. For Salmonella this includes resistance to ampicillin, cefotaxime, Nalidixic acid, streptomycin, gentamicin, tetracycline, chloramphenicol, trimethoprim and sulphamethoxazole.

Control program/mechanisms

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

An EU standardarized antimicrobial resistance monitoring system would be highly welcome.

Additional information

Nil

Table 18 Breakpoints for antibiotic resistance of *Salmonella* spp.**Test method used**

Disc diffusion	x
E-test	
Agar dilution	
Broth dilution	x

Standards used for testing

NCCLS	
Other	
EN ISO 20776-1	x

The methods are used for investigation of isolates from

Feedingstuff	
Animals	x
Food	x
Humans	x

<i>Salmonella</i>	Dilution method		Diffusion method	
	Standard for cut-off	Resistant > concentration (µg/ml)	Standard for breakpoint	Resistant ≤ zone diameter (mm)
Tetracyclines				
	Tetracycline	EFSA	8	CLSI 11
Amphenicols				
	Chloramphenicol	EFSA	16	CLSI 12
	Floramphenicol	EUCAST	16	
Penicillins				
	Ampicillin	EFSA	4	CLSI 13
Cephalosporins				
	Cefotaxim	EFSA	0.5	CLSI 14
	Ceftazidime	EUCAST	2	
Fluoroquinolones				
	Ciprofloxacin	EFSA	0.06	CLSI 15
Sulfonamides				
	Sulfamethoxazol	EFSA	256	CLSI 12
Aminoglycosides				
	Streptomycin	EUCAST	16	CLSI 11
	Gentamicin	EFSA	2	CLSI 12
	Kanamycin		?	CLSI 13
Quinolones				
	Nalidixic acid	EFSA	16	CLSI 13
Polymyxine				
	Colistin	EUCAST	8	
Trimethoprim				
		EFSA	2	CLSI 10

Table 19 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Salmonella* spp in humans, animals and food (diffusion method, clinical breakpoint)

	Humans		Broiler meat		Turkey meat		Bovine meat		Pig meat		Laying hens		Broiler		Turkeys		Cattle		Pigs	
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	no		no		no		no		no		no		no		no		no		no	
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	2829		52		27		2		1		212		270		174		15		38	
Antimicrobials:	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n
Tetracyclines																				
Tetracycline	11,6	328	46,2	24	40,7	11	0,0	0	0	0	4,7	10	47,0	127	57,5	100	20,0	3	42,1	16
Amphenicols																				
Chloramphenicol	2,6	73	1,9	1	3,7	1	0,0	0	100	1	1,4	3	0,4	1	0,0	0	13,3	2	34,2	13
Penicillins																				
Ampicillin	12,9	365	26,9	14	25,9	7	0,0	0	100	1	6,1	13	4,1	11	58,0	101	26,7	4	57,9	22
Cephalosporins																				
Cefotaxim	0,3	9	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	10,5	4
Fluoroquinolones																				
Ciprofloxacin	0,3	8	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0
Sulfonamides																				
Sulfamethoxazol	11,0	311	61,5	32	18,5	5	0,0	0	100	1	3,8	8	47,4	128	58,0	101	26,7	4	52,6	20
Aminoglycosides																				
Streptomycin	10,6	299	50,0	26	29,6	8	0,0	0	100	1	3,3	7	46,7	126	56,3	98	66,7	10	52,6	20
Gentamicin	0,6	18	1,9	1	0,0	0	0,0	0	0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0
Kanamycin	0,6	16	13,5	7	3,7	1	0,0	0	0	0	0,5	1	0,4	1	2,3	4	0,0	0	0,0	0
Quinolones																				
Nalidixic acid	6,5	184	61,5	32	40,7	11	100	2	100	1	2,4	5	47,0	127	55,7	97	6,7	1	13,2	5
Trimethoprim																				
	2,2	61	7,7	4	3,7	1	0,0	0	0	0	2,4	5	1,1	3	48,3	83	0,0	0	0,0	0
Number of multiresistant isolates*																				
fully sensitive	80,5	2278	19,2	10	33,3	9	0,0	0	0	0	89,6	190	49,6	134	24,7	43	26,7	4	31,6	12
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	6,6	186	17,3	9	14,8	4	100	2	0	0	5,7	12	2,6	7	7,5	13	40,0	6	2,6	1
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	1,3	38	0,0	0	22,2	6	0,0	0	0	0	0,5	1	0,7	2	9,2	16	0,0	0	2,6	1
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	1,7	49	13,5	7	11,1	3	0,0	0	0	0	0,0	0	0,4	1	2,3	4	0,0	0	15,8	6
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	6,7	189	38,5	20	7,4	2	0,0	0	0	0	2,4	5	45,2	122	10,3	18	20,0	3	23,7	9
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	3,1	89	11,5	6	11,1	3	0,0	0	100	1	1,9	4	1,5	4	45,4	79	6,7	1	23,7	9

Table 20 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Enteritidis* in humans, animals and food (diffusion method, clinical breakpoint)

	Humans		broiler meat		turkey meat		bovine meat		pig meat		laying hens		broiler		turkeys		cattle		pigs	
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	no		no		no		no		no		no		no		no		no		no	
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	1829		3		0		0		0		114		70		1		1		1	
Antimicrobials:	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	%r	n	%r	n	%r	n	%r	n	%r	n	%r	n
Tetracyclines																				
Tetracycline	1,3	24	0,0	0							0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	100	1
Amphenicols																				
Chloramphenicol	0,0	0	0,0	0							0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0
Penicillins																				
Ampicillin	3,5	64	66,7	2							0,9	1	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	100	1
Cephalosporins																				
Cefotaxim	0,1	2	0,0	0							0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0
Fluoroquinolones																				
Ciprofloxacin	0,0	0	0,0	0							0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0
Sulfonamides																				
Sulfamethoxazol	0,4	7	0,0	0							0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	100	1
Aminoglycosides																				
Streptomycin	0,2	4	0,0	0							0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	100	1
Gentamicin	0,1	1	0,0	0							0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0
Kanamycin	0,1	1	0,0	0							0,9	1	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0
Quinolones																				
Nalidixic acid	5,1	93	0,0	0							0,9	1	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0
Trimethoprim																				
Trimethoprim	0,3	5	0,0	0							0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0
Number of multiresistant isolates*	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n
fully sensitive	90,8	1661	33,3	1							98,2	112	100,0	70	0,0	0	0	0	0,0	0
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	8,0	146	66,7	2							0,9	1	0,0	0	0,0	0	0	0	0,0	0
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	0,8	15	0,0	0							0,9	1	0,0	0	0,0	0	0	0	0,0	0
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	0,2	4	0,0	0							0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0	0	0,0	0
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	0,1	2	0,0	0							0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0	0	100	1
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	0,1	1	0,0	0							0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0	0	0,0	0

Table 21 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Typhimurium* in humans, food and animals (Diffusion method, clinical breakpoint)

	Humans		Broiler meat		Turkey meat		Bovine meat		Pig meat		Laying hens		Broiler		Turkeys		Cattle		Pigs	
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	no		no		no		no		no		no		no		no		no		no	
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	500		5		1		0		1		39		13		1		4		20	
Antimicrobials:	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	%r	n	%r	n	%r	n	%r	n	%r	n
Tetracyclines																				
Tetracycline	33,8	169	20,0	1	100	1			0,0	0	5,1	2	15,4	2	0,0	0	75,0	3	65,0	13
Amphenicols																				
Chloramphenicol	11,2	56	20,0	1	100	1			100	1	7,7	3	7,7	1	0,0	0	50,0	2	65,0	13
Penicillins																				
Ampicillin	36,8	184	40,0	2	100	1			100	1	10,3	4	23,1	3	0,0	0	100	4	90,0	18
Cephalosporins																				
Cefotaxim	0,0	0	0,0	0	0	0			0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0	0	5,0	1
Fluoroquinolones																				
Ciprofloxacin	0,0	0	0,0	0	0	0			0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0	0	0,0	0
Sulfonamides																				
Sulfamethoxazol	36,4	182	20,0	1	100	1			100	1	7,7	3	23,1	3	0,0	0	100	4	90,0	18
Aminoglycosides																				
Streptomycin	34,4	172	0,0	0	100	1			100	1	7,7	3	15,4	2	0,0	0	100	4	85,0	17
Gentamicin	0,6	3	0,0	0	0	0			0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0
Kanamycin	0,8	4	0,0	0	0	0			0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0
Quinolones																				
Nalidixic acid	4,0	20	0,0	0	100	1			100	1	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	25,0	1	0,0	0
Trimethoprim																				
	4,0	20	0,0	0	0	0			0,0	0	0,0	0	7,7	1	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0
Number of multiresistant isolates*																				
fully sensitive	58,4	292	60,0	3	0,0	0			0,0	0	87,2	34	69,2	9	100	1	0,0	0	5,0	1
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	4,2	21	20,0	1	0,0	0			0,0	0	5,1	2	7,7	1	0,0	0	0,0	0	5,0	1
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	1,6	8	0,0	0	0,0	0			0,0	0	0,0	0	7,7	1	0,0	0	0,0	0	5,0	1
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	3,4	17	0,0	0	0,0	0			0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	22,8	114	20,0	1	0,0	0			0,0	0	2,6	1	7,7	1	0,0	0	75,0	3	40,0	8
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	9,6	48	0,0	0	100	1			100	1	5,1	2	7,7	1	0,0	0	25,0	1	45,0	9

Table 22 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of other serotypes than Enteritidis and Typhimurium in humans, food and animals (Diffusion method, clinical breakpoint)

	Humans		Broiler meat		Turkey meat		Bovine meat		Pig meat		Laying hens		Broiler		Turkeys		Cattle		Pigs	
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	no		no		no		no		no		no		no		no		no		no	
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	500		44		26		2		0		59		187		172		10		17	
Antimicrobials:	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n
Tetracyclines																				
Tetracycline	27,0	135	52,3	23	38,5	10	0,0	0			13,6	8	66,8	125	58,1	100	0,0	0	11,8	2
Amphenicols																				
Chloramphenicol	3,4	17	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0			0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0
Penicillins																				
Ampicillin	23,4	117	22,7	10	23,1	6	0,0	0			13,6	8	4,3	8	58,7	101	0,0	0	17,6	3
Cephalosporins																				
Cefotaxim	1,4	7	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0			0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	17,6	3
Fluoroquinolones																				
Ciprofloxacin	1,6	8	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0			0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0
Sulfonamides																				
Sulfamethoxazol	24,4	122	70,5	31	15,4	4	0,0	0			8,5	5	66,8	125	58,7	101	0,0	0	5,9	1
Aminoglycosides																				
Streptomycin	24,6	123	59,1	26	26,9	7	0,0	0			6,8	4	66,3	124	57,0	98	60,0	6	11,8	2
Gentamicin	2,8	14	2,3	1	0,0	0	0,0	0			0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	0
Kanamycin	2,2	11	15,9	7	3,8	1	0,0	0			0,0	0	0,5	1	2,3	4	0,0	0	0,0	0
Quinolones																				
Nalidixic acid	14,2	71	72,7	32	38,5	10	100,0	2			6,8	4	67,9	127	56,4	97	0,0	0	29,4	5
Trimethoprim																				
	7,2	36	9,1	4	3,8	1	0,0	0			8,5	5	1,1	2	48,3	83	0,0	0	0,0	0
Number of multiresistant isolates*																				
fully sensitive	65,0	325	13,6	6	34,6	9	0,0	0			74,6	44	29,4	55	24,4	42	40,0	4	64,7	11
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	3,8	19	13,6	6	15,4	4	100,0	2			15,3	9	3,2	6	7,6	13	60,0	6	0,0	0
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	3,0	15	0,0	0	23,1	6	0,0	0			0,0	0	0,5	1	9,3	16	0,0	0	0,0	0
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	5,6	28	15,9	7	11,5	3	0,0	0			0,0	0	0,5	1	2,3	4	0,0	0	35,3	6
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	14,6	73	43,2	19	7,7	2	0,0	0			6,8	4	64,7	121	10,5	18	0,0	0	0,0	0
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	8,0	40	13,6	6	7,7	2	0,0	0			3,4	2	1,6	3	45,9	79	0,0	0	0,0	0

Table 23 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. monophasic* Group B in humans, food and animals (Diffusion method, clinical breakpoint)

	Humans		Broiler meat		Turkey meat		Bovine meat		Pig meat		Laying hens		Broiler		Turkeys		Cattle		Pigs	
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	no		no		no		no		no		no		no		no		no		no	
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	58		0		0		0		0		0		0		0		0		0	
Antimicrobials:	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n
Tetracyclines																				
Tetracycline	98,3	57																		
Amphenicols																				
Chloramphenicol	6,9	4																		
Penicillins																				
Ampicillin	96,6	56																		
Cephalosporins																				
Cefotaxim	0,0	0																		
Fluoroquinolones																				
Ciprofloxacin	0,0	0																		
Sulfonamides																				
Sulfamethoxazol	98,3	57																		
Aminoglycosides																				
Streptomycin	98,3	57																		
Gentamicin	0,0	0																		
Kanamycin	0,0	0																		
Quinolones																				
Nalidixic acid	0,0	0																		
Trimethoprim	3,4	2																		
Number of multiresistant isolates*	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n
fully sensitive	0,0	0																		
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	1,7	1																		
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	0,0	0																		
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	3,4	2																		
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	86,2	50																		
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	8,6	5																		

Table 24 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Infantis* in humans, food and animals (Diffusion method, clinical breakpoint)

	Humans		Broiler meat		Turkey meat		Bovine meat		Pig meat		Laying hens		Broiler		Turkeys		Cattle		Pigs	
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	no		no		no		no		no		no		no		no		no		no	
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	58		25		0		0		0		0		0		0		0		0	
Antimicrobials:	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n
Tetracyclines																				
Tetracycline	13,8	8	72,0	18																
Amphenicols																				
Chloramphenicol	0,0	0	0,0	0																
Penicillins																				
Ampicillin	12,1	7	8,0	2																
Cephalosporins																				
Cefotaxim	3,4	2	0,0	0																
Fluoroquinolones																				
Ciprofloxacin	0	0	0,0	0																
Sulfonamides																				
Sulfamethoxazol	17,2	10	84,0	21																
Aminoglycosides																				
Streptomycin	12,1	7	72,0	18																
Gentamicin	0,0	0	0,0	0																
Kanamycin	0,0	0	0,0	0																
Quinolones																				
Nalidixic acid	22,4	13	88,0	22																
Trimethoprim	5,2	3	8,0	2																
Number of multiresistant isolates*	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n
fully sensitive	69,0	40	0,0	0																
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	6,9	4	12,0	3																
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	6,9	4	0,0	0																
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	3,4	2	20,0	5																
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	13,8	8	68,0	17																
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	0,0	0	0,0	0																

Table 25 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Saintpaul* in humans, food and animals (Diffusion method, clinical breakpoint)

	Humans		Broiler meat		Turkey meat		Bovine meat		Pig meat		Laying hens		Broiler		Turkeys		Cattle		Pigs	
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	no		no		no		no		no		no		no		no		no		no	
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	28		0		15		0		0		0		0		111		0		0	
Antimicrobials:	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n
Tetracyclines																				
Tetracycline	17,9	5			6,7	1										65,8	73			
Amphenicols																				
Chloramphenicol	0,0	0			0,0	0										0,0	0			
Penicillins																				
Ampicillin	14,3	4			13,3	2										77,5	86			
Cephalosporins																				
Cefotaxim	0,0	0			0,0	0										0,0	0			
Fluoroquinolones																				
Ciprofloxacin	0,0	0			0,0	0										0,0	0			
Sulfonamides																				
Sulfamethoxazol	10,7	3			13,3	2										77,5	86			
Aminoglycosides																				
Streptomycin	10,7	3			13,3	2										79,3	88			
Gentamicin	0,0	0			0,0	0										0,0	0			
Kanamycin	0,0	0			6,7	1										3,6	4			
Quinolones																				
Nalidixic acid	10,7	3			46,7	7										82,9	92			
Trimethoprim	3,6	1			0,0	0										65,8	73			
Number of multiresistant isolates*																				
fully sensitive	75,0	21			53,3	8										13,5	15			
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	7,1	2			33,3	5										7,2	8			
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	7,1	2			0,0	0										1,8	2			
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	3,6	1			0,0	0										0,0	0			
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	3,6	1			0,0	0										7,2	8			
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	3,6	1			13,3	2										70,3	78			

Table 26 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Hadar* in humans, food and animals (Diffusion method, clinical breakpoint)

	Humans		Broiler meat		Turkey meat		Bovine meat		Pig meat		Laying hens		Broiler		Turkeys		Cattle		Pigs	
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	no		no		no		no		no		no		no		no		no		no	
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	23		0		0		0		0		0		0		0		0		0	
Antimicrobials:	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n
Tetracyclines																				
Tetracycline	73,9	17																		
Amphenicols																				
Chloramphenicol	0,0	0																		
Penicillins																				
Ampicillin	39,1	9																		
Cephalosporins																				
Cefotaxim	0,0	0																		
Fluoroquinolones																				
Ciprofloxacin	0,0	0																		
Sulfonamides																				
Sulfamethoxazol	0,0	0																		
Aminoglycosides																				
Streptomycin	69,6	16																		
Gentamicin	0,0	0																		
Kanamycin	0,0	0																		
Quinolones																				
Nalidixic acid	69,6	16																		
Trimethoprim	0,0	0																		
Number of multiresistant isolates*	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n
fully sensitive	17,4	4																		
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	0,0	0																		
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	26,1	6																		
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	26,1	6																		
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	30,4	7																		
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	0,0	0																		

Table 27 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Agona* in humans, food and animals (Diffusion method, clinical breakpoint)

	Humans		Broiler meat		Turkey meat		Bovine meat		Pig meat		Laying hens		Broiler		Turkeys		Cattle		Pigs	
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	no		no		no		no		no		no		no		no		no		no	
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	14		0		0		0		0		0		0		12		0		0	
Antimicrobials:	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n
Tetracyclines															0,0	0				
Tetracycline	0,0	0																		
Amphenicols															0,0	0				
Chloramphenicol	0,0	0																		
Penicillins															0,0	0				
Ampicillin	0,0	0																		
Cephalosporins															0,0	0				
Cefotaxim	0,0	0																		
Fluoroquinolones															0,0	0				
Ciprofloxacin	0,0	0																		
Sulfonamides															0,0	0				
Sulfamethoxazol	0,0	0																		
Aminoglycosides															0,0	0				
Streptomycin	0,0	0													0,0	0				
Gentamicin	0,0	0													0,0	0				
Kanamycin	0,0	0																		
Quinolones															0,0	0				
Nalidixic acid	0,0	0													0,0	0				
Trimethoprim	0,0	0													0,0	0				
Number of multiresistant isolates*	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n
fully sensitive	100	14													100	12				
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	0,0	0													0,0	0				
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	0,0	0													0,0	0				
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	0,0	0													0,0	0				
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	0,0	0													0,0	0				
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	0,0	0													0,0	0				

Table 28 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Montevideo* in humans, food and animals (Diffusion method, clinical breakpoint)

	Humans		Broiler meat		Turkey meat		Bovine meat		Pig meat		Laying hens		Broiler		Turkeys		Cattle		Pigs	
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	no		no		no		no		no		no		no		no		no		no	
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	7		0		0		0		0		0		65		0		0		0	
Antimicrobials:	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n
Tetracyclines																				
Tetracycline	0,0	0											0.0	0						
Amphenicols																				
Chloramphenicol	0,0	0											0.0	0						
Penicillins																				
Ampicillin	0,0	0											0.0	0						
Cephalosporins																				
Cefotaxim	0,0	0											0.0	0						
Fluoroquinolones																				
Ciprofloxacin	0,0	0											0.0	0						
Sulfonamides																				
Sulfamethoxazol	0,0	0											0.0	0						
Aminoglycosides																				
Streptomycin	0,0	0											0.0	0						
Gentamicin	0,0	0											0.0							
Kanamycin	0,0	0											0.0	0						
Quinolones																				
Nalidixic acid	0,0	0											0.0	0						
Trimethoprim	0,0	0																		
Number of multiresistant isolates*	%	%	n	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	N	%	n	%	n	%	n
fully sensitive	100,0	7											100	65						
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	0,0	0											0.0	0						
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	0,0	0											0.0	0						
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	0,0	0											0.0	0						
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	0,0	0											0.0	0						
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	0,0	0											0.0	0						

Table 29 Qualitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Salmonella derived from control program in laying hens and broilers (Dilution method, cut-off values)

	Salmonella spp.				S. Enteritidis				S. Typhimurium				other Salmonella than Enteritidis or Typhimurium				S. Montevideo		other Salmonella than Enteritidis or Typhimurium or Montevideo	
	laying hens		broiler		laying hens		broiler		laying hens		broiler		laying hens		broiler		broiler		broiler	
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes		yes		yes		yes		yes		yes		yes		yes		yes		yes	
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	100		130		48		28		18		13		34		89		52		37	
Antimicrobials:	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n
Aminoglykosid AB																				
Gentamicin	0,0%	0	0,8%	1	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	1,1%	1	0%	0	2,7%	1
Kanamycin	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0%	0	0,0%	0
Streptomycin	6,0%	6	3,8%	5	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	16,7%	3	7,7%	1	8,8%	3	4,5%	4	0%	0	10,8%	4
Cephalosporine																				
Cefotaxim	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0%	0	0,0%	0
Ceftazidime	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0%	0	0,0%	0
Folsäureinhibitoren																				
Sulfamethoxazol	6,0%	6	4,6%	6	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	16,7%	3	15,4%	2	8,8%	3	4,5%	4	0%	0	10,8%	4
Trimethoprim	3,0%	3	1,5%	2	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	7,7%	1	8,8%	3	1,1%	1	0%	0	2,7%	1
Penicilline																				
Ampicillin	7,0%	7	6,9%	9	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	16,7%	3	23,1%	3	11,8%	4	6,7%	6	0%	0	16,2%	6
Phenicole																				
Chloramphenicol	3,0%	3	0,8%	1	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	16,7%	3	7,7%	1	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0%	0	0,0%	0
Florfenicol	3,0%	3	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	16,7%	3	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0%	0	0,0%	0
Polymyxine																				
Colistine	0,0%		0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0%	0	0,0%	0
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																				
Ciprofloxacin	4,0%	4	4,6%	6	2,1%	1	10,7%	3	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	8,8%	3	3,4%	3	0%	0	8,1%	3
Nalidixinsäure	4,0%	4	4,6%	6	2,1%	1	10,7%	3	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	8,8%	3	3,4%	3	0%	0	8,1%	3
Tetracycline																				
Tetracycline	8,0%	8	3,8%	5	2,1%	1	0,0%	0	16,7%	3	7,7%	1	11,8%	4	4,5%	4	0%	0	10,8%	4

	Salmonella spp.				S. Enteritidis				S. Typhimurium				other Salmonella than Enteritidis or Typhimurium				S. Montevideo		other Salmonella than Enteritidis or Typhimurium or Montevideo	
	laying hens		broiler		laying hens		broiler		laying hens		broiler		laying hens		broiler		broiler		broiler	
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes		yes		yes		yes		yes		yes		yes		yes		yes		yes	
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	100		130		48		28		18		13		34		89		52		37	
Antimicrobials:	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n	r%	n
Number of multiresistant isolates																				
fully sensitive	90%	90	87,7%	114	95,8%	46	89,3%	25	83,3%	15	69,2%	9	85,3%	29	89,9%	80	100%	52	75,7%	28
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	3%	3	7,7%	10	4,2%	2	10,7%	3	0,0%	0	15,4%	2	2,9%	1	5,6%	5	0%	0	13,5%	5
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	0%	0	0,8%	1	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	7,7%	1	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0%	0	0,0%	0
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0%	0	0,0%	0
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	2%	2	1,5%	2	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	5,9%	2	2,2%	2	0%	0	5,4%	2
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	5%	5	2,3%	3	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	16,7%	3	7,7%	1	5,9%	2	2,2%	2	0%	0	5,4%	2

Number of fully-susceptible and number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 or >4 antimicrobials of different classes, excluding cross-resistance. For Salmonella this includes resistance to ampicillin, cefotaxime, Nalidixic acid, streptomycin, gentamicin, tetracycline, chloramphenicol, trimethoprim and sulphamethoxazole

Table 30 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Salmonella* spp. derived from control program in laying hens (Dilution method)

				<i>Salmonella</i> spp. laying hens, control program																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		100		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Antimicrobials:				=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
	N	%R	n	n																			
Aminoglykosid AB																							
Gentamicin	100	0,0%							89	11													
Kanamycin	100	0,0%											100										
Streptomycin	100	6,0%	6								43	30	19	2		4	2						
Cephalosporine																							
Cefotaxim	100	0,0%				81	19																
Ceftazidime	100	0,0%						83	16	1													
Folsäureinhibitoren																							
Sulfamethoxazol	100	6,0%	6											10	32	47	5					6	
Trimethoprim	100	3,0%	3						97							3							
Penicilline																							
Ampicillin	100	7,0%	7						5	75	13					7							
Phenicole																							
Chloramphenicol	100	3,0%	3								1	70	26				3						
Florfenicol	100	3,0%	3								8	88	1		3								
Polymyxine																							
Colistine	100	0,0%											100										
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																							
Ciprofloxacin	100	4,0%	4		41	55		1	2	1													
Nalidixinsäure	100	4,0%	4										96					4					
Tetracycline																							
Tetracyclin	100	8,0%	8								25	67				3	1	4					

Table 31 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Enteritidis* derived from control program in laying hens (Dilution method)

				<i>S. Enteritidis</i> laying hens, control program																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		48		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Antimicrobials:				=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
		N	%R	n																			
Aminoglykosid AB																							
	Gentamicin	48	0,0%						44	4													
	Kanamycin	48	0,0%										48										
	Streptomycin	48	0,0%								41	7											
Cephalosporine																							
	Cefotaxim	48	0,0%			43	5																
	Ceftazidime	48	0,0%					47	1														
Folsäureinhibitoren																							
	Sulfamethoxazol	48	0,0%												5	12	30	1					
	Trimethoprim	48	0,0%						48														
Penicilline																							
	Ampicillin	48	0,0%						2	38	8												
Phenicole																							
	Chloramphenicol	48	0,0%								1	44	3										
	Florfenicol	48	0,0%								5	43											
Polymyxine																							
	Colistine	48	0,0%										48										
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																							
	Ciprofloxacin	48	2,1%	1		20	27	1															
	Nalidixinsäure	48	2,1%	1								47						1					
Tetracycline																							
	Tetracyclin	48	2,1%	1						14	33							1					

Table 32 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Typhimurium* derived from control program in laying hens (Dilution method)

				<i>S. Typhimurium</i> laying hens, control program																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		18		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Antimicrobials:				=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
		N	%R	n																			
Aminoglykosid AB																							
	Gentamicin	18	0,0%						13	5													
	Kanamycin	18	0,0%										18										
	Streptomycin	18	16,7%	3							1	6	7	1		3							
Cephalosporine																							
	Cefotaxim	18	0,0%																				
	Ceftazidime	18	0,0%				15	3															
Folsäureinhibitoren																							
	Sulfamethoxazol	18	16,7%	3												6	9					3	
	Trimethoprim	18	0,0%						18														
Penicilline																							
	Ampicillin	18	16,7%	3							11	4					3						
Phenicole																							
	Chloramphenicol	18	16,7%	3									11	4			3						
	Florfenicol	18	16,7%	3								2	13			3							
Polymyxine																							
	Colistine	18	0,0%										18										
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																							
	Ciprofloxacin	18	0,0%		6	12																	
	Nalidixinsäure	18	0,0%										18										
Tetracycline																							
	Tetracyclin	18	16,7%	3							1	14				3							

Table 33 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of other serotypes than Enteritidis and Typhimurium derived from control program in laying hens (Dilution method)

				<i>Salmonella</i> other than Enteritidis or Typhimurium laying hens, control program																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		34		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Antimicrobials:				= < 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
		N	%R	n																			
Aminoglykosid AB																							
	Gentamicin	34	0,0%	0																			
	Kanamycin	34	0,0%	0																			
	Streptomycin	34	8,8%	3																			
Cephalosporine																							
	Cefotaxim	34	0,0%	0																			
	Ceftazidime	34	0,0%	0																			
Folsäureinhibitoren																							
	Sulfamethoxazol	34	8,8%	3																			
	Trimethoprim	34	8,8%	3																			
Penicilline																							
	Ampicillin	34	11,8%	4																			
Phenicole																							
	Chloramphenicol	34	0,0%	0																			
	Florfenicol	34	0,0%	0																			
Polymyxine																							
	Colistine	34	0,0%	0																			
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																							
	Ciprofloxacin	34	8,8%	3																			
	Nalidixinsäure	34	8,8%	3																			
Tetracycline																							
	Tetracyclin	34	11,8%	4																			

Table 34 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Salmonella* spp. derived from control program in broilers (Dilution method)

				<i>Salmonella</i> spp. broiler, control program																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		130		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Antimicrobials:				=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
	N	%R	n	n																			
Aminoglykosid AB																							
Gentamicin	130	0,8%	1						67	60	2			1									
Kanamycin	130	0,0%											128	1		1							
Streptomycin	130	3,8%	5									13	47	56	9	2	1	1	1				
Cephalosporine																							
Cefotaxim	130	0,0%				103	24	3															
Ceftazidime	130	0,0%						99	30	1													
Folsäureinhibitoren																							
Sulfamethoxazol	130	4,6%	6											3	15	73	31	1	1				6
Trimethoprim	130	1,5%	2							128							2						
Penicilline																							
Ampicillin	130	6,9%	9								97	22	2				9						
Phenicole																							
Chloramphenicol	130	0,8%	1									3	92	32	2			1					
Florfenicol	130	0,0%										5	120	3	2								
Polymyxine																							
Colistine	130	0,0%												130									
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																							
Ciprofloxacin	130	4,6%	6		108	15	1	2	1	3													
Nalidixinsäure	130	4,6%	6										123	1				6					
Tetracycline																							
Tetracyclin	130	3,8%	5								59	63	3				1	4					

Table 35 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Enteritidis* derived from control program in broilers (Dilution method)

				<i>S. Enteritidis</i> broiler, control program																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																						
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	28			Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Antimicrobials:				=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
	N	%R	n	n																			
Aminoglykosid AB																							
Gentamicin	28	0,0%							21	7													
Kanamycin	28	0,0%											28										
Streptomycin	28	0,0%										12	16										
Cephalosporine																							
Cefotaxim	28	0,0%				25	3																
Ceftazidime	28	0,0%						24	4														
Folsäureinhibitoren																							
Sulfamethoxazol	28	0,0%														22	6						
Trimethoprim	28	0,0%							28														
Penicilline																							
Ampicillin	28	0,0%									18	10											
Phenicole																							
Chloramphenicol	28	0,0%											28										
Florfenicol	28	0,0%										1	27										
Polymyxine																							
Colistine	28	0,0%												28									
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																							
Ciprofloxacin	28	10,7%	3		21	4		2	1														
Nalidixinsäure	28	10,7%	3										25					3					
Tetracycline																							
Tetracyclin	28	0,0%									23	5											

Table 36 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Typhimurium* derived from control program in broilers (Dilution method)

				<i>S. Typhimurium</i> broiler, control program																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		13		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Antimicrobials:				=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
		N	%R	n																			
Aminoglykosid AB																							
	Gentamicin	13	0,0%						5	8													
	Kanamycin	13	0,0%										13										
	Streptomycin	13	7,7%	1								3	9				1						
Cephalosporine																							
	Cefotaxim	13	0,0%				11	2															
	Ceftazidime	13	0,0%						12	1													
Folsäureinhibitoren																							
	Sulfamethoxazol	13	15,4%	2											3	7	1					2	
	Trimethoprim	13	7,7%	1						12							1						
Penicilline																							
	Ampicillin	13	23,1%	3							9	1					3						
Phenicole																							
	Chloramphenicol	13	7,7%	1									9	3				1					
	Florfenicol	13	0,0%										13										
Polymyxine																							
	Colistine	13	0,0%											13									
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																							
	Ciprofloxacin	13	0,0%		10	3																	
	Nalidixinsäure	13	0,0%										13										
Tetracycline																							
	Tetracyclin	13	7,7%	1							3	9						1					

Table 37 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Montevideo* derived from control program in broilers (Dilution method)

				<i>S. Montevideo</i> broiler, control program																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		52		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Antimicrobials:				=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
		N	%R	n																			
Aminoglykosid AB																							
	Gentamicin	52	0,0%	0																			
	Kanamycin	52	0,0%	0																			
	Streptomycin	52	0,0%	0																			
Cephalosporine																							
	Cefotaxim	52	0,0%	0																			
	Ceftazidime	52	0,0%	0																			
Folsäureinhibitoren																							
	Sulfamethoxazol	52	0,0%	0																			
	Trimethoprim	52	0,0%	0																			
Penicilline																							
	Ampicillin	52	0,0%	0																			
Phenicole																							
	Chloramphenicol	52	0,0%	0																			
	Florfenicol	52	0,0%	0																			
Polymyxine																							
	Colistine	52	0,0%	0																			
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																							
	Ciprofloxacin	52	0,0%	0																			
	Nalidixinsäure	52	0,0%	0																			
Tetracycline																							
	Tetracyclin	52	0,0%	0																			

Table 38 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of other serotypes than Enteritidis and Typhimurium and Montevideo derived from control program in broilers (Dilution method)

				<i>Salmonella</i> other than Enteritidis or Typhimurium or Montevideo broiler, control program																								
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																										
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		37		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																								
Antimicrobials:				= < 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048					
		N	%R	n																								
Aminoglykosid AB																												
	Gentamicin	37	2,7%	1																								
	Kanamycin	37	0,0%					14	20	2				1														
	Streptomycin	37	10,8%	4																								
Cephalosporine																												
	Cefotaxim	37	0,0%					23	12	2																		
	Ceftazidime	37	0,0%					16	20	1																		
Folsäureinhibitoren																												
	Sulfamethoxazol	37	10,8%	4																								
	Trimethoprim	37	2,7%	1					36																			
Penicilline																												
	Ampicillin	37	16,2%	6																								
Phenicole																												
	Chloramphenicol	37	0,0%																									
	Florfenicol	37	0,0%																									
Polymyxine																												
	Colistine	37	0,0%																									
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																												
	Ciprofloxacin	37	8,1%	3					31	2	1																	
	Nalidixinsäure	37	8,1%	3																								
Tetracycline																												
	Tetracyclin	37	10,8%	4																								

4.2. Campylobacteriosis

4.2.1. General evaluation of the national situation

A. Thermotolerant *Campylobacter* general evaluation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

In 2006, the number of notified human campylobacteriosis cases exceeded for the first time the number of notified salmonellosis cases in Austria. Since then, the gap between the number of human campylobacter cases and salmonella cases has been widening.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In recent years, the number of notified cases of campylobacteriosis – with the exception of 2003 – steadily increased, reaching a new peak of 6,077 cases in 2007. After a reduction in 2008 to 5,012 cases (aggregated data) an increase could be observed again in 2009 up to 5,507 cases; attention must be paid to the future trends.

The sources of infection are still unclear. The few published outbreaks in Austria were due to contaminated cow's raw milk or chicken meat. Pets may be considered another possible source.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Feedings stuff has no obvious relevance. Animals are heavily infected: broiler flocks up to 55 %. The actual source of infection is unknown in human cases, chicken meat may account for approx. 40% of human infections.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

On January 1st, 2006, the Federal Zoonoses Act (128. Bundesgesetz: Zoonosengesetz, published on 18th November 2005) was implemented. The subject of this Act is to ensure that zoonoses, zoonotic agents and related antimicrobial resistance are properly monitored, that food-borne outbreaks receive proper epidemiological investigation, to enable the collection of the information necessary in the EU. According to this Zoonoses Act, to survey and combat the zoonoses in Austria, a Federal Commission for Zoonoses (Zoonoses Commission) has been founded to advise the Federal Minister. The first meeting took place on May 3rd, 2006. The tasks of this Zoonoses Commission are

- Securing of effective and continuous teamwork of special fields concerned
- Cooperation based on free exchange of general information and where necessary, of specific data
- Determination of measures in case of Austrian-wide food borne outbreaks (concerning several provinces by one outbreak)
- Issues the annually report on trends and sources of zoonoses in Austria
- Preparation of risk based, integrated monitoring and surveillance programmes

The Austria-wide monitoring program on the trends of campylobacter prevalence and antimicrobial resistance of campylobacter in broiler was continued for the fifth year according to the directive 2003/99/EC of the European Parliament and the Council and the Federal Zoonoses Act. The sampling was carried out from January to December 2009, and follow up programs will be implemented in the forthcoming years. In 2009, the monitoring program was suspended in cattle and pigs due to lower relevance for human infections.

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Continue to work for harmonization of monitoring programs

Additional information

If zoonotic agents which are listed in the national Zoonoses Act are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obliged to send these strains to the respective national reference lab for typing and comparative analysis.

4.2.2. Campylobacteriosis in humans

A. Thermotolerant *Campylobacter* in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

Case definition

Clinical picture compatible with campylobacteriosis, e.g.: diarrheal illness of variable severity and isolation of *Campylobacter* spp. from stool.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Stool samples are plated on selective media and incubated in microaerobic atmosphere at 37 - 42 °C for a minimum of 36 hours (Anonymus: Standardisierung und Qualitätssicherung in der mikrobiologischen Diagnostik. Richtlinien. Bundesministerium für Soziale Sicherheit und Generationen. ISBN 3-84123-126-0, Wien, 2001, pg. 13). *Campylobacter* is confirmed by observing the typical colony morphology and characteristic motility and morphology under the microscope. For typing and differentiation of isolates to species level the production of catalase and oxidase, the reaction in hippurate and indoxylacetate-hydrolysis is performed. The differentiation to species-level is not performed in each laboratory.

Notification system in place

Notification of campylobacteriosis according to the epidemic act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): The attending physicians and the laboratories have to notify.

The data presented in this report reflect the number of cases notified as aggregated data. Additionally a sentinel surveillance program for *Campylobacter* isolates from human infections was installed in October 2006. On a monthly basis, the first 10 isolates collected at each of four designated diagnostic laboratories serving different provinces in Austria are sent to the National Reference Laboratory for *Campylobacter* for speciation analysis and antimicrobial resistance testing.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

In 2006, the number of notified human campylobacteriosis cases in Austria exceeded the number of notified salmonellosis cases for the first time. Since that year campylobacteriosis has remained the most frequently reported bacterial enteritis in humans in Austria.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2009 campylobacteriosis (n = 5,507) was the most frequently notified foodborne enteric disease. It seems that the main sources of infection are chicken meat and raw milk (Feierl G. 2007. Jahresbericht 2006 der Nationalen Referenzzentrale für *Campylobacter*. Mitteilungen der Sanitätsverwaltung 4/2007).

Relevance as zoonotic disease

In 2009, campylobacteriosis remained the most frequently notified food borne disease in Austria.

Additional information

According to the federal Epidemic Act the laboratories which isolate zoonotic agents causing notifiable diseases in humans and which are listed in the national Zoonoses Act are obliged to send these isolates to the respective national reference lab for speciation. The NRLs on their part have to inform the

competent authorities, the Federal Zoonoses Commission and the AGES about locally and temporally observed accumulations or clusters of human cases.

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Annual report of the National Reference Centre

http://www.bmg.gv.at/cms/site/attachments/5/1/6/CH0954/CMS1268584256464/jb_campylobacter_2009_final2.pdf

Data source of Tables 39 to 41: NRL Campylobacter, sentinel system

Table 39 Campylobacteriosis in humans - species/serotype distribution (single case notification)

	Cases *	Notification rate/100.000	Sentinel system
Campylobacteriosis	5,507	65.9	1,516
<i>C. jejuni</i>	n.a.		1,343
<i>C. coli</i>	n.a.		147
<i>C. upsalensis</i>	n.a.		1
<i>C. spp. unspecified</i>	n.a.		25

* notified cases according to Statistik meldepflichtiger Infektionskrankheiten, vorläufiger Jahresbericht 2009 (Stand per 28.01.2010)

Table 40 Campylobacteriosis in humans - age distribution (sentinel system)

Age group	Campylobacter sp.			C. jejuni			C. coli		
	All	F	M	All	F	M	All	F	M
< 1 year	22	10	12	21	9	12	1	1	0
1 to 4 years	143	63	80	126	57	69	14	5	9
5 to 14 years	175	81	94	162	75	87	10	5	5
15 to 24 years	290	140	150	270	131	139	17	8	9
25 to 44 years	374	179	195	323	156	167	44	21	23
45 to 64 years	282	134	148	244	114	130	31	17	14
65 years and older	229	122	107	196	101	95	30	18	12
Age unknown	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0
All age groups	1,516	729	787	1,343	643	700	147	75	72

Table 41 Campylobacteriosis in humans - seasonal distribution (sentinel system)

Month	Campylobacter Cases	C. jejuni Cases	C. coli Cases	C. upsalensis Cases	C. spp. Cases
January	86	73	12	0	1
February	73	64	7	0	2
March	75	63	12	0	0
April	89	81	8	0	0
May	98	87	11	0	0
June	152	140	12	0	0
July	238	215	18	0	5
August	176	152	19	1	4
September	195	173	16	0	6
October	134	116	13	0	5
November	122	113	9	0	0
December	78	66	10	0	2
Total	1,516	1,343	147	1	25

4.2.3. Campylobacter in foodstuffs

A. Campylobacter, thermotolerant in food - all foodstuffs - official food

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Foodstuff was sampled according to the ordinance „Revisions- und Probenplan für das Jahr 2009 gemäß §31 LMSVG; Richtlinien über die Vollziehung der Überwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Berichtsschema 2008“ (BMGFJ – 75500/0332-IV/B/7/2008) from the Federal Ministry of Health. This “Revisions- und Probenplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2007-2010) according to Art. 41 ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004.

The Revision-Plan determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be sampled and tested randomly according to the number of food enterprises per province. Every business within Austria has to be sampled at least once per year. The inspection can comprise sampling, hygienic investigations of the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes etc.

In 2009, approximately 40,000 samples were planned to be tested in Austria. About 60% (24,000) of these are planned samples (surveillance) and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). These planned samples either consist of samples of the yearly sampling plan which determines the number of samples of each food category that have to be investigated randomly, e.g. raw meat (fresh or frozen); sausages; cheeses; milk; preserved food etc. There are different sampling stages where food samples are taken: e.g. from retail, processing plant, primary production.

In addition there is a monitoring plan for food items (40-45 campaigns per year). In the course of these programs food items of special interest for defined parameters – amongst others zoonotic agents – are investigated. The sampling takes place during a fixed period of time in order to gain in-dept information. In 2009, seven relevant food campaign programs were conducted throughout Austria (Schwerpunktprogramm 2009 BMGFJ-75500/0242-IV/B/7/2008). Details and results of these campaigns can be found in the respective chapters.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Samples are cultured either according to ISO 10272: 1995 or preenriched in Bolton bouillon at 42 °C for 48 hours and subsequent plated on CCDA- or modified CCDA agar at 42 °C for 48 hours microaerophilic. Campylobacter-like colonies were identified serologically, observing their characteristic motility and morphology under the microscope and the production of catalase and oxidase. Not all isolates of Campylobacter spp. are differentiated.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infections

39 single samples of fresh broiler meat were tested and in 26% (=10 samples) thermotolerant Campylobacter (*C. jejuni*) was found (2008: in 8%). In 13 samples of pasteurised cows' milk, no sample was found positive as well as in 112 samples of raw cows' milk.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Campaign A-802-09: Campylobacter in food – raw milk - intended for direct human consumption - at farm - Surveillance - official controls - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at farm (unpasteurised milk vending machine) by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: April - June

Type of specimen taken

Raw milk - intended for direct human consumption

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of Campylobacter in 25g

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up surveillance programs

Results of the investigation

71 samples tested for Campylobacter: 0 positive

Additional information

Samples were also tested for STEC, *Listeria monocytogenes* and *Salmonella* spp.

Table 42 Thermophilic *Campylobacter* spp. in food

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Units tested	Total units positive for thermophilic <i>Campylobacter</i> spp.
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy products, not specified	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	26	0
Milk, cows' - pasteurised milk	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	13	0
Milk, cows' - raw	at farm	single	25g	15	0
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	5	0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	6	0
Milk, cows' - raw milk - intended for direct human consumption		single	25g	4	0
Milk - raw - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - intended for direct human consumption (Campaign A-802-09)	at farm (unpasteurised milk vending machine)	single	25g	71	0
Milk, cows' - raw milk for manufacture - intended for manufacture of raw or low heat-treated products	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	11	0
Milk, goats' - raw (and sheeps)	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	5	0
Meat from pig - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	4	0
Meat from other animals - meat preparation		single	25g	1	0
Other food	at catering	single	25g	12	0
Fish - raw - frozen		single	25g	2	0
Other food - processed food products and prepared dishes unspecified ready-to-eat foods frozen		single	25g	8	0

Table 43 Thermophilic *Campylobacter* spp. in poultry meat

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Units tested	Total units positive for thermophilic <i>Campylobacter</i> spp.		
					<i>Campylobacter coli</i>	<i>Campylobacter jejuni</i>	<i>Campylobacter</i> spp., unspecified
Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - fresh	at catering	single	25g	34	8		8
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	2	1		1
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	3	1		1
Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - meat products - cooked - ready-to-eat		single	25g	1	0		
Meat from broilers - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked		single	25g	31	3		3
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked	at catering	single	25g	4	0		
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	1	0		
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	3	0		
Meat from turkey - fresh	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	2	2	1	1
	at retail - imported	single	25g	1	0		

4.2.4. Campylobacter in animals

A. *Campylobacter* spp. in animal - Cattle (bovine animals) - at slaughterhouse - animal sample - faeces - Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

No monitoring in 2009

B. *Campylobacter* spp. in animal – broiler - at slaughterhouse – baseline survey – official sampling – objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

In 2009 the monitoring on the prevalence and antimicrobial resistance of *Campylobacter* spp. was carried out in broiler flocks. The date of sampling was randomized over the whole year. Sampling was performed in the 5 broiler slaughter facilities with slaughter batches consisting of >2000 animals in Austria in 2008.

Frequency of the sampling

Rearing period: no program

Before slaughter at farm: no program

At slaughter: according to the randomized sampling plan

Type of specimen taken

Intestines of 10 animals per slaughter batch.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Rearing period: no program

Before slaughter at farm: no program

At slaughter: The sampling was performed by official veterinarians carrying out the post-mortem inspection. At time of evisceration the whole intestines of 10 animals were taken and wrapped in a sterile plastic bag. Additionally a carcass from the same slaughter batch was sampled. After cooling down to 4 °C the sample was sent in a hobbox or polystyrene box after adding cooling units to the Institute of Veterinary Diseases Control (IVET) in Graz. In the laboratory a caecum of each intestinal convolute was identified, some content of each caecum pooled and plated on selective medium suitable for *Campylobacter jejuni/coli*.

Case definition

At slaughter: A slaughter batch is considered to be infected with thermotolerant *Campylobacter* following isolation of *Campylobacter jejuni* or *C. coli* from the pooled caecal content.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

At slaughter: The pooled samples were examined by direct inoculation on modified CCD agar (mCCDA) that was incubated in microaerophilic atmosphere at 42 ± 1 °C for 48 hours. *Campylobacter*-like colonies were identified by observing their characteristic motility and morphology under the microscope and the production of catalase and oxidase. For typing and differentiating of *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* isolates, hippurate reaction and indoxylacetate-hydrolysis was performed. All *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* isolates were frozen in proteose peptone solution containing 10 % glycerol or thioglycolat-broth at -70 °C. For quality

control Campylobacter jejuni ATCC 33560, Escherichia coli ATCC 25922 and internal control isolates C. jejuni and C. coli were used. Statistical analysis was performed with EpiInfo version 3.3.2.

Vaccination policy

Vaccination is not performed in Austria.

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Different strategies are in discussion, e.g. a quick test for identification of campylobacter infected flocks at farm.

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

None

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

None

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Emphasis should be placed on education of the people for a better care in kitchen hygiene.

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

None.

Notification system in place

Findings of C. jejuni and C. coli in animals must not be reported to authorities in Austria.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In the course of this monitoring thermotolerant Campylobacter were detected in 181 out of 326 (55.5%) of the tested slaughter batches. Due to the fact that poultry is the animal species with the highest prevalence of Campylobacter jejuni and coli, poultry meat seem to be the most risky food combined with mistakes in kitchen hygiene for humans acquiring an infection with C. jejuni/coli.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

C. Campylobacter spp. in animal - Pigs - at slaughterhouse – monitoring programme – official sampling – objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

No monitoring in 2009

Table 44 Thermophilic *Campylobacter* spp. in animals

Animal species	comment	Source of information	Sampling unit	Units tested	total units positive for <i>Campylobacter</i>	<i>C. jejuni</i>	<i>C. coli</i>	other thermotolerant <i>C. spp.</i>
Gallus gallus								
Broiler - at slaughterhouse - animal sample - caecum - monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	Caeca of 10 animals per batch pooled	Institute for Veterinary Disease Control, Graz	Slaughter batch	326	181	114	64	3

Graz: AGES Institute for Veterinary Disease Control in Graz

4.2.5. Antimicrobial resistance in *Campylobacter* spp.

A. Antimicrobial resistance in *Campylobacter jejuni* and *coli* in humans

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

A sentinel surveillance program for *Campylobacter* isolates from human infections was installed in October 2006. On a monthly basis, the first 10 isolates collected at each of four designated diagnostic laboratories serving different provinces in Austria are sent to the National Reference Laboratory for *Campylobacter* for speciation analysis and antimicrobial resistance testing.

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

Stool specimens were plated on *Campylobacter* blood-free selective media at 37°C or 42°C for 48 hours under micro aerobic conditions, and organisms were identified as *Campylobacter* spp. by oxidase testing and cell morphology. Isolates were speciated by hippurate hydrolysis, indoxyl acetate hydrolysis, katalase production, and species-specific real-time PCR.

Broth micro dilution susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter* spp. isolates was done using customised Sensititre® susceptibility micro titre plates (TREK Diagnostic Systems, Ltd., East Grinstead, West Sussex, and England). Briefly, *Campylobacter* spp. strains were subcultivated on Columbia blood agar and incubated for 48 hours at 37 °C in a microaerophilic atmosphere. Inocula from fresh cultures were prepared by suspension in physiological saline to obtain a turbidity equivalent to that of a McFarland standard 0.5. The suspension was added to Mueller Hinton bouillon for a final concentration of approximately 500,000 cfu/ml and incubated for 48 hours at 37 °C in a microaerophilic atmosphere. *Campylobacter jejuni* ATCC 33560 was used as control.

The number of isolates that are fully sensitive and the number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 and > 4 antimicrobials for *Campylobacter* includes only resistance to tetracycline, erythromycin, nalidixic acid, gentamicin, and streptomycin!

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Again, a further increase in resistance to fluoroquinolones was observed, the actual prevalence of antimicrobial resistance to ciprofloxacin in *Campylobacter* spp. is 59.6 % throughout Austria. Resistance to tetracycline rose to 31.9 %, and resistance to macrolides is 0.5 %.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Additional information

The newly established sentinel surveillance system will be continued. The results are published annually in the NRL-C Report and the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria (AURES).

B. Antimicrobial resistance in *Campylobacter jejuni* and *coli* in broiler

Sampling strategy used in monitoring

Frequency of the sampling

Described in chapter: Thermotolerant campylobacter in broilers

Type of specimen taken

Described in chapter: Thermotolerant campylobacter in broilers

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Described in chapter: Thermotolerant campylobacter in broilers

Procedures for the selection of isolates for antimicrobial testing

Testing of all isolates will be performed in the AGES Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene in Graz. The randomized sampling plan was calculated to obtain approximately 170 thermotolerant Campylobacter isolates per animal species. If less than 170 isolates were obtained, all isolates were tested. If more than 170 thermotolerant Campylobacter were isolated 170 were randomly chosen.

Methods used for collecting data

All informations concerning the tested animals, sampled slaughterhouses and results of the antimicrobial testing were entered and analysed in a Microsoft® Excel tables.

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

Described in chapter thermotolerant campylobacter in broilers.

Broth micro dilution susceptibility testing of Campylobacter spp. isolates was done using customised Sensititre® susceptibility micro titre plates (TREK Diagnostic Systems, Ltd., East Grinstead, West Sussex, and England). Briefly, Campylobacter spp. strains were subcultivated on Columbia blood agar and incubated for 48 hours at 37 °C in a microaerophilic atmosphere. Inocula from fresh cultures were prepared by suspension in physiological saline to obtain a turbidity equivalent to that of a McFarland standard 0.5. The suspension was added to Mueller Hinton bouillon for a final concentration of approximately 500,000 cfu/ml and incubated for 48 hours at 37 °C in a microaerophilic atmosphere. Campylobacter jejuni ATCC 33560 was used as control.

MIC values have been entered in a Microsoft® Excel datasheet.

The number of isolates that are fully sensitive and the number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 and > 4 antimicrobials for Campylobacter includes only resistance to tetracycline, erythromycin, nalidixic acid, gentamicin, and streptomycin!

Preventive measures in place

None

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Samples from food animals were monitored for antimicrobial residues according to a randomized sampling scheme (BMGF-74320/0003-IV/B/7/2009, Rückstandsuntersuchung-Durchführungserlass 2007).

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

A project has been started to assess the appropriate method for collecting data on antimicrobial usage in animals. Results of this study are expected in 2010.

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Nil

Notification system in place

No notification system for resistant isolates in place.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2009 in *C. jejuni* isolated from broiler an increase in the resistance could be observed for ciprofloxacin from 49% in 2008 to 59% in 2009 and for tetracycline from 26% to 30%; this trend can also be seen in isolates from humans; all isolates in 2008 and 2009 were sensitive for erythromycin.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Additional information

Table 45 Breakpoints used for antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter jejuni*

Test method used	Number of reporting laboratory	1
Disc diffusion		
E-test		
Agar dilution		
Broth dilution	x	

Standards used for testing	The methods are used for investigation of isolates from
CLSI	Feedingstuff
other	Animals
EN ISO 20776-1	Food
	Humans
	x

<i>Campylobacter jejuni</i>	Standard for breakpoint (NCCLS,...)	Dilution method		
		Breakpoint Resistant >	Range tested concentration (µg/ml)	
			lowest	highest
Aminoglykosid AB				
Gentamicin	EFSA	> 1	0,125	16
Neomycin	EUCAST	> 1	0,125	8
Streptomycin	EFSA	> 2	0,5	32
Betalaktamantibiotika/Betalactamase Inhibitor - Kombination				
Amoxicillin/Clavulan-säure (2:1)	CLSI	> 16	1	64
Quinolone und Quinoxalin				
Ciprofloxacin	EFSA	> 1	0,06	32
Nalidixinsäure	EUCAST	> 16	2	256
Makrolide				
Erythromycin	EFSA	> 4	0,25	128
Penicilline				
Ampicillin	EUCAST	> 8	0,5	64
Phenicole				
Chloramphenicol	EUCAST	> 16	2	64
Polymyxine				
Colistin	DANMAP	> 32	4	128
Tetracycline				
Tetracyclin	EFSA	> 2	0,125	64

Table 46 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter jejuni* in humans, quantitative data

<i>C. jejuni</i> human			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme	yes		
Number of isolates available in the	386		
Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:			
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n
Aminoglykosid AB			
Gentamicin	386	0	0
Neomycin	386	0	0
Streptomycin	386	0,777	3
Betalaktamantibiotika/Betalactamase Inhibitor - Kombination			
Amoxicillin/Clavulan-säure (2:1)	386	0	0
Quinolone und Quinoxalin			
Ciprofloxacin	386	58,29	225
Nalidixinsäure	386	58,03	224
Makrolide			
Erythromycin	386	0	0
Penicilline			
Ampicillin	386	17,88	69
Phenicole			
Chloramphenicol	386	0	0
Polymyxine			
Colistin	386	0	0
Tetracycline			
Tetracyclin	386	32,38	125

<=0,0039	0,007	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	>= 512
n																	
					285	99	2										
					31	201	149	5									
							325	56	2			3					
								198	176	12							
					65	86	8	2		10	129	56	18	12			
									35	97	28	2	1	3	54	161	5
							21	118	204	39	4						
									6	66	170	75	7	15	34	13	
										259	95	24	8				
											340	42	4				
					50	136	47	26	2	2		1	7	36	79		

Table 47 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter jejuni* in broiler flocks - at slaughter - quantitative data [Dilution method]

<i>C. jejuni</i> Gallus gallus																							
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																					
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n	<=0,0039	0,007	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	>= 512		
				n																			
Aminoglykosid AB																							
Gentamicin	125	0	0						84	40	1												
Neomycin	125	0	0						12	49	61	3											
Streptomycin	125	0,8	1								97	27				1							
Betalaktamantibiotika/Betalactamase Inhibitor - Kombination																							
Amoxycillin/Clavulan-säure (2:1)	125	0	0									61	57	7									
Quinolone und Quinoxalin																							
Ciprofloxacin	125	59	74					22	27	2				3	34	26	5	6					
Nalidixinsäure	125	56	70										14	29	11	1			14	50	6		
Makrolide																							
Erythromycin	125	0	0								4	37	68	16									
Penicilline																							
Ampicillin	125	22	28									1	1	25	53	17	2	9	15	2			
Phenicole																							
Chloramphenicol	125	0	0											67	43	8	7						
Polymyxine																							
Colistin	125	0	0												102	23							
Tetracycline																							
Tetracyclin	125	30	37						8	48	18	10	4					7	7	23			

Table 48 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Campylobacter jejuni in humans and broiler slaughter batches

C. jejuni		human			Gallus gallus		
		N	%R	n	N	%R	n
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes			yes		
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		386			125		
Antimicrobials:		N	%R	n	N	%R	n
Aminoglykosid AB							
	Gentamicin	386	0	0	125	0	0
	Neomycin	386	0	0	125	0	0
	Streptomycin	386	0,8	3	125	0,8	1
Betalaktamantibiotika/Betalactamase Inhibitor - Kombination							
	Amoxycillin/Clavulan-säure (2:1)	386	0	0	125	0	0
Quinolone und Quinoxalin							
	Ciprofloxacin	386	58,3	225	125	59,2	74
	Nalidixinsäure	386	58,0	224	125	56	70
Makrolide							
	Erythromycin	386	0	0	125	0	0
Penicilline							
	Ampicillin	386	17,9	69	125	22,4	28
Phenicol							
	Chloramphenicol	386	0	0	125	0	0
Polymyxine							
	Colistin	386	0	0	125	0	0
Tetracycline							
	Tetracyclin	386	32,4	125	125	29,6	37
Number of multiresistant isolates							
	fully sensitive	386	36,0	139	125	36	45
	resistant to 1 antimicrobial	386	36,5	141	125	38,4	48
	resistant to 2 antimicrobials	386	27,5	106	125	25,6	32
	resistant to 3 antimicrobials	386	0		125	0	0
	resistant to 4 antimicrobials	386	0		125	0	0
	resistant to >4 antimicrobials	386	0		125	0	0

Number of multiresistant isolates: For Campylobacter this includes resistance to tetracycline, erythromycin, Nalidixic acid, gentamicin, and streptomycin

Table 49 Breakpoints used for antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter coli*

Test method used	Number of reporting laboratory
Disc diffusion	1
E-test	
Agar dilution	
Broth dilution	

Standards used for testing	The methods are used for investigation of isolates from	
CLSI	Feedingstuff	
other	Animals	x
EN ISO 20776-1	Food	
	Humans	x

<i>Campylobacter coli</i>	Standard for breakpoint (NCCLS,...)	Dilution method		
		Breakpoint	Range tested	
			concentration (µg/ml)	
		Resistant >	lowest	highest
Aminoglykosid AB				
Gentamicin	EFSA	> 2	0,125	16
Neomycin	EUCAST	> 2	0,125	8
Streptomycin	EFSA	> 4	0,5	32
Betalaktamantibiotika/Betalactamase Inhibitor - Kombination				
Amoxicillin/Clavulan-säure (2:1)	CLSI	> 16	1	64
Quinolone und Quinoxalin				
Ciprofloxacin	EFSA	> 1	0,06	32
Nalidixinsäure	EUCAST	> 32	2	256
Makrolide				
Erythromycin	EFSA	> 16	0,25	128
Penicilline				
Ampicillin	EUCAST	> 16	0,5	64
Phenicol				
Chloramphenicol	EUCAST	> 16	2	64
Polymyxine				
Colistin	DANMAP	> 32	4	128
Tetracycline				
Tetracyclin	EFSA	> 2	0,125	64

Table 50 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter coli* in humans quantitative data

<i>C. coli</i> human																						
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																				
Number of isolates available in the laboratory																						
Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																						
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n	<=0,0039	0,007	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	>= 512	
Aminoglykosid AB				n																		
Gentamicin	40	2,5	1						8	26	5											
Neomycin	40	2,5	1							9	26	4					1					
Streptomycin	40	15	6								11	20	3			3		3				
Betalaktamantibiotika/Betalactamase Inhibitor - Kombination																						
Amoxycillin/Clavulan-säure (2:1)	40											1	9	26	3	1						
Quinolone und Quinoxalin																						
Ciprofloxacin	40	72,5	29					4	6	1			1	5	10	11	1	1				
Nalidixinsäure	40	72,5	29											7	4			1	17	11		
Makrolide																						
Erythromycin	40	5	2							1	11	8	15	3								2
Penicilline																						
Ampicillin	40	10	4											6	16	14		1	3			
Phenicole																						
Chloramphenicol	40	2,5	1										7	14	17	1			1			
Polymyxine																						
Colistin	40													39	1							
Tetracycline																						
Tetracyclin	40	45	18						3	10	5	4						1	17			

Table 51 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter coli* in broiler slaughter batches - quantitative data [Dilution method]

<i>C. coli</i> <i>Gallus gallus</i>																						
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																					
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n	<=0,0039	0,007	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	>= 512	
Aminoglykosid AB				n																		
Gentamicin	47	0	0						6	38	3											
Neomycin	47	2,13	1						1	7	37	1					1					
Streptomycin	47	25,53	12								11	22	2				6	4	2			
Betalaktamantibiotika/Betalactamase Inhibitor - Kombination																						
Amoxycillin/Clavulan-säure (2:1)	47	0	0									2	22	17	4	2						
Quinolone und Quinoxalin																						
Ciprofloxacin	47	70,21	33					8	6				2	6	11	8	6					
Nalidixinsäure	47	70,21	33										1	9	4				1	22	10	
Makrolide																						
Erythromycin	47	6,38	3							5	12	7	16	4								3
Penicilline																						
Ampicillin	47	12,77	6												18	17	6		1	5		
Phenicole																						
Chloramphenicol	47	0	0										9	26	12							
Polymyxine																						
Colistin	47	0	0												46	1						
Tetracycline																						
Tetracyclin	47	51,06	24						2	16	4	1							3	21		

Table 52 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Campylobacter coli in broiler slaughter batches - quantitative data [Dilution method]

		human			Gallus gallus		
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes			yes		
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		40			47		
Antimicrobials:		N	%R	n	N	%R	n
Aminoglykosid AB							
	Gentamicin	40	2,5	1	47	0	0
	Neomycin	40	2,5	1	47	2,1	1
	Streptomycin	40	15	6	47	25,5	12
Betalaktamantibiotika/Betalactamase Inhibitor - Kombination							
	Amoxycillin/Clavulan-säure (2:1)	40	0	0	47	0,0	0
Quinolone und Quinoxalin							
	Ciprofloxacin	40	72,5	29	47	70,2	33
	Nalidixinsäure	40	72,5	29	47	70,2	33
Makrolide							
	Erythromycin	40	5	2	47	6,4	3
Penicilline							
	Ampicillin	40	10	4	47	12,8	6
Phenicole							
	Chloramphenicol	40	2,5	1	47	0,0	0
Polymyxine							
	Colistin	40	0	0	47	0,0	0
Tetracycline							
	Tetracyclin	40	45	18	47	51,1	24
Number of multiresistant isolates							
	fully sensitive	40	25,0	10	47	23,4	11
	resistant to 1 antimicrobial	40	30,0	12	47	21,3	10
	resistant to 2 antimicrobials	40	30,0	12	47	36,2	17
	resistant to 3 antimicrobials	40	12,5	5	47	17,0	8
	resistant to 4 antimicrobials	40	0,0	0	47	2,1	1
	resistant to >4 antimicrobials	40	2,5	1	47	0,0	0

Number of multiresistant isolates: For Campylobacter this includes resistance to tetracycline, erythromycin, Nalidixic acid, gentamicin, and streptomycin

4.3. Listeriosis

4.3.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Listeriosis can be regarded as a relatively rare infectious disease in Austria with an annual incidence between 0.1 and 0.25 cases per 100,000 inhabitants in the years 1996 to 2007. In 2008 a total of 31 culturally verified human cases of listeriosis were recorded for Austria (incidence 0.38 per 100,000 inhabitants), four of them were associated with pregnancy. In 2009 a further increase had to be assessed, 46 cases what corresponds to an incidence of 0.6. Two cases were associated with pregnancy. The incidences are similar to those of most other western European countries (0.2-0.9). Lethality was high with 26% (12 out of 46) in 2009. This (usually) high rate and the sometimes severe permanent disabilities demand every effort to ascertain potential food-associated outbreaks as early as possible.

A multinational food borne outbreak of listeriosis affected 34 persons (8 fatal cases) in Austria, Germany and Czech Republic between June 2009 and February 2010 due to consumption of "Quargel" cheese produced in Austria. In 2009, the outbreak accounted for 13 Austrian outbreak cases, including five cases with lethal outcome. (Fretz R et al. Listeriosis outbreak caused by acid curd cheese 'Quargel', Austria and Germany 2009. Euro Surveill. 2010;15(5) pii=19477. Available from: <http://www.eurosurveillance.org/ViewArticle.aspx?ArticleId=19477> ; Fretz R et al. Update: Multinational listeriosis outbreak due to 'Quargel', a sour milk curd cheese, caused by two different L. monocytogenes serotype 1/2a strains, 2009-2010 . Euro Surveill. 2010;15(16):pii=19543. Available online: <http://www.eurosurveillance.org/ViewArticle.aspx?ArticleId=19543>).

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

See History of the disease

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Listeriosis is a rare disease, but not a rare bacterium, which means that a systemic disease develops only under certain particular predispositions, including pregnancy and immunosuppression. Although dairy products and salmon are likely candidates, the source of an infection often remains unclear. Ready-to-eat meat and meat products harbour listeria in 0–7 % and ready-to-eat smoked fish in approx. 10 %.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

A monthly report is sent to the Ministry of Health by the National Reference Center, whereas outbreaks are reported immediately.

Restrictions tightened to sell unpasteurised milk in remote areas (Alps).

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

More widespread information for pregnant and immunocompromised persons should be provided.

Additional information

The National Reference Laboratory in the AGES (Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety) Vienna coordinates the confirmation, subtyping and comparison of isolates.

4.3.2. Listeriosis in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

A monthly report is sent to the Ministry of Health by the National Reference Center, whereas outbreaks are reported immediately.

Case definition

A clinically compatible case that is laboratory confirmed after isolation of *L. monocytogenes* from a normally sterile site or vaginal swabs.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Bacteriology: Smears of the samples are Gram stained. Specimen from normally sterile sites are inoculated in blood culture broth or thioglycollate broth and Columbia blood agar plates, vaginal swabs are plated only directly on Columbia blood and colistin-nalidixic acid (CNA) agar. *L. monocytogenes* is identified by catalase and Api Listeria test.

Stool samples were examined after cold enrichment in Fraser enrichment broth and streaked onto selective chromogenic agar plate and Columbia blood-agar. All isolates obtained in Austria are sent to the National Reference Center for confirmation, subtyping by PCR and PFGE and comparison.

Notification system in place

Medical doctors specialised in Laboratory Diagnosis or Microbiology and Hygiene and the attended physicians are subjected to notification. Suspected, confirmed and lethal cases of invasive listeriosis have to be notified according to the national Epidemic Act.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

History of the disease in chapter general evaluation.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

History of the disease

Relevance as zoonotic disease

Listeriosis is a rare disease, but not a rare bacterium, which means that a systemic disease develops only under certain particular predispositions, including pregnancy and immunosuppression. Although dairy products and salmon are likely candidates, the source of an infection often remains unclear.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Annual report of the National Reference Centre:

http://www.bmg.gv.at/cms/site/attachments/0/5/0/CH0954/CMS1268584443598/jb_listeriose_2009_25_02_10.pdf

Data source of Tables 52 and 53: Primary isolates from patients typed in the national reference centre for listeria

Table 53 Listeriosis in humans - species/serotype distribution

	Cases	Incidence /100,000 population
Listeriosis	46	0,6
<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> 1/2a	29	0,3
<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> 1/2b	8	0,1
<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> 4b	9	0,1
Congenital cases	2	0,0
Deaths	12	0,1

Table 54 Listeriosis in humans - age distribution

Age group	Listeriosis			<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 1,2a			<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 1,2b			<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 4b		
	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F
< 1 year	2	-	2	1	-	1	-	-	-	1	-	1
1 to 4 years	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
5 to 14 years	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
15 to 24 years	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
25 to 44 years	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
45 to 64 years	12	11	1	8	8	-	2	1	1	2	2	-
65 years and older	32	22	10	20	14	6	6	3	3	6	5	1
Age unknown	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
All age groups	46	33	13	29	22	7	8	4	4	9	7	2

4.3.3. *Listeria* spp. in foodstuffs

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Foodstuff was sampled according to the ordinance „Revisions- und Probenplan für das Jahr 2009 gemäß §31 LMSVG; Richtlinien über die Vollziehung der Überwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Berichtsschema 2008“ (BMGFJ – 75500/0332-IV/B/7/2008) from the Federal Ministry of Health. This “Revisions- und Probenplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2007-2010) according to Art. 41 ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004.

The Revision-Plan determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be sampled and tested randomly according to the number of food enterprises per province. Every business within Austria has to be sampled at least once per year. The inspection can comprise sampling, hygienic investigations of the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes etc.

In 2009, approximately 40,000 samples were planned to be tested in Austria. About 60% (24,000) of these are planned samples (surveillance) and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). These planned samples either consist of samples of the yearly sampling plan which determines the number of samples of each food category that have to be investigated randomly, e.g. raw meat (fresh or frozen); sausages; cheeses; milk; preserved food etc. There are different sampling stages where food samples are taken: e.g. from retail, processing plant, primary production.

In addition there is a monitoring plan for food items (40-45 campaigns per year). In the course of these programs food items of special interest for defined parameters – amongst others zoonotic agents – are investigated. The sampling takes place during a fixed period of time in order to gain in-depth information. In 2009, seven relevant food campaign programs were conducted throughout Austria (Schwerpunktprogramm 2009 BMGFJ-75500/0242-IV/B/7/2008). Details and results of these campaigns can be found in the respective chapters.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up surveillance programs; a folder was created by the AGES in cooperation with the Austrian Medical Chamber: Pregnancy – infections transmitted via food (Schwangerschaft – Infektionen durch Nahrungsmittel, http://www.ages.at/uploads/media/AGES_Folder_Schwangerschaft_Web.pdf). This folder was distributed to all gynaecologists. The folder contains advices to prevent food-borne infections during pregnancy, including listeriosis, toxoplasmosis, campylobacteriosis and salmonellosis as well as mycotoxicosis.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Campaign A-801-09: Listeria in food - Meat from farmed game- land mammals – meat products – fermented sausages - at retail - Surveillance - official controls - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: October – December

Type of specimen taken

Meat from farmed game – fermented sausages

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of Listeria in 25g

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up surveillance programs

Results of the investigation

85 samples tested for Listeria: 8 samples <10 CFU/ml, 1 sample 20 CFU/ml, 3 x L. innocua

Additional information

Samples were also tested for STEC and Salmonella spp.

Campaign A-026-09: Listeria in food - Meat from pig – meat products – cooked, ready-to-eat - at retail - Surveillance - official controls - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: June - September

Type of specimen taken

Meat from pig – meat products – cooked, ready-to-eat

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of Listeria in 25g

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up surveillance programs

Results of the investigation

101 samples tested for Listeria: 8–times positive <10 CFU/g

Campaign A-800-09: Listeria in food – fishery products - cold-smoked fish - at retail - Surveillance - official controls - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: January - March

Type of specimen taken

Fishery products - cold-smoked fish

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of Listeria in 25g

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up surveillance programs

Results of the investigation

65 samples tested for Listeria: 1-time positive 15,000 CFU/g, 9-times positive in 25g, 2-times positive for *L. innocua*, 1-time positive for *L. welshimeri*

Campaign A-802-09: Listeria in food – raw milk - intended for direct human consumption - at farm - Surveillance - official controls - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at farm (unpasteurised milk vending machine) by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: April - June

Type of specimen taken

Raw milk - intended for direct human consumption

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of Listeria in 25g

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up surveillance programs

Results of the investigation

71 samples tested for Listeria: 1 positive <10 CFU/ml

Additional information

Samples were also tested for STEC, thermotolerant *Campylobacter* and *Salmonella* spp.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used at the production plant or at retail

Qualitative detection of *Listeria* spp. is performed according to ISO 11290: Part 1 (1996).

Quantification of *Listeria* spp. content in food is conducted either according to ISO 11290: Part 2 (1998) with following modifications: *Listeria monocytogenes* are confirmed on Ottaviani Agosti Agar, ALOA Agar, RapidLmono agar, using Gram stain, motility testing and catalase production or by the Api *Listeria* test or Vidas LMO II.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infections

Listeria monocytogenes was detected in one sample (1.9%) of pasteurised cows' milk (1/53) – the content of *L. monocytogenes* was < 100 cfu/g. In all the 115 tested samples of raw cows' milk 4 samples were found positive for *L. monocytogenes*, 1-time < 100 cfu/g.

18.9 % of samples from fishery products (10/53) revealed a contamination with *L. monocytogenes* (2 of them < 100 cfu/g). Also in 2 of 49 ready-to-eat pig meat product samples (4%) both of them showed an amount of *L. monocytogenes* <100 cfu/g. In 28 of 273 cold smoked fish samples (10.3%) were positive for *L. monocytogenes* – 2 samples showed an amount >100 cfu/g, additionally *L. innocua* was found 1-time and *L. welshimeri* 2-times.

Table 55 Listeria monocytogenes in milk and milky products

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling unit	Sampling weight	Units tested total units positive	for L. monocytogenes	Units tested with detection method	L. monocytogenes presence in x g	Units tested with enumeration method
Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk		single	25g	2	0	2		2
Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		single	25g	3	0	3		3
Cheeses made from cows' milk - unspecified - made from pasteurised milk	at catering	single	25g	4	0	4		4
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	90	0	90		43
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	55	0	46		48
	at retail - imported	single	25g	33	0	29		30
Cheeses made from cows' milk - unspecified - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at catering	single	25g	174	0	174		173
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	56	1	56	1	27
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	24	0	23		19
Cheeses made from unspecified milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk		single	25g	13	0	13		13
Cheeses made from cow milk - hard - made from pasteurised milk		single	25g	20	0	20		19
Cheeses made from cow milk - hard - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		single	25g	18	0	18		3
Cheeses made from unspecified milk - spreadable		single	25g	2	0	2		2
Cheeses made from unspecified milk - curd		single	25g	8	0	8		8
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - unspecified - made from pasteurised milk	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	30	0	30		13
	at retail - imported	single	25g	11	1	10	1	7
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - unspecified - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	15	0	15		8
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	3	0	3		2
Cheeses made from goat milk - soft and semi-soft milk - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		single	25g	5	0	5		5
Cheeses made from sheep milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk		single	25g	1	0	0		0
Cheeses made from sheep milk - soft and semi-soft milk - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		single	25g	1	0	1		1
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - butter	at catering	single	25g	6	0	6		6
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	12	0	11		10
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	5	0	5		5
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - sour milk		single	25g	2	0	2		2
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy desserts	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	4	0	4		4
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	3	0	3		3
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy desserts chilled		single	25g	16	0	16		16
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy products, not specified	at catering	single	25g	4	0	4		2
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	38	0	35		29
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	9	0	8		9
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - fermented dairy products		single	25g	2	0	2		2
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - ice-cream	at catering	single	25g	1	0	1		0
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	6	0	6		0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - yoghurt		single	25g	17	0	17		17
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - probiotic drinks		single	25g	1	0	1		1
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - cream made from pasteurised milk		single	25g	48	0	48		48
Milk, cows' - pasteurised milk	at catering	single	25g	4	0	4		3
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	38	1	38	1	13
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	11	0	11		10
Milk, cows' - raw	at farm	single	25g	22	2	22	2	22
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	5	0	5		5
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	6	0	6		4
Milk - raw - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - intended for direct human consumption (Campaign A-4)	at farm (unpasteurised milk vending machine)	single	25g	71	1	71	1	71
	at farm	single	25g	2	1	2	1	2
Milk, cows' - raw milk for manufacture - intended for manufacture of raw or low heat-treated products	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	5	0	5		5
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	4	0	4		4
Milk, goats' - raw		single	25g	2	0	2		2
Milk, sheep's - raw		single	25g	2	0	2		2

Table 56 *Listeria monocytogenes* in other foods

Food	Sampling stage	Sampling unit	Sampling weight	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Listeria</i>	Units tested with detection method	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> presence in x.g.	Units tested with enumeration method
Bakery products - cakes	at catering	single	25g	5	0	5	0	5
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	32	0	32	0	24
Bakery products - pastry	at catering	single	25g	13	0	13	0	12
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	1	0	1	0	1
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	80	1	80	1	72
Confectionery products and pastes	at catering	single	25g	10	0	10	0	10
Fish - raw	at catering	single	25g	4	1	4	1	4
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	5	2	5	2	3
Fishery products, unspecified	at catering	single	25g	3	0	2	0	2
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	21	6	14	5	20
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	20	1	20	1	19
	at retail - imported	single	25g	32	4	32	3	32
Fishery products - unspecified - ready-to-eat	at catering	single	25g	33	5	33	5	33
Fishery products - crustaceans - cooked	at catering	single	25g	2	0	2	0	2
Fishery products - smoked fish	at catering	single	25g	208	18	208	18	208
Fishery products - smoked fish - cold (Campaign A-800-09)	at retail	single	25g	65	10	65	10	65
Fruits - products	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	2	0	2	0	1
	at catering	single	25g	1	0	1	0	1
Fruits - pre-cut ready-to-eat	at catering	single	25g	7	0	7	0	7
Infant formula	at retail - imported	single	25g	1	0	1	0	0
Juice fruit - juice unpasteurised	at catering	single	25g	9	0	9	0	9
Juice vegetable - juice unpasteurised	at catering	single	25g	5	0	5	0	5
Juice mixed - juice unpasteurised	at catering	single	25g	3	0	3	0	3
other food	at catering	single	25g	1	0	1	0	0
	at hospital or care home	single	25g	4	0	4	0	0
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	2	1	2	1	0
Meat from bovine - fresh		single	25g	2	0	2	0	2
Meat from bovine - meat products - ready-to-eat		single	25g	2	0	2	0	2
Meat from bovine animals - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	2	0	2	0	2
Meat from bovine animals and pig - meat products	at catering	single	25g	7	0	7	0	7
Meat from deer (venison) - meat preparation	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	1	0	1	0	1
Meat from deer (venison) - meat products	at game handling establishment	single	25g	7	1	6	1	7
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	2	1	2	1	2
Meat from pig - fresh	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	1	1	1	1	1
Meat from pig - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	at catering	single	25g	12	1	11	1	12
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	18	1	14	1	12
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	31	1	29	1	18
Meat from pig - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat (Campaign A-026-09)	at retail	single	25g	101	8	101	8	101
Meat from pig - meat products - pate	at catering	single	25g	7		7		7
Meat from pig - meat products - cooked - ham sliced	at catering	single	25g	3		3		3
Meat from pig - meat products - cooked - ham non-sliced	at catering	single	25g	4		4		4
Meat from pig - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw	at catering	single	25g	2		2		1
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	8	2	7	2	8
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	14	1	13	1	12
Meat from pig - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked	at catering	single	25g	1		1		0
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	4		4		3
	at catering	single	25g	1		1		1
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	1		1		0
	at retail - imported	single	25g	6		6		0
Meat from poultry, species - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	at catering	single	25g	16		16		16
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	1		1		0
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - fermented sausages	at catering	single	25g	5	1	5	1	5
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	19	1	14	1	17
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	23		23		11
Meat from wild game - land mammals meat products fermented sausages (Campaign A-801-09)	at retail	single	25g	86	10	86	10	86
Meat, mixed meat - meat products - fermented sausages	at catering	single	25g	19	2	19	2	19
Meat, mixed meat - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked chilled		single	25g	7		7		7
Meat, mixed meat - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked frozen		single	25g	5		5		5
Mushrooms	at retail	single	25g	3		3		3
Other food	at catering	single	25g	24		12		20
	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	6		5		4
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	14	1	14	1	10
Other food - products and prepared dishes - pasta	at catering	single	25g	4		4		4
Other food - products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods - chilled	at catering	single	25g	1		1		1
Other food - products and prepared dishes - unspecified - non-ready-to-eat foods - chilled	at catering	single	25g	4	0	4	0	4
Other food - products and prepared dishes - sandwiches with meat	at catering	single	25g	1		1		1
Ready-to-eat salads	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	3		3		0
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	6		5		4
Sauces and dressings	at retail	single	25g	1		1		1
Sauces and dressings - mayonnaise	at catering	single	25g	3		3		3
Vegetables	at retail - imported	single	25g	4		4		2

4.3.4. *Listeria* spp. in animals

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

There is no active surveillance system and detection of cases is based on clinical observations.

Frequency of the sampling

When there is a suspected case of invasive listeriosis.

Case definition

A case may be defined with positive histopathology and/or positive bacteriology. The animal is the epidemiological unit.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

The diagnostic methods used include histopathology and bacteriology.

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

None

Notification system in place

No notification system of listeriosis in animal species available at this time.

Results of the investigation**National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection****Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)**

No relevance because products of sick animals are not used for human consumption.

Table 57 Listeria spp. in animals

animal species	sampling context	sampling details	Source of information	sampling unit	Units tested	Total units positive for Listeria	L. monocytogenes
cattle	at farm - animal sample - clinical investigations	foetus/stillbirth	AGES IVET	animal	4	4	4
cattle	at farm - animal sample - clinical investigations	organs	AGES IVET	animal	34	24	24
chicken	at farm - animal sample - clinical investigations	organs	AGES IVET	animal	1	1	1
deer	animal sample - clinical investigations	organs	AGES IVET	animal	10	2	2
goat	at farm - animal sample - clinical investigations	organs	AGES IVET	animal	24	20	20
goat	at farm - animal sample - clinical investigations	foetus/stillbirth	AGES IVET	animal	1	1	1
horse	at farm - animal sample - clinical investigations	organs	AGES IVET	animal	2	1	1

animal species	sampling context	sampling details	Source of information	sampling unit	Units tested	Total units positive for Listeria	L. monocytogenes
pig	at farm - animal sample - clinical investigations	organs	AGES IVET	animal	1	1	1
rabbit	at farm - animal sample - clinical investigations	organs	AGES IVET	animal	1	0	0
sheep	at farm - animal sample - clinical investigations	foetus/stillbirth	AGES IVET	animal	2	2	2
sheep	at farm - animal sample - clinical investigations	organs	AGES IVET	animal	21	13	13

AGES IVET: AGES Institutes for Veterinary Disease Control

4.4. Verotoxic Escherichia coli

4.4.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

In the year 2009, 528 samples were investigated at the Austrian Reference Center for Enterohemorrhagic Escherichia coli (EHEC). Thereby, 86 human isolates (from 84 patients) were confirmed, comprising 59 human EHEC and 27 human LP-STECS (Shiga toxin producing E. coli without eae-gene) isolates. In addition, 7 serologically identified EHEC cases were diagnosed (91 human cases in total). The ratio of EHEC O157 (23 isolates and 7 serologic cases) to EHEC non-O157 (36) was similar to the year before. Among the 91 diagnosed human EHEC and STEC cases in 2009, 13 cases were diagnosed with hemolytic uremic syndrome (HUS) as post infectious complication (9 caused by O157, 3 by O26:H- and 1 by O111:H-). The incidence of HUS in children in Austria due to EHEC and STEC was about 0.76 HUS-case per 100.000 children (10 children) of age between 0 and 14 years in the year 2009.

The number of EHEC/STEC cases varied markedly between the different provinces, led by the province Tyrol with 33 confirmed human EHEC/STEC cases. The reason for that may lie in a new EHEC screening program initiated in 2004.

There were no big outbreaks in Austria in 2009, only 9 small family outbreaks.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

See History of the disease

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

The prevalence of isolated VTEC from calves but also from other cattle increased to 30% and from sheep to 70%, but we hypothesize that this is due to a higher sensitivity of the new ELISA, the sampling material (rectum-anal swabs) and improvement in the VTEC isolation techniques (see chapter Pathogenic Escherichia coli in animals). Concerning the 5 most important VTEC serotypes for humans (O157, O26, O103, O111 and O145), only O157 (2 x), O103 (2 x) and O26 (3x) were isolated from 341 animal samples.

The relevance of findings of VTEC in faeces seems to be low because VTEC are found only in a very low prevalence on meat samples from bovines and sheep.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

An Austrian wide monitoring program on the trends of VTEC prevalence in bovine animals and sheep was implemented according to the directive 2003/99/EC of the European Parliament and the Council of 17 November 2003 in the National Orders. The sampling was carried out throughout 2009 and follow up programs will be implemented in the forthcoming years.

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Increased awareness and information should be made available for parents, paediatricians and general practitioners in regard to food safety and the prevention of infection.

Additional information

The National Reference Center at the Innsbruck Medical University coordinates the confirmation, subtyping and comparison of human isolates. In addition, the Reference Center is involved in outbreak investigations. When EHEC is diagnosed in a patient, the patients as well as their families are interviewed using a questionnaire. The questionnaire helps obtain the necessary information in regard to the characteristics of the illness and potential exposure 6 days prior to onset. Thus, the Reference Center contributes to finding the source of infection. The Reference Center also reports

EHEC cases and coordinates environmental investigations with the Local and Regional Health Authorities.

4.4.2. Verocytotoxic Escherichia coli in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

The National Reference Center provides a monthly report discussing recent outbreaks to the Ministry of Health.

Case definition

Clinical description: Clinical picture compatible with EHEC infection, e.g. diarrhoea (often bloody) and abdominal cramps. Illness may be complicated by haemolytic uraemic syndrome (HUS) or thrombotic thrombocytopenic purpura (TTP).

Laboratory criteria for diagnosis: Detection of genes coding for Stx1/Stx2 production.

For probable cases: Isolation of E. coli belonging to a serogroup known to cause enterohaemorrhagic disease.

Serological confirmation in patients with HUS or TTP (only in selected cases).

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

1. Detection of E. coli O157 (most prominent serotype in HUS cases):

- Bacteriology: Isolation of O157 colonies on Sorbitol-MacConkey agar after incubation for 24 hours at 37 °C. O157 is confirmed via the E. coli O157 Latex Test.

- Serology: This method is constantly used at the German HUS-"Konsiliarlabor"; anti-O157 antibodies of IgG and IgM types can be distinguished.

2. Detection of Verotoxin (VTEC)-producing strains (used at the National Reference Center for EHEC/VTEC/STEC in Innsbruck): Stools are enriched overnight in a medium containing mitomycin C (EHEC Direct Medium, Heipha, Heidelberg, Germany). Enriched cultures are investigated for presence of Shiga toxins by commercial EIA (e.g. Premier, Novitec). Isolate identification is further confirmed by conventional biochemical tests (API 20 E, bioMerieux, Marcy-l'Etoile, France).

Enrichments are plated on Sorbitol-MacConkey agar and incubated for 24 hours at 37 °C. Detection of stx1 and stx2 genes and of the genes encoding EHEC hemolysin (hlyA) and intimin (eae) is done by PCR (Gerber et al. (2002) J Infect Dis 186:493-500).

All EHEC/STEC/VTEC isolates obtained in Austria are to be sent to the National Reference Center for confirmation, subtyping and comparison. All Shiga toxin producing E. coli are serotyped with E. coli antisera (E. coli antisera, Statens Serum Institut, Copenhagen, Denmark). Comparison of the isolates is done by Pulsed-Field-Gel-Electrophoresis and Ribotyping.

Notification system in place

Notification of Verotoxin (VTEC) according to the epidemic act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): The attending physicians and the laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

See History of the disease

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

See History of the disease

Relevance as a zoonotic disease

HUS is a rare complication of E. coli infection; however EHECs themselves are not rare, which means that a systemic disease develops only under certain particular predispositions, most of which are currently unknown. Although raw or undercooked meat and unpasteurised dairy products are likely

candidates to transfer the bacterium to humans, the actual source of infection often remains unclear. The importance of hand hygiene after animal contact should be always considered.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Annual Report of the National Reference Center 2008 (Report 2009 not available yet):

<http://www.bmg.gv.at/cms/site/attachments/8/9/1/CH0954/CMS1253514069547/ehec-jahresbericht-2008-revised-final.pdf>

Data source of Tables 57 and 58: Primary isolates from patients typed in the national reference centre for EHEC (VTEC)

Table 58 Verocytotoxic Escherichia coli infections in human - species/serotype distribution

	Cases	Incidence /100,000 population	Autochtone	Imported	unknown
HUS					
- clinical cases	13	0.2			13
- lab. confirmed cases	13	0.2			13
- caused by O157 (VT+)	9	0.1			9
- caused by other VTEC	4	0.0			4
E. coli infect. (except HUS)					
- clinical cases	78	0.9			78
- laboratory confirmed	78	0.9			78
- caused by O157 (VT+)	21	0.3			21
- caused by other VTEC	57	0.7			56

Table 59 Verocytotoxic Escherichia coli infections in human - age distribution

Age group	Verotoxigenic <i>E. coli</i> (VTEC)			<i>E. coli</i> infections O157			<i>E. coli</i> infections non-O157			<i>HUS</i> cases		
	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F
< 1 year	5	2	3	2	1	1	3	1	2	-	-	-
1 to 4 years	51	30	21	16	13	3	35	17	18	7	5	2
5 to 14 years	14	6	8	5	1	4	9	5	4	3	-	3
15 to 24 years	3	1	2	1	-	1	2	1	1	1	-	1
25 to 44 years	11	4	7	6	2	4	5	2	3	2	1	1
45 to 64 years	5	3	2	-	-	-	5	3	2	-	-	-
65 years and older	2	1	1	-	-	-	2	1	1	-	-	-
Age unknown	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
All age groups	91	47	44	30	17	13	61	30	31	13	6	7

4.4.3. Pathogenic Escherichia coli in foodstuffs

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Foodstuff was sampled according to the ordinance „Revisions- und Probenplan für das Jahr 2009 gemäß §31 LMSVG; Richtlinien über die Vollziehung der Überwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Berichtsschema 2008“ (BMGFJ – 75500/0332-IV/B/7/2008) from the Federal Ministry of Health. This “Revisions- und Probenplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2007-2010) according to Art. 41 ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004.

The Revision-Plan determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be sampled and tested randomly according to the number of food enterprises per province. Every business within Austria has to be sampled at least once per year. The inspection can comprise sampling, hygienic investigations of the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes etc.

In 2009, approximately 40,000 samples were planned to be tested in Austria. About 60% (24,000) of these are planned samples (surveillance) and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). These planned samples either consist of samples of the yearly sampling plan which determines the number of samples of each food category that have to be investigated randomly, e.g. raw meat (fresh or frozen); sausages; cheeses; milk; preserved food etc. There are different sampling stages where food samples are taken: e.g. from retail, processing plant, primary production.

In addition there is a monitoring plan for food items (40-45 campaigns per year). In the course of these programs food items of special interest for defined parameters – amongst others zoonotic agents – are investigated. The sampling takes place during a fixed period of time in order to gain in-depth information. In 2009, seven relevant food campaign programs were conducted throughout Austria (Schwerpunktprogramm 2009 BMGFJ-75500/0242-IV/B/7/2008). Details and results of these campaigns can be found in the respective chapters.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

25 g of the sample is pre-enriched using modified tryptic soy broth containing novobiocin (mTSB + n) for 24h at 37 °C. Subsequently about 1 microliter is plated on trypton-bile-glucuronid (TBX) for 24h at 37 °C. 5 colonies per plate are identified as E. coli (indole positive, glucuronidase positive or using enterotube. E. coli are tested in a multiplex PCR for stx1 and stx2 (Brian et al, 1992. Polymerase chain reaction for diagnosis of enterohemorrhagic Escherichia coli infection and haemolytic-uremic syndrome. J Clin Microbiol 30, 1801-06).

The typing for virulence factors as the eae-gene and serotyping is carried out by the National Reference Laboratory for VTEC in the AGES Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED) in Graz.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Campaign A-801-09: VTEC in food - Meat from farmed game- land mammals – meat products – fermented sausages - at retail - Surveillance - official controls - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: October – December

Type of specimen taken

Meat from farmed game – fermented sausages

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of VTEC in 25g

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up surveillance programs

Results of the investigation

85 samples tested, VTEC: 2-times positive (non-O157, one O146:H21)

Additional information

Samples were also tested for Salmonella spp. and Listeria monocytogenes

Campaign A-802-09: VTEC in food – raw milk - intended for direct human consumption - at farm -
Surveillance - official controls - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at farm (unpasteurised milk vending machine) by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: April - June

Type of specimen taken

Raw milk - intended for direct human consumption

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of STEC in 25g

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up surveillance programs

Results of the investigation

71 samples tested for VTEC: 0 positive

Additional information

Samples were also tested for thermotolerant Campylobacter, Listeria monocytogenes and Salmonella spp.

Table 60 Verocytotoxic Escherichia coli in food

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Units tested	Total units positive for VTEC		
					VTEC non-O157	O146:H21	
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy products, not specified	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	1	0		
Food intended for direct human consumption	at farm	single	25g	4	0		
Meat, red meat - farmed game - land mammals - meat products		single	25g	5	3	3	
Meat from pig - fresh	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	2	0		
Meat from pig - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	4	0		
Meat from wild game - land mammals meat products fermented sausages (Campaign A-801-09)	at retail	single	25g	86	2	1	1
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - fermented sausages	at processing plant - domestic production	single	25g	9	0		
	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	8	0		
Meat, mixed meat - meat products - fermented sausages	at catering	single	25g	8	0		
Milk, cows' - raw	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	2	0		
Milk, sheep's - raw milk - for manufacture of raw or low heat-treated products	at farm	single	25g	1	0		
Milk - raw - made from raw or low heat-treated milk - intended for direct human consumption (Campaign A-802-09)	at farm (unpasteurised milk vending machine)	single	25g	71	0		
Mushrooms	at retail - domestic production	single	25g	1	0		

4.4.4. Pathogenic Escherichia coli in animals

A. Verotoxigenic Escherichia coli in cattle (bovine animals)

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

The monitoring program on the prevalence of VTEC in slaughtered animals: In the previous years, a higher prevalence of VTEC in calves could be observed compared to cattle of other age groups. In 2009, two monitoring programs were implemented, one on calves and one on cattle older than 1 year. Therefore, 96 slaughtered calves and 80 slaughtered cattle older than 1 year had to be tested in 2009; this was based on the approx. 86,000 calves and 590,000 cattle (except calves) slaughtered in 2008.

The sampling was stratified based on the number of processed animals per abattoir in Austria. The date of sampling was randomized over the year 2009. Sampling was performed in the 37 abattoirs which processed more than 80 % of Austria's cattle in 2008.

Frequency of the sampling

Animals at slaughter

The sampling was distributed randomly over the period of the study from January to December 2009.

Type of specimen taken

Animals at slaughter

A part of rectum and anus

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Animals at slaughter

The sampling is performed by qualified veterinarians who carry out the post – mortem inspection. At time of evisceration, a part of rectum and anus was sampled. After cooling down to 4 °C, the sample had been sent to the AGES Institute of Veterinary Diseases Control (IVET) in Graz the same day, in a hobbox or polystyrene box along with cooling packs. In the laboratory, a swab from the rectum-anal mucosa was incubated in a broth.

Case definition

Animals at slaughter

An animal is considered to be infected with VTEC following the isolation of VTEC (verotoxin producing E. coli irrespective of intimin) from its rectum-anal mucosa.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Animals at slaughter

In a first step the samples were screened for presence of verotoxins by ELISA, secondly the positive samples were processed for VTEC isolation.

At first the swab was pre-enriched using modified tryptic soy broth containing novobiocin (mTSB + n) for 5 hours at 37 °C on a shaker. Then 1 ml of each pre-enrichment was inoculated into mTSB + n containing mitomycin C for 18-20 hours at 37 °C on a shaker too. The process was followed by testing the enrichment for the occurrence of verotoxin in an enzyme linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA, Premier TM EHEC). Positive enrichments were plated on MacConkey (MAC) -, on cefixime tellurite sorbitol MAC (CTSMAC) - and on enterohemolysin agar and incubated for 24 hours at 37 °C. 2-4 colonies from each of the plates were subcultured on MAC as well as on CTSMAC. Afterwards the genomes of subcultured E. coli were investigated in a real time PCR for harboring the genes for

Verotoxin 1, Verotoxin 2, Intimin and Enterohemolysin (Reischl U. et al. 2002: Real-Time Fluorescence PCR Assays for Detection and Characterization of Shiga Toxin, Intim and Enterohemolysin Genes from Shiga Toxin-Producing Escherichia coli. Journ of Clin Microb, 40, p 2555-2565).

The serotyping was carried out by the National Reference Laboratory for VTEC in the AGES Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED) in Graz.

Statistical analysis was performed with EpiInfo version 3.5.1.

Vaccination policy

No vaccination

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

No measures

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Harmonization of methods with regard to all possible VTEC serotypes.

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

No measures foreseen

Notification system in place

No notification system in place at this time.

Results of the investigation

Calves: Verotoxin was detected in 45 of 94 samples, VTEC could be isolated from 26 verotoxin-positive samples, 2 x O157. In several samples more than one VTEC serotype was identified.

Cattle (other than calves): Verotoxin was detected in 44 of 78 samples, VTEC could be isolated from 25 verotoxin-positive samples, all non-O157. In several samples more than one VTEC serotype was identified.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The prevalence of isolated VTEC from calves but also from other cattle remained high compared to 2008 at 30%, but we hypothesize that this is due to a higher sensitivity of the new ELISA, the sampling material (rectum-anal swabs) and the improvement in the VTEC isolation techniques especially the use of the enterohemolysin-agar.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

The relevance of findings of VTEC in feces seems to be low because VTEC are found only in a very low prevalence on meat samples from bovines.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

B. Verotoxigenic E. coli (VTEC) in animal - Sheep

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Monitoring program on the prevalence of VTEC in sheep at farm:

The monitoring in 2009 was directed towards sheep at farms. 90 sheep (out of 90 different farms) had to be tested, calculated on a population of sheep of 350,000 in Austria in 2008. The sampling had been stratified on the number and size of sheep holdings in Austrian provinces.

Frequency of the sampling

Animals at farm:

The sampling was done after blood sampling in course of the Brucella melitensis control program.

Type of specimen taken

Animals at farm:

From one sheep a mucosa swab of the recto-anal area (1) and fleece from the basis of an ear (2)

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Animals at farm:

The swab was sent in transport medium cooled down to 4 °C and the fleece in a separate plastic bag in a hobbox or polystyrene box after adding cooling units to the AGES Institute of Veterinary Diseases Control (IVET) in Graz. In the laboratory, the swab and fleece were inoculated into separate broths.

Case definition

Animals at farm

An animal is considered to be infected with VTEC following the isolation of VTEC (verotoxin producing E. coli irrespective of intimin) from one of the samples tested.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Animals at farm

In a first step the samples were screened for presence of verotoxins by ELISA, secondly the positive samples were processed for VTEC isolation, see chapter above.

The serotyping was carried out by the National Reference Laboratory for VTEC in the AGES Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED) in Graz.

Statistical analysis was performed with EpiInfo version 3.5.1.

Vaccination policy

No vaccination

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

No measures

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Harmonization of methods with regard to all possible VTEC serotypes.

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

No measures foreseen

Notification system in place

No notification

Results of the investigation

Verotoxin was detected in 70 of 88 swab samples and 27 of 81 fleece samples. VTEC could be isolated from 62 verotoxin-positive swab samples but only 2 verotoxin-positive fleece samples, all non-O157. In several samples more than one VTEC serotype was identified.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The prevalence of isolated VTEC from sheep increased to more than 70% (26% in 2008), but we hypothesize that this is due to a higher sensitivity of the new ELISA, the sampling material (rectum-anal swabs) and the improvement in the VTEC isolation techniques especially the use of the enterohemolysin-agar.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

The relevance of findings of VTEC in/on sheep seems to be low because sheep meat is consumed well-done.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Table 61 Verocytotoxic Escherchia coli in animals

animal species	sampling unit	Units tested	Total units positive	Units positive for VTEC O157	VTEC O100:H8	VTEC O103:H2	VTEC O103:H-	VTEC O104:H12	VTEC O104:H21	VTEC O112ab:H2	VTEC O113:H21	VTEC O113:H4	VTEC O113:H-	VTEC O116:H21	VTEC O116:H-	VTEC O118:H16	VTEC O125ac:H4	VTEC O128ab:H-	VTEC O128abc:H2	VTEC O128abc:HNT	VTEC O130:H11	VTEC O134:H-	VTEC O142:H16	VTEC O146:H21	VTEC O146:H-	VTEC O150:H-	VTEC O153:H25	VTEC O154:H3	VTEC O157:H-	VTEC O166:H28	VTEC O168:H5
Cattle (bovine animals) - calves (under 1 year) - at slaughterhouse - animal sample - mucosal swab (rectum-anal) - monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	animal	94	26	2	-	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	1	1	1	1	1	-	-	1	1	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	2	-	-
Cattle (bovine animals) - at slaughterhouse - animal sample - mucosal swab (rectum-anal) - monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling (older than 1 year)	animal	78	25	-	1	-	-	1	1	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	1	1
Sheep - at farm - animal sample - mucosal swab (rectum-anal) - monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	animal	88	62	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	1	4	3	-	-	1	-	4	-
Sheep - at farm - animal sample - fleece - monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	animal	81	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	

Tuberculosis

animal species	sampling unit	Units tested	Total units positive	Units positive for VTEC O157	VTEC O168:H8	VTEC O168:HNT	VTEC O17:H18	VTEC O172:H8	VTEC O174:H12	VTEC O174:H8	VTEC O176:H4	VTEC O176:H-	VTEC O177:H11	VTEC O177:H-	VTEC O178:H19	VTEC O179:H12	VTEC O181:H49	VTEC O181:H-	VTEC O22:H8	VTEC O23:H15	VTEC O26:H-	VTEC O39:H12	VTEC O39:HNT	VTEC O5:H-	VTEC O55:H11	VTEC O55:H12	VTEC O55:H-	VTEC O70:HNT	VTEC O75:H12	VTEC O75:H8	VTEC O75:H-
Cattle (bovine animals) - calves (under 1 year) - at slaughterhouse - animal sample - mucosal swab (rectum-anal) - monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	animal	94	26	2	1	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	1	-	-	-	3	-	-	-	1	2	-	-	-	-	-
Cattle (bovine animals) - at slaughterhouse - animal sample - mucosal swab (rectum-anal) - monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling (older than 1 year)	animal	78	25	-	-	-	-	1	1	-	-	-	1	2	-	1	3	-	2	1	-	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Sheep - at farm - animal sample - mucosal swab (rectum-anal) - monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	animal	88	62	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	2	2	1	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	11	-	-	1	1	1	3	1
Sheep - at farm - animal sample - fleece - monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	animal	81	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	

Tuberculosis

animal species	sampling unit	Units tested	Total units positive	Units positive for VTEC O157	VTEC O75:HNT	VTEC O76:H19	VTEC O76:H-	VTEC O8:HNT	VTEC O84:HNT	VTEC O84:Hrough	VTEC O86:H19	VTEC O86:H28	VTEC O87:H10	VTEC O87:H16	VTEC O87:HNT	VTEC O91:H21	VTEC O91:H-	VTEC ONT:H18	VTEC ONT:H19	VTEC ONT:H21	VTEC ONT:H28	VTEC ONT:H4	VTEC ONT:H8	VTEC ONT:H-	VTEC NT	VTEC ONT:Hrough	VTEC Orough:H-	VTEC Orough:HNT	VTEC OrVTEC Ough:Hrough
Cattle (bovine animals) - calves (under 1 year) - at slaughterhouse - animal sample - mucosal swab (rectum-anal) - monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	animal	94	26	2	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	1	1	-
Cattle (bovine animals) - at slaughterhouse - animal sample - mucosal swab (rectum-anal) - monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling (older than 1 year)	animal	78	25	-	-	1	-	-	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	1	1	-	2	-	-	-	2	1	-	-	1
Sheep - at farm - animal sample - mucosal swab (rectum-anal) - monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	animal	88	62	-	1	5	3	-	-	-	1	2	2	2	1	-	6	-	2	2	-	1	2	2	1	-	2	-	-
Sheep - at farm - animal sample - fleece - monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	animal	81	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

4.5. Tuberculosis

4.5.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Human tuberculosis has steadily declined during the last decades. Commission Decision 1999/467/EC of 15 July 1999 established the officially tuberculosis-free status of bovine herds of Austria.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Bovine tuberculosis poses no public health problem in Austria. Sheep, goats and pigs are free of bovine tuberculosis. Although in spring 2008 in one slaughtered cattle infective lung tuberculosis was diagnosed caused by *M. caprae*. All cattle of that holding were culled following an intra cutan testing showing several positive reactors. Two more cattle holdings with several reagents were culled and some single reactors in contact holdings. In 21 cattle out of 14 holdings *M. caprae* was isolated in 2008. In 2009 again 6 cattle out of 3 holdings were confirmed bacteriologically. Since several years a reservoir of *M. caprae* in red deer in one Austrian region has been confirmed and cattle are exposed to the bacteria in the summertime grazing on contaminated pastures in the Alps.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

No findings of *M. bovis* in animals, although *M. caprae* was detected.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

A new national regulation has been implemented due to the finding of *M. caprae* in cattle from a certain region (Rindertuberkuloseverordnung, BGBl II 2008/322). This regulation obliges the intracutan testings (using simultaneously bovine and avium tuberculin) of all cattle and goats that are kept together with cattle in given districts due to the epidemiological situation.

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Continuation of the existing control programs

Additional information

Nil

4.5.2. Tuberculosis in humans

A. Tuberculosis due to *Mycobacterium bovis* in humans

Case definition

Definite: A case with isolation of *M. tuberculosis* complex (except *M. bovis* BCG) from any clinical specimen.

Other than definite: A case that meets the clinical criteria above but does not meet the laboratory criteria of a definite case.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

- Definite: Staining: Ziehl-Neelsen, Auramin-Rhodamin stains are performed on histological preparation and smears of the sample material

- Culture: After decontamination of the homogenised sample material in NALC-NaOH and centrifugation, the sample material is transferred in parallel on Loewenstein-Jensen agar containing glycerol and PACT and Stonebrink agar containing PACT and MGITmedium. The media are incubated at 37 °C for up to 8 weeks. Confirmation of the species by Amplicor (Roche)
- Other than definite: A skin test and an X-Ray of the thorax are performed.

Notification system in place

The person who diagnoses (laboratory/hospital/general practitioner) has to notify definite (*M. tuberculosis* and *M. bovis*) and other than definite cases (this excludes radiologists) to the local health authority (Federal Law BGBl. 127/1968: Tuberkulosegesetz, as amended; Epidemiegesetz 1950, as amended). *M. bovis* is notifiable since 2004 (National Regulation BGBl. Nr. 254/2004: Anzeigepflichtige übertragbare Krankheiten 2004).

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

The National Reference Laboratory for Tuberculosis (NRL-T) has been nominated since 1995. Since 1998 all data are compiled in a national database.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Preliminary *M. bovis* was isolated from three cases; although *M. caprae* was not found in humans.

Relevance as zoonotic disease

The relevance is inconsiderable; in 2009 only three out of preliminary 733 human tuberculosis cases were caused by *M. bovis*.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Annual report of the National Reference Center from 2007 (2008 not available yet):

http://www.bmgfi.gv.at/cms/site/attachments/8/1/9/CH0954/CMS1253785411621/tb_ib_2008.pdf

Data Source of Tables 61 and 62: national reference centre for tuberculosis, preliminary data (by 15.05.2010)

Table 62 Tuberculosis in humans - species/serotype distribution

	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population	Autochtone cases	Imported cases
Tuberculosis	733	8.8	unknown	unknown
<i>M. bovis</i>	3	< 1	unknown	unknown
<i>M. tuberculosis</i>	126	1.5	unknown	unknown
<i>M. caprae</i>	0	0.0	unknown	unknown
<i>M. africanum</i>	4	0.0	unknown	unknown
<i>M. tuberculosis</i> Complex	276	3.3	unknown	unknown
Unknown	324	3.9	unknown	unknown

Table 63 Tuberculosis in humans - age distribution

Age group	Tuberculosis due to <i>M. bovis</i>			<i>M. tuberculosis</i>			<i>M. africanum</i>			<i>M. tuberculosis</i> Complex			Unknown		
	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F
< 1 year	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
1 to 4 years	-	-	-	2		2	-	-	-	2	1	1	2	1	1
5 to 14 years	-	-	-	3	1	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	9	3	6
15 to 24 years	-	-	-	12	5	7	1	1	-	29	16	12	34	14	20
25 to 44 years	1	1	-	32	16	16	1	-	1	101	68	33	89	52	36
45 to 64 years	1	-	1	42	33	9	-	-	-	74	51	22	104	74	29
65 years and older	1	-	1	35	22	13	2	1	1	70	43	27	86	58	28
Age unknown	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
All age groups	3	1	2	126	77	49	4	2	2	276	179	95	324	202	120

4.5.3. Mycobacterium spp. in animals

A. Mycobacterium bovis in bovine animals

Status as officially free of bovine tuberculosis during the reporting year

The entire country free: Yes

Additional information

According to Council Directive 64/432/EWG from June 26, 1964, Austria has the status Officially Tuberculosis Free Member State declared in the Commission Decision 1999/467/EC from July 15th, 1999, replaced by Commission Decision 2003/467/EC from June 23rd, 2003. The national surveillance programme is regulated Decree GZ 39.624/24-IX/A/8/2000. The monitoring programme is based on the compulsory ante-mortem and post-mortem inspection in which all cattle and goats originating from an official tuberculosis free holding have to be tested for tuberculous alterations.

A new national Regulation has been implemented due to the finding of *M. caprae* in cattle from a certain region (Rindertuberkuloseverordnung, BGBl II 322/2008). This Regulation includes provisions which apply for all Mycobacteria belonging to the Mycobacterium tuberculosis complex; therefore also a compulsory notification exists.

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Specimens are taken from carcasses with macroscopically observable alterations, characteristic for tuberculosis. They are sampled in slaughterhouses and sent to the national reference laboratory for tuberculosis in animals.

All cattle in holdings of designated regions given in annex 2 of the Rindertuberkuloseverordnung (BGBl II 2008/322) were subjected to simultaneous intracutan testing.

Frequency of the sampling

Continuous post-mortem inspections of each slaughtered bovine and caprine animal.

Intracutan testing: All cattle in holdings of designated regions given in annex 2 of the Rindertuberkuloseverordnung (BGBl II 322/2008).

Type of specimen taken

Organs/tissues: Tissues that are macroscopically altered due to tuberculosis, inclusive lymph nodes (according to Annex 4 of the Rindertuberkuloseverordnung, BGBl II 322/2008).

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

The alterations and lymph nodes are excised and sent to the national reference laboratory for tuberculosis in animals.

Case definition

According to Order "Richtlinien für die veterinärbehördliche Überwachung zur Erhaltung der Freiheit der österreichischen Rinderbestände von Rindertuberkulose" und zur "Durchführung und Beurteilung der intrakutanen Tuberkulinprobe" (GZ 39.624/24-IX/A/8/2000): Tubercles pathogenomically for tuberculosis detected in course of the post-mortem inspection or Mycobacterium bovis or Mycobacterium tuberculosis isolated from suspected material.

Results of the intracutan test: Doubtful and positive reactions are defined (see Rindertuberkuloseverordnung, BGBl II 2008/322).

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Intracutan testing (simultaneous testing using bovine and avium tuberculin): The test is performed according to Council Directive 64/432/EEC of 26 June 1964, as amended and the national Rindertuberkuloseverordnung (BGBl II 322/2008).

Staining: Ziehl-Neelsen stains are performed on histological preparation and smears of the sample material.

Culture: After decontamination of the homogenised sample material in NALC and centrifugation, the sample material is transferred in parallel on Loewenstein-Jensen agar containing glycerol and PACT and Stonebrink agar containing PACT and Middlebrook medium. The media are incubated at 37 °C for up to 8 weeks.

Confirmation of the Mycobacterium species by PCR (De los Monteros et al. 1998: Journal of Clinical Microbiology 36: 239-242) in the National Reference Laboratory for Tuberculosis in Animals.

Vaccination policy

Due to the importance of the intracutan tests for diagnostic purposes, vaccinations are prohibited.

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Compulsory ante-mortem and post-mortem inspection of all slaughtered bovine and caprine carcasses originating from official tuberculosis free holding and intracutan tests in animals of given regions according to Rindertuberkuloseverordnung.

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

The control programs are based on the compulsory ante-mortem and post-mortem inspection of all slaughtered bovine and caprine carcasses originating from an official tuberculosis free holding.

Intracutan tests are performed in animals in holdings of given regions according to the epidemiological situation, defined in the Rindertuberkuloseverordnung.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

A new national Regulation has been implemented due to the finding of *M. caprae* in cattle from a certain region (Rindertuberkuloseverordnung, BGBl II 322/2008). This Regulation includes provisions which apply for all Mycobacteria belonging to the Mycobacterium tuberculosis complex; therefore also a compulsory notification exists.

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

The carcass is condemned.

Loss of the status OTF for the holding from which the animal was originated and for contact holdings. It is prohibited to bring bovines and goats in and out of the holding. Slaughtering of cows and goats can only be allowed by the official veterinarian and has to be performed using a special testing and slaughtering frame. Epidemiological investigations have to be done.

Prohibition of keeping these animals together with animals from OTF-holdings on pastures or market places etc.

Regaining the status OTF:

There must be no animals in the holding showing signs of clinical tuberculosis

All animals are recruited from an OTF-holding

Animals have to be tested according to the Rindertuberkuloseverordnung (BGBl II 322/2008).

No reactors are identified after two intradermal testings of all animals in the holding older than 6 months examined earliest 60 days (first tuberculin test) and earliest 4 months (second tuberculin test) but latest 12 months after elimination of the last reactor.

Notification system in place

A suspected case of tuberculosis must be notified.

Results of the investigation

No findings of *M. bovis* in cattle.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

No findings of *M. bovis* in cattle. Due to the fact that *M. caprae* is endemic in wildlife deer in Western parts of Austria (and South-Western parts of Germany), cattle in this areas should be observed with higher sensitivity. The National Regulation concerning Bovine Tuberculosis has been revised and set into force on 1. September 2008 (Rindertuberkuloseverordnung, BGBl II 2008/322).

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

M. caprae is differentiated in Austria.

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

B. *Mycobacterium bovis* in farmed deer

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Due to the identification of *M. caprae* in several cattle holdings new control programmes have been developed to be implemented in 2009.

Frequency of the sampling

Every shot farmed deer that is foreseen to be used as a food is subjected to pre and post mortem inspection. Pre mortem inspection can be performed by the livestock owner if the owner is trained in this

special inspection and if the Veterinarian has assured himself of the physical health of the animal within the last month prior to slaughtering.

Type of specimen taken

Other: Macroscopically tuberculous alterations and lymph nodes

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

The alterations and lymph nodes are excised and sent to the national reference laboratory for tuberculosis in animals.

Case definition

Tubercles pathognomically for tuberculosis detected in course of the post-mortem inspection or *Mycobacterium bovis* or *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* isolated from suspected material

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Staining: Ziehl-Neelsen stain is performed on histological preparation and smears of the sample material

Culture: After decontamination of the homogenised sample material in NALC and centrifugation, the sample material is transferred in parallel on Loewenstein-Jensen agar containing glycerol and PACT and Stonebrink agar containing PACT and Middlebrook medium. The media are incubated at 37 °C up to 8 weeks.

Confirmation of the *Mycobacterium* species by PCR (De los Monteros et al. 1998: Journal of Clinical Microbiology 36: 239-242) in the National Reference Laboratory for Tuberculosis in Animals

Vaccination policy

Vaccination is prohibited.

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Nil

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

The control programs are based on the compulsory ante-mortem and post-mortem inspection of all slaughtered carcasses originating from an official tuberculosis free holding

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

A new national Regulation has been implemented due to the finding of *M. caprae* in cattle from a certain region (Rindertuberkuloseverordnung, BGBl II 322/2008). This Regulation includes provisions which apply for all *Mycobacteria* belonging to the *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex; therefore also a compulsory notification exists.

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

The carcass is condemned. Further measures according to Tierseuchengesetz RGrBl. 1909/177 as amended.

Notification system in place

The suspicion and finding of tuberculosis is notifiable.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

No cases of *M. bovis* in 2009.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

No cases of *M. bovis* in 2009.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

C. *Mycobacterium* spp. in animal - all animals - at slaughter – Control programme - mandatory - official sampling (all slaughtered animals except those mentioned above)

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Samples from suspected swine are taken in slaughterhouses. Sampling is performed when tissue of slaughtered animals is visibly altered, seen by the unaided eye.

Goats in defined regions that are kept together with cattle are subjected to intracutan testing (see chapter *Mycobacterium bovis* bovine animals; Rindertuberkuloseverordnung, BgBl II 2008/322).

Frequency of the sampling

Continuous post-mortem inspections of each slaughtered animal

Type of specimen taken

Other: Macroscopic tuberculous alterations and lymphnodes

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

The altered tissue and lymph nodes are excised and sent to the laboratory

Case definition

Tubercles pathognomically for tuberculosis detected in course of the post-mortem inspection or *Mycobacterium bovis* or *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* or *Mycobacterium avium* isolated from suspected material

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Staining: Ziehl-Neelsen stains are performed on histological preparation and smears of the sample material

Culture: After decontamination of the homogenised sample material in NALC and centrifugation, the sample material is transferred in parallel on Loewenstein-Jensen agar containing glycerol and PACT and Stonebrink agar containing PACT and Middlebrook medium. The media are incubated at 37°C up to 8 weeks.

Confirmation of the *Mycobacterium* species by PCR (De los Monteros et al. 1998: Journal of Clinical Microbiology 36: 239-242) in the National Reference Laboratory for Tuberculosis in Animals

Vaccination policy

Vaccination is prohibited.

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

See other chapters.

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

The control programs are based on the compulsory ante-mortem and post-mortem inspection of all slaughtered carcasses originating from an official tuberculosis free holding

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

No need at the moment

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

The carcass is condemned. Further measures are performed according to Tierseuchengesetz RGBI. 1909/177, as amended.

Notification system in place

The detection of tuberculosis is notifiable.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

No cases in Austria in 2009.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

No cases in Austria in 2009.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Table 64 Bovine tuberculosis in countries and regions that do not receive Community co-financing for eradication programme

Member State: Austria..... Date of the report: 10.05.2010..... Year: 2009.....											
The official post-mortem examination for all slaughtered bovine animals is implemented: Yes											
Region (1)	Total number of existing bovine		Officially free herds		Infected herds * all M. capra		Routine tuberculin testing		Number of tuberculin tests carried out before the introduction into the herds (Annex A(1)(2)(c) third indent (1) of Directive 64/432/EEC)	Number of animals with suspicious lesions of tuberculosis examined and submitted to histopathological and bacteriological examinations	Number of animals detected positive in bacteriological examination *all M. caprae
	Herds	Animals	Number of herds	%	Number of herds	%	Interval between routine tuberculin tests (2)	Number of animals tested			
Austria	73990	2019759	73987	99.986	3	0.004	a)	38796	280	70	6*
Total	73990	2019759	73987	99.986	3	0.004	a)	38796	280	70	6*

* all "M. caprae": Same measures for control and eradication as for M. bovis

Source of information: Central Veterinary Services

(1) Detailed regional information is required, unless the officially free status has been granted to the whole territory of the Member State.

(2) Use the following letter codes: (a) no routine tests; (b) tests once a year; (c) tests every two years; (d) tests every three years concerning 24 month-old animals; (f) tests every 4 years; (g) others (please give details).

Table 65 Tuberculosis in other animals

Animal species	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Sampling Details	Source of information	Sampling unit	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Mycobacteriaspp.</i>
Sheep	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programme - official sampling - census sampling	compulsory ante- mortem and post- mortem inspection	CVS	animal	290,088	0
Goats	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programme - official sampling - census sampling	compulsory ante- mortem and post- mortem inspection	CVS	animal	41,276	0
Pigs	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programme - official sampling - census sampling	compulsory ante- mortem and post- mortem inspection	CVS	animal	5,597,387	0

CVS: Central Veterinary Service

4.6. Brucellosis

4.6.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

In Austria, human brucellosis cases are considered to be an imported infectious disease. The Austrian cattle, sheep and goat population bears the status Officially Brucellosis Free (OBF) and Officially Brucella melitensis free (OBmF).

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Two human cases were identified in 2009; both cases were imported.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

No findings in Austria, OBF and OBmF

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

A new national regulation has been implemented concerning the examination of milk- and bloodsamples in cattle (Bangseuchen-Untersuchungsverordnung 2008, BGBl II 2007/305).

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Continuation of the existing control programs

Additional information

Nil

4.6.2. Brucellosis in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

Notification of cases according to EU case definitions.

Case definition

Clinical description: Clinical picture compatible with brucellosis, e.g. acute or insidious onset of fever, night sweats, fatigue, anorexia, weight loss, headache and arthralgia.

Laboratory criteria for diagnosis

- Demonstration of a specific antibody response
- Isolation of Brucella spp. from a clinical specimen
- Identification and confirmation of the species by PCR.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

- Serological examination: Serum samples are tested in the Complement Fixation Test (CFT) with reference standard antisera from CVL-Weybridge. Participation in international ring trials: Brucellosis European Ring Trial 2000 and 2002 (VLA Weybridge) with ELISA, CFT, RBT and SAT.

- Bacteriological: Multiple blood samples are inoculated in blood culture broth over several consecutive days. The incubation lasted 4 to 6 weeks, once per week medium is transferred on brucella agar and incubated 5-10 % CO₂ atmosphere (Anonymus: Standardisierung und Qualitätssicherung in der mikrobiologischen Diagnostik. Richtlinien. Bundesministerium für Soziale Sicherheit und Generationen. ISBN 3-84123- 126-0, Wien, 2001, pg. 56).

- The genus is identified by microscopic examination, catalase-, oxidase- and the slide agglutination test using brucella serum. The species is identified by CO₂ requirement, H₂S formation, urease activity, growth on media containing standard concentrations of basic fuchsin or thionin and agglutination with monospecific sera and by PCR (Real-time detection of *Brucella abortus*, *Brucella melitensis* and *Brucella suis*. 2001: Redkar et al., Mol Cell Probes. 2001 Feb;15(1):43-52.)

Notification system in place

Notification of brucellosis according to the epidemic act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended):
The attending physicians and the laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Austria is OBF and OBmF. All cases reported in Austria are epidemiologically linked to travel in endemic countries or to foreign workers from endemic countries.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

This zoonosis has no relevance in Austria.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Data source of Tables 65 and 66: National Reference Laboratory for Brucellosis

Table 66 Brucellosis in humans - species/serotype distribution

	Cases	Notification rate/100.000	Autochtone cases	Imported cases	Unknown status
Brucellosis	2	<0,1	0	2	0
<i>B. abortus</i>	1	<0,0	0	1	0
<i>B. melitensis</i>	1	<0,0	0	1	0

Table 67 Brucellosis in humans - age distribution

Age group	<i>Brucellosis</i>			<i>B. abortus</i>			<i>B. melitensis</i>		
	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F
< 1 year	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0
1 to 4 years	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0
5 to 14 years	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0
15 to 24 years	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0
25 to 44 years	2	2	-	1	1	-	1	1	0
45 to 64 years	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0
65 years and older	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0
Age unknown	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0
All age groups	2	2	-	1	1	-	1	1	-

4.6.3. Brucella in foodstuffs

Due to the fact that Austria is OBF and OBmF, food is not investigated for Brucella spp.

4.6.4. Brucella spp. in animals

A. Brucella abortus in Bovine Animals

Status as officially free of bovine brucellosis during the reporting year

The entire country free: Yes

Additional information

Upon the request of the Commission Decision of July 15th 1999, CD 1999/466/EC, as amended, by the Council Directive 64/432/EEC of 26 June 1964, Austria achieved the status: officially brucellosis-free for bovine herds.

A new national regulation has been implemented concerning the examination of milk- and bloodsamples in cattle (Bangseuchen-Untersuchungsverordnung 2008, BGBl II 2007/305). This means that in the case of dairy herds, the examination of milk samples in accordance with Annex C of Council Directive 64/432/EEC of 26 June 1964 can be performed.

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Nationwide all bovine milk producing holdings were subjected to bulk milk testing.

In non-milk producing holdings a risk based sampling plan was performed.

Abortion or premature birth: Abortive material and blood of the cow is sampled

Frequency of the sampling

Bulk milk sampling: All milk producing holdings had been sampled minimum once per year according to the new regulation (§6 Bangseuchen-Untersuchungsverordnung 2008, BGBl II 2007/305). In case of not-negative bulk milk samples, blood samples in the affected holding were investigated.

Holdings without milk production: A risk based sampling plan has been calculated stratified according to the different provinces (§6 Bangseuchen-Untersuchungsverordnung 2008, BGBl II 2007/305). If blood serology does not show a definitive negative result diagnostic slaughtering of the affected animal has to be carried out.

- Abortion or premature birth: Tissue and blood from the cow is sampled immediately post abortion. If the result of the first serological examination was negative, a second blood sample was taken 2 weeks post abortion for serological testing. If this result was negative again, sampling and testing was repeated after two weeks.

Type of specimen taken

Bulk milk

Blood samples

Diagnostic slaughtering: organs and lymph nodes of the genital tract; udder and accessory lymph nodes; fetus (stomach, lungs); retropharyngeal lymph node.

Abortion or premature birth: Tissue and blood samples from the animal that had an abortion.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Bulk milk sampling: §6 Bangseuchen-Untersuchungsverordnung 2008, BGBl II 2007/305.

Holdings without milk production: According to the sampling plan individual blood samples are taken in the holdings and sent to the laboratories (§6 Bangseuchen-Untersuchungsverordnung 2008, BGBl II 2007/305).

Diagnostic slaughtering: §6 Bangseuchen-Untersuchungsverordnung 2008, BGBl II 2007/305.

Abortion or premature birth: Aborted tissue and blood samples sent to a veterinary laboratory.

Case definition

An animal is considered to be positive for *Brucella abortus*, in case of positive blood-serological test result and the epidemiological situation of the herd indicates the possibility that a brucella infection has been introduced to the herd or in case of bacteriological isolation. If a single animal reactor is detected in the holding, tracing back is an important tool to get more information about the animal.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Bulk milk: Testings according to Council Directive 64/432/EEC and the manual of Diagnostic Tests and Vaccines for Terrestrial Animals of the OIE.

Blood samples: Testings according to Council Directive 64/432/EEC and the manual of Diagnostic Tests and Vaccines for Terrestrial Animals of the OIE: Routinely single serum samples or serum pools (5 sera in one pool) were tested in the Indirect-ELISA (I-ELISA) using the three OIE ELISA Brucella Standard Sera (OIE ELISAwSS, OIE ELISAspSS, OIE ELISAnSS) and the OIE Brucella abortus Positive International Standard Antiserum (OIEISS) to calibrate the method (Commission Regulation 535/2002/EC of 21 March 2002 amending Annex C to Council Directive 64/432/EEC and amending Decision 2000/330/EC). Following a positive or suspected test result in the IELISA single serum samples were also tested in the Complement Fixation Test (CFT), Rose Bengal test (RBT) and Competitive ELISA (C-ELISA). Participation in international ring trials:

Participation in international ring trials (Weybridge, AFSSA and other) with ELISA, CFT, RBT and Serum Agglutination Test (SAT). The National Reference Laboratory for Brucellosis, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control in Moedling organized the national Brucellosis Ring Trials for all Veterinary Institutes.

Abortion or premature birth: Aborted material was tested bacteriologically and serologically as described above. Bacteriology: Smears of the samples are stained by Stableforth's method. Brucella agar and Columbia agar (Merck) containing selective additives were used (Oxoid). After inoculation the media were incubated for 4-10 days at 37°C in an atmosphere containing 10% CO₂. The genus was identified by microscopic examination, catalase-, oxidase- and the slide agglutination test using brucella serum. The species was differentiated by CO₂ requirement, H₂S formation, urease activity, growth on media containing standard concentrations of basic fuchsin or thionin and agglutination with monospecific sera and by PCR (Real-time detection of *Brucella abortus*, *Brucella melitensis* and *Brucella suis*. 2001: Redkar et al., Mol Cell Probes. 2001 Feb;15(1):43-52.).

Vaccination policy

Vaccination is not allowed (BGBl. 1957/147, Bangseuchengesetz, § 13 Impfung)

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Control programme according to the National Regulation (Bangseuchen-Untersuchungsverordnung 2008, BGBl II 2007/305). Abortion or premature birth: Compulsory notification according BGBl 1957/147, Bangseuchengesetz, as amended, §11 Anzeigepflicht;

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

No actions, because OBF

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

According to BGBl 1957/147, Bangseuchengesetz, as amended, and BGBl 1909/177, Tierseuchengesetz, as amended

Notification system in place

Abortion or premature birth: Notification of abortions: The livestock owner has to notify each abortion within 24 hours to the mayor (Gemeinde). The mayor has to forward the notification to the local authority (Bezirksverwaltungsbehörde) (BGBl. 1957/147, Bangseuchengesetz, § 11 Anzeigepflicht). If the cow is being treated by a veterinarian or the veterinarian has been informed about the abortion, then the veterinarian has to notify to the official authority (Bezirksverwaltungsbehörde).

Results of the investigation

See tables

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

OBF

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

B. *Brucella melitensis* in Sheep and Goats

Status as officially free of ovine brucellosis during the reporting year

The entire country free: Yes

Additional information

According to Commission Decision Nr. 93/52/EWG, as amended, Austria has the status officially brucellosis (*B. melitensis*) free (ObmF).

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

To maintain the status officially brucellosis (*B. melitensis*) free, according to BGBl. 2002/184 (Brucella melitensis-Überwachungsverordnung, of 14 May 2002) a representative number of samples were examined with a confidence level of 95 % to detect infected holdings at a target prevalence of 0.2 %. Sampling was performed by the competent authority or under its supervision, by bodies to which it had delegated this responsibility. Samples were taken in the holdings. Aborted material and blood samples from the animal were also investigated.

Frequency of the sampling

Principally the sampling was performed during the cold season, between November and May when the animals were kept in the stables.

Type of specimen taken

- Monitoring: Blood samples according to a sampling plan.
- Clinical cases: Aborted material and blood samples from the affected animal.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Individual blood samples and aborted material are taken within the holdings and sent to the laboratories.

Case definition

An animal is considered to be infected with *B. melitensis* in case of bacteriological isolation or positive serological test result.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

- Routinely single serum samples were tested in the Indirect ELISA. Confirmation of suspected or positive results was performed by the Complement Fixation Test (CFT) with reference standard antisera from CVL-Weybridge. Participation in international ring trials on Brucellosis (Weybridge and other) with ELISA, CFT, RBT and SAT. The National Reference Laboratory for Brucellosis, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control in Moedling organized the national Brucellosis Ring Trials for all national Veterinary Institutes.

Bacteriology: Smears of the samples were stained by Stableforth's method.

Brucella agar and Columbia agar (Merck) containing selective additives (Oxoid) were used. After inoculation the media are incubated for 4 - 10 days at 37 °C in an atmosphere containing 10 % CO₂. The genus was identified by microscopic examination, catalase-, oxidase- and the slide agglutination test using brucella serum. The species were differentiated by CO₂ requirement, H₂S formation, urease activity, growth on media containing standard concentrations of basic fuchsin or thionin and agglutination with monospecific sera and by PCR (Real-time detection of *Brucella abortus*, *Brucella melitensis* and *Brucella suis*. 2001: Redkar et al., Mol Cell Probes. 2001 Feb;15(1):43-52.).

Vaccination policy

According to BGBl. 2002/184 (*Brucella melitensis*-Überwachungsverordnung, of 14 May 2002, §4, Impfverbot) vaccination is not allowed.

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Monitoring program and investigation of abortions

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

To maintain the status officially brucellosis (*B. melitensis*) free, according to BGBl. 2002/184 (*Brucella melitensis*-Überwachungsverordnung, of 14 May 2002) a representative number of samples have to be examined with a confidence level of 95 % to detect infected holdings at a prevalence of 0.2 %. Sampling is performed by the appropriate authority or under its supervision, by bodies to which it has delegated this responsibility. Samples are taken in the holdings.

Notification and clarification of each clinical case by bacteriology and serology.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

ObmF

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

According to BGBl. 2002/184 (*Brucella melitensis*-Überwachungsverordnung, of 14 May 2002, §3, Ausmerzung von Reagenten) reactors have to be culled, the carcasses have to be incinerated in an incineration plant.

Notification system in place

Notification of brucellosis or a suspicion of brucellosis according to BGBl. 2002/184 (Brucella melitensis-Überwachungsverordnung, of 14 May 2002).

Results of the investigation

See tables

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

ObmF

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

D. Brucella suis in animal – Pigs

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

According to Guideline 64/432/EEC as amended.

Frequency of the sampling

Targeted, following abortion and in positive cases contact holdings.

Type of specimen taken

- Monitoring: Blood samples;
- Clinical cases: Abortion material and blood samples from the affected animal; tissues: according to decree 74700/0132-IV/B/5/2008

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Individual blood samples and abortion material are taken from animals in the holdings and sent to the laboratories.

Case definition

An animal is considered to be serologically positive for brucellosis following one/more positive CFT Complement Fixation Test (CFT) and RBT Rose Bengal test (RBT) results (B. abortus used antigen). A bacteriological isolation may also be possible as in the case of B. suis.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

- Due to the fact that a Brucella suis antigen is not available, the B. abortus antigen is used for the Complement Fixation Test (CFT) and the Rose Bengal test (RBT) because B. abortus shows cross reactions with B. suis antibodies.
- ELISA and CFT is not available, the B. abortus ELISA and CFT are used because these tests show cross reactions with B. suis antibodies.
- Participation in international ring trials: Brucellosis European Ring Trial 2000 and 2002 (VLA Weybridge) with ELISA, CFT, RBT and Serum Agglutination Test (SAT). The National Reference Laboratory for

Brucellosis, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control in Moedling organized the national Brucellosis Ring Trials for all Veterinary Institutes.

Bacteriology: Quality control: Laboratory strains

- Smears of the samples are stained by Stableforth's method

- Brucella agar and Columbia agar (Merck) containing selective additives (Oxoid) were used. After inoculation the media are incubated for 4-10 days at 37 °C in an atmosphere containing 10 % CO₂. The genus was identified by microscopic examination, catalase-, oxidase- and the slide agglutination test using brucella serum. The species were differentiated by CO₂ requirement, H₂S formation, urease activity, growth on media containing standard concentrations of basic fuchsin or thionin and agglutination with monospecific sera and by PCR (Real-time detection of *Brucella abortus*, *Brucella melitensis* and *Brucella suis*. 2001: Redkar et al., Mol Cell Probes. 2001 Feb;15(1):43-52.).

Vaccination policy

Nil

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Nil

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Nil

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

No mandatory measures but notification is required.

Notification system in place

B. suis has been a notifiable disease since 1993 according to BGBl 1993/756, Tierseuchen-Anzeigepflichtverordnung, as amended.

Results of the investigation

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Due to the results of the passive monitoring in pigs (no cases of B. suis) we conclude that there is no need for an active monitoring program.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Table 68 Bovine Brucellosis data from countries and regions that do not receive Community co-financing (non co-financed)

Member State: Austria Date of report: 10.05.2010..... Year: 2009.....																					
Region (1)	Total number of existing bovine		Officially free herds		Infected herds		Surveillance (2)						Investigations of suspect cases								
			Number of herds	%	Number of herds	%	Serological tests			Examination of bulk milk samples			Information on abortions			Epidemiological investigation					
	Herds	Animals					Number of bovine herds tested	Number of animals tested	Number of infected herds	Number of bovine herds tested	Number of animals or pools tested	Number of infected herds	Number of notified abortions whatever cause	Number of isolations of <i>Brucella</i> infections	Number of abortions due to <i>Brucella abortus</i>	Number of animals tested with serological blood tests	Number of suspended herds	Number of positive animals		Number of animals examined microbologically	Number of animals positive microbologically
																	Serologically	BST			
Austria	73990	2019759	73990	100	0	0	3529	27685	0	36275	36297	0	1366	0	0	1112	36	0	0	3	0
Total	73990	2019759	73990	100	0	0	3529	27685	0	36275	36297	0	1366	0	0	1112	36	0	0	3	0

Source of information: Central Veterinary Services

(1) Detailed regional information is required, unless the officially free status has been granted to the whole territory of the Member State.

(2) Please give details.

Table 69 Ovine and caprine brucellosis - data from countries that do not receive co-financing for control or eradication programme

Member State: Austria..... Date of report: 05.05.2010..... Year: 2009.....														
Region (1)	Total number of existing ovine/caprine		Officially free herds		Infected herds		Surveillance (2)			Investigations of suspect cases				
	Herds	Animals	Number of herds	%	Number of herds	%	Number of herds tested	Number of animals tested	Number of infected herds	Number of animals tested with serological blood tests	Number of animals positive serologically	Number of animals examined microbiologically	Number of animals positive microbiologically	Number of suspended herds
Austria	32460	468677	32460	100	0	0	1618	13065	0	4	0	0	0	3
Total	32460	468677	32460	100	0	0	1618	13065	0	4	0	0	0	3

Source of information: Central Veterinary Services, Provincial Veterinary Services

(1) Detailed regional information is required, unless the officially free status has been granted to the whole territory of the Member State.

(2) Please give details.

4.7. Yersiniosis

4.7.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Yersiniosis is not considered a major food borne illness in Austria. The incidence of human disease is low when compared to salmonellosis or campylobacteriosis.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2009, a total of 148 human infections were reported as aggregated notified cases on a monthly basis. 113 primary isolates from patients were sent to the National Reference Laboratory for Yersinia. The sources of infections are unclear. Neither studies on sporadic cases nor scientific outbreak investigations were performed in Austria so far.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

None

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Additional information

Nil

4.7.2. Yersiniosis in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

Notification of cases according to EU case definitions. The numbers presented in this report reflect the number of primary isolates sent to the national reference lab for confirmation and typing.

Case definition

Clinical description: An illness of variable severity characterised by diarrhoea, fever, nausea, cramps and tenesmus.

Laboratory criteria for diagnosis: Isolation of Yersinia enterocolitica Serogroup O:3, O:9 or O:5 or Y. pseudotuberculosis from a clinical specimen.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Faecal (Yersinia enterocolitica) or resection (Y. pseudotuberculosis) sample material is plated directly on cefsulodin-irgasan-novobiocin (CIN) agar and incubated for 18 hours at 30 °C. Suspicious colonies are identified in an Api 20 E reaction and API 50 CHE reaction. Y. enterocolitica is agglutinated with sera against serogroups O:3, O:5, O:9 and O:8. Biovar and pathogenicity are defined.

Notification system in place

Notification of yersiniosis according to the epidemic act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): The attending physicians and the laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Yersiniosis is the third most bacterial food borne pathogen in Austria although compared to salmonellosis and campylobacteriosis, the number of notified cases are much lower.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The number of human cases has been similar in the last years.

Relevance as zoonotic disease

Yersiniosis is the third most bacterial food borne pathogen in Austria although compared to salmonellosis and campylobacteriosis, the number of notified cases are much lower.

Data source of Tables 69 to 71: Primary isolates from patients typed in the national reference centre for yersiniosis

Table 70 Yersiniosis in human - species/serotype distribution

	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population	Autochtone cases	Imported cases	Unknown status
Yersiniosis	113	1.4			113
<i>Y. enterocolitica</i>	110	1.3			110
<i>Y. enterocolitica</i> O:3	94	1.1			94
<i>Y. enterocolitica</i> O:9	15	0.2			15
<i>Y. pseudotuberculosis</i>	3	0.0			3

Table 71 Yersiniosis in humans - age distribution

Age group	Yersiniosis			<i>Y. enterocolitica</i>			<i>Y. pseudotuberculosis</i>			<i>Y. ent. O:3 bv 4</i>		
	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F
< 1 year	5	2	2	5	2	3	-	-	-	4	2	2
1 to 4 years	28	17	17	28	17	11	-	-	-	24	14	10
5 to 14 years	21	11	11	19	11	8	-	-	2	19	11	8
15 to 24 years	18	13	13	18	13	5	-	-	-	18	13	5
25 to 44 years	23	10	10	22	10	11	-	-	1	16	7	8
45 to 64 years	11	7	7	11	7	4	-	-	-	6	4	2
65 years and older	7	4	4	7	4	3	-	-	-	6	3	3
Age unknown	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0
All age groups	113	64	64	11-	64	45	-	-	3	93	54	38

Table 72 Yersiniosis in humans - seasonal distribution

	Yersiniosis	<i>Y. enterocolitica</i>	<i>Y. pseudotuberculosis</i>	<i>Y. ent. O:3 bv 4</i>
Month	Cases	Cases	Cases	Cases
January	11	11	-	10
February	10	9	1	8
March	6	6	-	4
April	7	7	-	7
May	7	7	-	4
June	6	5	1	4
July	7	7	-	7
August	8	8	-	7
September	15	14	1	11
October	13	13	-	13
November	14	14	-	10
December	9	9	-	8
not known	-	-	-	-
Total	113	110	3	93

4.7.3. Yersinia in foodstuffs

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Foodstuff was sampled according to the ordinance „Revisions- und Probenplan für das Jahr 2008 gemäß §31 LMSVG; Richtlinien über die Vollziehung der Überwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Berichtsschema 2008“ (BMGFJ – 75500/0332-IV/B/7/2008) from the Federal Ministry of Health. This “Revisions- und Probenplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2007-2010) according to Art. 41 ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004.

The Revision-Plan determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be sampled and tested randomly according to the number of food enterprises per province. Every business within Austria has to be sampled at least once per year. The inspection can comprise sampling, hygienic investigations of the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes etc.

In 2009, approximately 40,000 samples were planned to be tested in Austria. About 60% (24,000) of these are planned samples (surveillance) and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). These planned samples either consist of samples of the yearly sampling plan which determines the number of samples of each food category that have to be investigated randomly, e.g. raw meat (fresh or frozen); sausages; cheeses; milk; preserved food etc. There are different sampling stages where food samples are taken: e.g. from retail, processing plant, primary production.

In addition there is a monitoring plan for food items (40-45 campaigns per year). In the course of these programs food items of special interest for defined parameters – amongst others zoonotic agents – are investigated. The sampling takes place during a fixed period of time in order to gain in-dept information. In 2009, seven relevant food campaign programs were conducted throughout Austria (Schwerpunktprogramm 2009 BMGFJ-75500/0242-IV/B/7/2008). Details and results of these campaigns can be found in the respective chapters.

Results of the investigation

Table 73 Yersiniosis in food

Food	Sampling Stage	Sample weight	Units tested	Total units positive for Yersinia spp.
Other food	at catering	25g	1	0

4.7.4. Yersinia spp. in animals

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Not relevant in Austria therefore no testing.

Vaccination policy

No vaccination.

Other preventative measures than vaccination in place

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

EU wide harmonized monitoring program.

Notification system in place:

Findings of Yersinia are not notifiable in animals.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

No changes in recent years.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

The relevance has not been investigated.

Additional information

Nil

4.8. Trichinellosis

4.8.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

No documented human infestations since several years.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

No documented human infestations in 2009.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

One documented infestations in a food-animal (wild boar) since several years in 2009.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

No new measures implemented

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Reconsider the necessity of routine trichinella meat inspection in pig carcasses

Additional information

Nil

4.8.2. Trichinellosis in humans

No cases identified in 2009.

Case definition

Clinical description: A disease caused by ingestion of Trichinella larvae. The disease has variable clinical manifestations. Common signs and symptoms include eosinophilia, fever, myalgia, and periorbital edema. Laboratory criteria for diagnosis: Demonstration of Trichinella larvae in tissue obtained by muscle biopsy, or positive serologic test for Trichinella

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

ELISA and Westernblot

Notification system in place

Notification of trichionellosis according to the epidemic act since 1950 (BGBI. 1950/186 Epidemiegesetz, as amended).

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

The last autochthonous cases have been reported in 1970

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Nil

Relevance as zoonotic disease

No relevance in Austria

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Data source of Table 73: national reference laboratory for toxoplasmosis, echinococcosis, toxocarosis and other parasitic diseases

Table 74 Trichinellosis in human - species/serotype distribution

	Cases	Incidence per 100.000
Trichinellosis	0	0

4.8.3. Trichinella in animals

A. *Trichinella* spp. in pigs

Number of officially recognised *Trichinella*-free holdings

Categories of holdings officially recognised *Trichinella*-free

Officially recognised regions with negligible *Trichinella* risk

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

General

Targeted sampling of all slaughtered pigs except pigs slaughtered by the farmer for his own consumption; the sampling is performed by competent authorities; the samples are taken at slaughterhouses; the sampling is part of a permanent monitoring scheme.

Frequency of the sampling

General

Other: Permanent post-mortem sampling of each slaughtered pig

Type of specimen taken

General

Muscles: Diaphragm (crus), tongue, masseter and abdominal muscles.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

General

Appropriate muscle is excised out of the carcass.

Case definition

General

When trichinosis is detected with one of the given methods

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

According to Regulation (EC) Nr. 2075/2005

Vaccination policy

Nil

Preventive measures in place

Nil

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Lebensmittelsicherheits- und Verbraucherschutzgesetz (LMSVG, BGBl. I 2006/13, as amended),
Fleischuntersuchungsverordnung (BGBl II 2006/109 as amended)

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

According to Regulation (EC) Nr. 854/2004, as amended.

The contingency plan in place

Notification system in place

Results of the investigation including description of the positive cases and the verification of the Trichinella species

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

B. Trichinella spp. in horses

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Targeted sampling of all slaughtered horses; the sampling is performed by competent authorities; the samples are taken at slaughterhouses; the sampling is part of a permanent monitoring scheme

Frequency of the sampling

Permanent post-mortem sampling of each slaughtered horse

Type of specimen taken

Muscles from tongue, masseter, diaphragm and neck.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Appropriate muscle is excised out of the carcass.

Case definition

When trichinosis is detected with one of the given methods.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

According to Regulation (EC) Nr. 2075/2005

Vaccination policy

Nil

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Nil

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Lebensmittelsicherheits- und Verbraucherschutzgesetz (LMSVG, BGBl. I 2006/13, as amended),
Fleischuntersuchungsverordnung (BGBl II 2006/109 as amended)

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

According to Regulation (EC) Nr. 854/2004 as amended.

Results of the investigation

No findings in horses.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Nil

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

C. Trichinella spp. in animal - Wildlife - wild boars

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Sampling of all hunted or harvested wild boars; the sampling is performed by hunters with special knowledge about trichinella investigation or by competent authorities; the sampling is stratified by geographical regions depending to the habitats of wild boar in Austria; samples are taken either immediately after shooting the animal or at the cold storage depots; the sampling is part of a monitoring scheme.

Frequency of the sampling

All farmed wild boars are controlled for trichinella.

Type of specimen taken

Diaphragm muscles (crus), tongue, masseter and abdominal muscles.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Appropriate muscle is excised out of the carcass.

Case definition

When trichinosis is detected with one of the given methods.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

According to Regulation (EC) Nr. 2075/2005

Vaccination policy

Nil

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Nil

Control program/mechanisms**The control program/strategies in place**

Lebensmittelsicherheits- und Verbraucherschutzgesetz (LMSVG, BGBl. I 2006/13, as amended),
Fleischuntersuchungsverordnung (BGBl II 2006/109 as amended)

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

According to Regulation (EC) Nr. 854/2004 as amended.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Since several years trichinella were found for the first time in a wild boar.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Table 75 *Trichinella* spp. in animals

Animal species	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Sampling Details	Source of information	Sampling unit	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Trichinella</i> spp.
Pigs							
fattening pigs raised under controlled housing conditions in integrated system							
fattening pigs not raised under controlled housing conditions in integrated system	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official and industry sampling - census sampling		CVS	animal	5,537,389	0
breeding animals -unspecified - sows and boars							
Domestic solipeds							
horses	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official and industry sampling - census sampling			animal	978	0
Wild boars							
Farmed	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official and industry sampling - census sampling			animal	10,347	1
wild							
Foxes							
Badger					animal	10	0
Bears							
Rodents							
Rats							

CVS: Central Veterinary Services

4.9. Echinococcosis

4.9.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Austria is a low risk country for both forms of echinococcosis.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

We expect the future prevalence to be low. In 2009, 3 cases of *Echinococcus multilocularis* infestation were diagnosed in Austria, all three autochtone case confirmed; 18 patients were diagnosed with cystic echinococcosis.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Alveolar echinococcosis: Due to the infestation rates of red foxes in Austria (0-40 %) there is a relatively elevated risk for hunters, cat owners and farmers.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Tools for preventive serological screening of hunters (and also other persons) have been established to detect *Echinococcus multilocularis* infections in an early stage. The early detection of the infection is the prerequisite for a successful curative treatment.

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Additional information

Nil

4.9.2. Echinococcosis in humans

Case definition

Clinical apparent case (differentiation between alveolar and cystic echinococcosis necessary) with laboratory diagnostic confirmation: = histopathology or combination of imaging (ultrasound, X-ray, computed tomography or others) and positive serology or combination of specific DNA (by PCR) and positive serology).

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

ELISA and Westernblot technique, participant of the UK National External Quality Assessment Service for Microbiology, National Reference Laboratory for Echinococcosis.

Notification system in place

Notification of echinococcosis according to the epidemic act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): The attending physicians and the laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

- Alveolar echinococcosis has been known in Austria since 1897; annual incidence (1897- 2004): 0-6 cases, mean incidence: 2.4 cases/year (only autochthonous cases); geographic distribution in Austria: mainly in the western provinces (Vorarlberg, Tyrol, Salzburg), but cases have been reported in every province; outbreaks are not known.

- Cystic echinococcosis has been known in Austria at least since 1819; Cases of cystic echinococcosis have been registered in the Clinical Institute of Hygiene and Medical Microbiology (Medical University Vienna) regularly since the beginning of the 1980ies. Annual incidence (1984 - 2006): 20 - 60 cases; mean incidence: 31 cases per year, one third of patients are of Austrian origin; two thirds are from abroad. Geographic distribution in Austria is unknown; a few autochthonous infections could be observed mainly in the eastern and southern provinces (Lower Austria, Burgenland, and Styria); outbreaks are not known.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

- Alveolar echinococcosis: We expect the future incidence to be low; sources of infestation: fox faeces (contaminated hands and fingers, vegetables, water).
- Cystic echinococcosis: We expect the future incidence to be low; sources of infestation: dog faeces, presumably in a very few foci (in or around farmers houses)

Relevance as zoonotic disease

Low incidence of both forms of echinococcosis

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Data source of Tables 75 and 76: national reference laboratory for toxoplasmosis, echinococcosis, toxocarosis and other parasitic diseases

Table 76 Echinococcosis in humans - species/serotype distribution

	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population	Autochtone cases	Imported cases	unknown
Echinococcosis	21	0.3			16
Cystic echinococcosis	18	0.2		2	16
Alveolar echinococcosis	3	0.0	3		0

Table 77 Echinococcosis in humans - age distribution

Age group	<i>Echinococcus</i>			<i>E. granulosus</i>			<i>E. multilocularis</i>		
	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F
< 1 year	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
1 to 4 years	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
5 to 14 years	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
15 to 24 years	2	1	1	2	1	1	-	-	-
25 to 44 years	10	2	8	9	1	8	1	1	0
45 to 64 years	8	2	6	6	1	5	2	1	1
65 years and older	1	0	1	1	0	1	-	-	-
Age unknown	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
All age groups	21	5	16	18	3	15	3	2	1

4.9.3. Echinococcus in animals

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Targeted sampling of all in abattoirs slaughtered animals; the sampling is performed by competent authorities in course of the post-mortem meat inspection; the sampling is part of a permanent monitoring scheme.

Frequency of the sampling

Permanent post-mortem sampling of each slaughtered animal

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

All organs and muscles that were used for human consumption

Case definition

Each carcass in which cystic or alveolar hydatids are detected in muscles or organs

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Other: All organs and muscles that were used for human consumption were visually inspected, palpated and cuttings were performed

Vaccination policy

No vaccination

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

No measures

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Post mortem meat inspection act according to BGBl. 1982/522, Fleischuntersuchungsgesetz, as amended

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Cystic or alveolar echinococcosis in animals that are used for food production do not play a role for the infection of humans; it is primarily a hygienic problem. Only when infected waste from animals is used as feed for carnivores the risk of infection for humans increases.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Table 78 Echinococcus sp. in animals

Animal species	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Source of information	Sampling unit	Units tested	Total units positive for Echinococcus spp.	<i>E. multilocularis</i>	<i>E. granulosus</i>	<i>Echinococcus</i> spp., unspecified
Cattle	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official sampling - census sampling	x	animal	619,617	226			
Sheep	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official sampling - census sampling	x	animal	121,547	37			
Goats	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official sampling - census sampling	x	animal	4,967	0			
Pigs	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official sampling - census sampling	x	animal	5,537,389	0			

x ... Central Veterinary Services, Provincial Veterinary Services

4.10. Toxoplasmosis

4.10.1. General evaluation of the national situation

No data available.

4.10.2. Toxoplasma in humans

Not notifiable in Austria.

4.10.3. Toxoplasma in animals

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

There is no official surveillance for *Toxoplasma* spp. in animals. Sampling of cattle, sheep, goats or pigs is performed depending on clinical suspicion of toxoplasmosis and if ordered by the sender in cases after abortion. Other animal species are also occasionally sampled.

Frequency of the sampling

In case of clinical suspicion and abortion and if ordered.

Type of specimen taken

Blood, organ, faeces

Case definition

A case is defined as an animal that tested positive serologically ($\geq 1:40$) or if the pathogen is detected microscopically. The animal is the epidemiological unit.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

The diagnostic methods used for serology is the microagglutination test.

Vaccination policy:

No vaccination

Other preventative measures than vaccination in place:

Control programme/ mechanisms:

The control programmes/ strategies in place

Nil

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases:**Notification system in place:**

Toxoplasmosis is not notifiable in animals.

Results of the investigation

No valid data available

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection:

Nil

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection):**Additional information**

Nil

Table 79 Toxoplasmosis in animals

animal species	sampling context	sampling details	Source of information	sampling unit	Total units tested	Total units positive for Toxoplasma	
							T. gondii
dog	clinical investiagtion	organ	AGES IVET	animal	1	0	0
cat	clinical investiagtion	blood	AGES IVET	animal	2	1	1
cat	clinical investiagtion	feces	AGES IVET	animal	1	0	0
cat	clinical investiagtion	organ	AGES IVET	animal	1	0	0
cattle	clinical investiagtion	blood	AGES IVET	animal	23	0	0
sheep	clinical investiagtion	blood	AGES IVET	animal	41	20	20
sheep	clinical investiagtion	organ	AGES IVET	animal	1	0	0
pig	clinical investiagtion	blood	AGES IVET	animal	5	1	1
goat	clinical investiagtion	blood	AGES IVET	animal	74	32	32
goat	clinical investiagtion	organ	AGES IVET	animal	2	1	1

4.11. Rabies

4.11.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Rabies in humans was a major public health issue in the 1960s.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2009, there was no case of rabies detected in animals in Austria.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

In 2009, vaccination programmes were carried out in fox populations in areas of higher risk. Additionally, a brochure was published by AGES and BMG: Recommendations for prophylaxis in humans (http://www.ages.at/uploads/media/Tollwut_01.pdf).

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Additional information

Nil

4.11.2. Rabies in humans

Case definition

Laboratory criteria for diagnosis

Detection by direct fluorescent antibody of viral antigens in a clinical specimen (preferably the brain or the nerves surrounding hair follicles in the nape of the neck)

Detection of rabies nucleic acid in clinical specimen

Isolation (in cell culture or in a laboratory animal) of rabies virus from saliva, cerebrospinal fluid (CSF), or central nervous system tissue

Identification of a rabies-neutralising antibody titre (complete neutralization) in the serum or CSF of an unvaccinated person.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Liquor, smears from pharynx, swab from conjunctivae biopsy at the nape of the neck and serum were examined in the fluorescent antibody test (FAT), immunohistochemistry and RT-PCR (Ito M., Itou T., Sakai T., et al. (2001). Detection of Rabies Virus RNA isolated from several species of animals in Brazil by RT-PCR. Journal of Veterinary medicine Science 63(12): 1309-1313.).

Notification system in place

Notification of rabies according to the epidemic act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended):
The attending physicians and the laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Nil

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Nil

Relevance as zoonotic disease

Nil

Data source of Table 79: national reference laboratory for rabies

Table 80 Rabies in humans

	Cases	Incidence/1 00,000	Autochtone cases	Imported cases
Rabies	0	0	0	0
Human expose	0	0	0	0

4.11.3. Lyssavirus (rabies) in animals

A. Rabies virus in animal - Wildlife - foxes

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

According to GZ:39.642/14-VII/B/03: 8 foxes per 100 qkm in rabies infected and rabies endangered areas, 4 foxes per 100 qkm in not endangered and free areas (definition of areas: GZ 30.517/35-IV/12/03).

Frequency of the sampling

8 foxes per 100 km² in rabies infested and rabies endangered areas, 4 foxes per 100km² in not endangered and free areas.

Type of specimen taken

Other: Brain (brain stem or hippocampus)

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Whole animals or heads of the dead animals are sent to the laboratories; sometimes brain tissue (derived from other laboratories). Brain tissue (e.g. 1 cm²) is examined.

Case definition

An animal is considered positive if the fluorescent antibody test (FAT) shows a positive signal.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

The routine test was the fluorescent antibody test (FAT).

RTCIT (rabies tissue culture infection test) was performed on mouse neuroblastoma cells.

MIT (mouse inoculation test) will be only performed on demand, not for routine confirmation

Vaccination policy

Delivery of vaccine containing baits in the southern part of East Tyrol; the requirement is 25 baits/km² in an area of approximately 854 km² (27 packets with 800 pieces each); additionally emergency vaccination from southern Tyrol to the Deferegger Alps (iG, Drautal) Lesachtal in

Carinthia due to cases of rabies registered in North Italy since October 2008 (108 confirmed cases; http://www.hpa.org.uk/web/HPAweb&HPAwebStandard/HPAweb_C/1224745740644; last visit 28.04.2010) and the expansion of the infected area until the border of Austria (southern areas in Burgenland, Styria and Carinthia). Reported cases were observed recently in November 2009.

Figure 1. Cases registered in Northern Italy (circle) and planned vaccination area in Austria

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

No measures

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Fuchs-Tollwutbekämpfungsverordnung BGBl II 2001/75, Tierseuchengesetz TSG RgBl 1909/177 as amended, BGBl I 2002/65 IV. Abschnitt, §41, §42, Tierseuchengesetz-Durchführungsverordnung 1909/178 as amended: BGBl 1955/76 TSG-DVO zum IV. Abschnitt Wutkrankheiten

Control of vaccination: Detection of tetracycline in jaw bones of randomly chosen foxes from the vaccination area; additionally an ELISA is performed to proof seroconversion.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

A helicopter was requested to delivery the baits; recommendation of vaccination for dogs and cats in the southern border area and public awareness through BMGs homepage.

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Probably the reduction of the number of the animals (foxes) for investigation

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Tierseuchengesetz TSG RGBI 1909/177 as amended, BGBl I 2002/65 IV. Abschnitt, §41, §42, and vaccination of the fox population

Notification system in place

According to Tierseuchengesetz TSG RGBI 1909/177 as amended, BGBl I 2002/65 IV. Abschnitt, §41, §42

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Austria is declared as rabies free since 28.9.08. Note the additional emergency vaccination in Carinthia according GZ. 74.10070105-IV/B572008

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

B. Rabies virus in animal - all animals except foxes

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Sampling is targeted when animals are observed with central nerval symptoms or after biting a person. The suspicious animal is killed or euthanized and the carcass or head is sent to the laboratory.

Frequency of the sampling

If a case is suspected

Type of specimen taken

Other: Brain (hippocampus and brain stem)

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Routinely a sample will be taken from one site of the brain: a part from the hippocampus, brain stem or cerebellum. If an animal has bitten a person then 2 parts from the brain will be taken: hippocampus and brain stem.

Case definition

An animal is considered positive if the fluorescent antibody tests (FAT) or the rabies tissue culture infection test or the mouse inoculation test show a positive result.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

The routine test was the fluorescent antibody test (FAT).

RTCIT (rabies tissue culture infection test) was performed on mouse neuroblastoma cells.

MIT (mouse inoculation test) will be only performed on demand, not for routine confirmation

Vaccination policy

Voluntary vaccination of pets.

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

No measures

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Tierseuchengesetz TSG RGBI 1909/177 as amended, BGBl I 2002/65 IV. Abschnitt, §41, §42;

Tierseuchengesetz-Durchführungsverordnung 1909/178 as amended: BGBl 1955/76

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Tierseuchengesetz TSG RGBI 1909/177 as amended, BGBl I 2002/65 IV. Abschnitt, §41, §42. If a rabies suspicious pet bites a person, the person is treated.

Notification system in place

According to Tierseuchengesetz TSG RGBI 1909/177 as amended, BGBl I 2002/65 IV. Abschnitt, §41, §42

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Nil

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

On 28th of September 2008, Austria has been declared free of rabies.

Vaccination areas, rabies endangered and rabies free areas were redefined.

Table 81 Rabies in animals

Fehler! Keine gültige Verknüpfung.

4.12. Q-Fever

4.12.1. General evaluation of the situation

In January 2010, a questionnaire was sent to nine laboratories in nine Austrian provinces, requesting anonymized data on Q fever tests performed in 2009. In parallel, all Austrian Departments of Infectious Disease were asked to report clinical cases of Q fever diagnosed in 2009. In total, 5361 initial sera were tested, 166 yielding antibody titers' specific for *C. burnetii* (3.1%). Three patients showed signs and symptoms compatible with Q fever, two of them with connections to highly likely animal reservoirs. No outbreak was documented in 2009.

4.12.2. Q-fever in humans

Not notifiable in Austria, therefore no data available

4.12.3. *Coxiella burnetii* in animals

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

There is no official surveillance for *Coxiella burnetii* in animals. Sampling of cattle, sheep or goats is performed in case of clinical suspicion of Q-fever and after abortion.

Frequency of the sampling

In case of clinical suspicion and abortion.

Type of specimen taken

Blood

Case definition

A case is defined as an animal showing a titre $\geq 1:20$ or a positive PCR reaction. The animal is the epidemiological unit.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

The diagnostic method is the complement fixation reaction, detecting phase 1 and phase 2 antigens. Organs and swabs are tested by real time PCR.

Vaccination policy

No vaccination.

Other preventative measures than vaccination in place:

Nil

Control programme/ mechanisms

The control programmes/ strategies in place

Nil

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Notification system in place

Q-fever in animals is not a notifiable disease

Results of the investigation

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Q-fever in humans is not a notifiable disease. In Austria the number of sheep per holding is low (3.9 animals per holding in average) compared to countries that have a problem with Q-fever; therefore no change of the epidemiological situation in Austria is expected.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

Nil

Table 82 Q-fever in animals

Animal species	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Sampling Details	Source of information	Sampling unit	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Coxiella burnetii</i>
Cattle	clinical investigations	at farm - animal sample - organ/tissue	Coxiella burnetii	AGES IVET	animal	3	1
Cattle	clinical investigations	at farm - animal sample - blood	Coxiella burnetii Ak	AGES IVET	animal	926	31
Sheep	clinical investigations	at farm - animal sample - organ/tissue	Coxiella burnetii	AGES IVET	animal	1	0
Sheep	clinical investigations	at farm - animal sample - blood	Coxiella burnetii Ak	AGES IVET	animal	34	0
Goats	clinical investigations	at farm - animal sample - organ/tissue	Coxiella burnetii	AGES IVET	animal	3	1
Goats	clinical investigations	at farm - animal sample - blood	Coxiella burnetii Ak	AGES IVET	animal	90	1

VET: all AGES Institute for Veterinary Disease Control

5. Information on Specific Indicators of Antimicrobial Resistance

5.1. E. coli Indicators

5.1.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Resistance monitoring of faeces isolates from slaughtered animals was started in Austria in 2004 and has been continued annually.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

The Austrian wide monitoring program on the trends of antimicrobial resistance of E. coli in broiler slaughter batches, bovine animals and pigs was implemented according to the directive 2003/99/EC of the European Parliament and the Council of 17 November 2003 in the National Order GZ: BMGF-74600/0092-IV/B/8/2005 (Überwachungsprogramme 2005 zu ausgewählten Zoonosen und Antibiotikaresistenzen). The sampling was carried out from January to December 2009 in slaughterhouses.

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Europe wide harmonized standards for antimicrobial resistance monitoring are be highly welcome.

Additional information

The results are published annually in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria (AURES).

5.1.2. Antimicrobial resistance in Escherichia coli isolates

A. Antimicrobial resistance of E. coli in animal - All animals - farmed - at slaughterhouse - Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling

Sampling strategy used in monitoring

Frequency of the sampling

A sampling plan was created according to the federal surveillance program „Überwachung ausgewählter Zoonosen und Antibiotikaresistenzen 2009 (GZ BMGFJ GZ 74600/0274-IV/B/5/2008)“. The sampling plan for E. coli included cattle, pigs and broiler slaughter batches.

Type of specimen taken

E. coli was isolated from the caecum of slaughtered cattle, pigs and broiler. 170 E. coli strains were tested for their antimicrobial susceptibility. The caecum from one cow or pig or the whole intestines from ten slaughtered broilers within a single slaughter batch at each slaughterhouse were collected.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

The intestines were refrigerated to 4 °C and samples were sent to the Institute of Veterinary Disease Control (IVET) in Graz, where each pathogen was isolated and further characterized. The national Reference Lab for antimicrobial resistance in the Institute of Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED) in Graz performed the antimicrobial susceptibility testing for all strains.

Procedures for the selection of isolates for antimicrobial testing

The number of samples was calculated by experts of the Division for Data, Statistics and Risk Assessment of the AGES based on the expected prevalence of E. coli among the different animal species (cattle, pigs, broiler flocks). All isolated strains of E. coli were sent to the IMED Graz for antimicrobial susceptibility testing.

Methods used for collecting data

All information concerning the tested animals and the sampled slaughterhouses were recorded in a questionnaire. In the laboratory, the data were entered into a database and later analysed in Microsoft® Excel tables.

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

The intestinal contents are streaked onto the MacConkey-agar plates (Merck Nr. 1.05465) and incubated for 24 hrs at 37±1 °C. The process is repeated for colonies which are suspected for E. coli. These colonies are streaked onto a blood-agar (Oxoid Nr. CM0055, 5% Sheep blood) and incubated for 24 hrs at 37±1 °C. The confirmation of the identification of E. coli is done with an oxidase- (Merck Nr. 1.13300.0001) and spot indol test (Firma Biomedica, Nr. 1069).

Laboratory used for detection for resistance

Antimicrobials included in monitoring

E. coli samples isolated from cattle, pigs and broiler slaughter batches are tested for antimicrobial susceptibility against gentamicin, kanamycin, streptomycin, ceftotaxim, sulfamethoxazol, trimethoprim, ciprofloxacin, nalidixic acid, ampicillin, chloramphenicol and tetracycline.

Breakpoints used in testing

See respective tables

Preventive measures in place

None

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

None

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

None

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

None

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

None

Notification system in place

None

Results of the investigation

See respective tables.

National evaluation of the recent situation

Trends and sources of infection is not available yet; a census on the use of antimicrobials in veterinary medicine is planned.

Additional information

Table 83 Breakpoints used for antibiotic resistance testing of E. coli in animals

Test method used	Number of reporting laboratory	1
Disc diffusion		
E-test		
Agar dilution		
Broth dilution	x	

Standards used for testing	The methods are used for investigation of isolates from
CLSI	Feedingstuff
other	Animals x
EN ISO 20776-1	Food x
	Humans

<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Standard for breakpoint (NCCLS,...)	Dilution method		
		Breakpoint	Range tested concentration (µg/ml)	
			Resistant >	lowest
Aminoglykosid AB				
Gentamicin	EFSA	> 2	0,25	32
Streptomycin	EFSA	> 16	2	256
Carbapeneme				
Imipenem	EFSA	> 0.5	0.125	32
Cephalosporine				
Cefotaxim	EFSA	> 0,25	0,06	128
Folsäureinhibitoren				
Sulfamethoxazol	EFSA	> 256	8	1024
Trimethoprim	EFSA	> 2	0,25	16
Quinolone and Quinoxalin				
Ciprofloxacin	EFSA	> 0,032	0,008	8
Nalidixinsäure	EFSA	> 16	2	256
Penicilline				
Ampicillin	EFSA	> 8	0,5	64
Phenicole				
Chloramphenicol	EFSA	> 16	2	256
Tetracycline				
Tetracyclin	EFSA	> 8	0,5	64

Table 84 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of E. coli in animals (qualitative tables)

	Gallus Gallus			Cattle			Pigs		
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes			yes			yes		
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	170			168			162		
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n
Aminoglykosid AB									
Gentamicin	170	2,9	5	168	0,0	0	162	1,9	3
Streptomycin	170	41,2	70	168	4,2	7	162	50,0	81
Carbapeneme									
Imipenem									
Cephalosporine									
Cefotaxim	170	2,4	4	168	0,0	0	162	0,6	1
Folsäureinhibitoren									
Sulfamethoxazol	170	37,6	64	168	3,0	5	162	30,9	50
Trimethoprim	170	20,0	34	168	1,2	2	162	15,4	25
Quinolone and Quinoxalin									
Ciprofloxacin	170	64,7	110	168	0,0	0	162	1,2	2
Nalidixinsäure	170	62,9	107	168	0,0	0	162	1,2	2
Penicilline									
Ampicillin	170	32,9	56	168	3,0	5	162	13,6	22
Phenicol									
Chloramphenicol	170	7,1	12	168	2,4	4	162	4,9	8
Tetracycline									
Tetracyclin	170	25,9	44	168	6,5	11	162	56,2	91
Number of multiresistant isolates									
fully sensitive	170	21,8	37	168	92,3	155	162	35,8	58
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	170	31,8	54	168	3,0	5	162	32,1	52
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	170	15,9	27	168	2,4	4	162	11,7	19
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	170	10,6	18	168	1,2	2	162	13,6	22
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	170	5,9	10	168	1,2	2	162	5,6	9
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	170	14,1	24	168	0,0		162	1,2	2

Number of fully-susceptible and number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 or >4 antimicrobials of different classes, excluding cross-resistance. For E. coli this includes resistance to ampicillin, cefotaxime, nalidixic acid, streptomycin, gentamicin, tetracycline, chloramphenicol, trimethoprim and sulphamethoxazol

Table 85 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of E. coli in Cattle (bovine animals) - at slaughter - monitoring programme - active monitoring - quantitative data [Dilution method]

		<i>E.coli</i> CATTLE																					
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																						
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	168		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n	=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
Aminoglykosid AB	N	%R	n	n																			
Gentamicin	168	0,0	0						92	68	7	1											
Streptomycin	168	4,2	7									4	124	31	2	1	2		2	2			
Carbapeneme																							
Imipenem																							
Cephalosporine																							
Cefotaxim	168	0,0	0				155	13															
Folsäureinhibitoren																							
Sulfamethoxazol	168	3,0	5											17	56	63	27					5	
Trimethoprim	168	1,2	2						52	81	29	4		1		1							
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																							
Ciprofloxacin	168	0,0	0	14	139	15																	
Nalidixinsäure	168	0,0	0									137	29	2									
Penicilline																							
Ampicillin	168	3,0	5							1	5	69	83	5					5				
Phenicole																							
Chloramphenicol	168	2,4	4									7	42	107	8	1		1	2				
Tetracycline																							
Tetracyclin	168	6,5	11								16	128	13				4	7					

Table 86 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of E. coli in broiler - at slaughter - monitoring programme – active monitoring (slaughter batch) - quantitative data [Dilution method]

				<i>E.coli</i>																				
				GALLUS GALLUS																				
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																						
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		170		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
Antimicrobials:				=<0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
				n																				
Aminoglykosid AB				N	%R	n																		
	Gentamicin	170	2,9	5					45	98	22			1		2	2							
	Streptomycin	170	41,2	70								4	50	36	10	23	17	15	10	5				
Carbapeneme																								
	Imipenem																							
Cephalosporine																								
	Cefotaxim	170	2,4	4			126	39	1		1	1	2											
Folsäureinhibitoren																								
	Sulfamethoxazol	170	37,6	64										17	27	44	14	3	1		1	63		
	Trimethoprim	170	20,0	34					54	59	18	5												
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																								
	Ciprofloxacin	170	64,7	110	5	48	7	2	13	54	14	7	1	2	17									
	Nalidixinsäure	170	62,9	107								45	13	4	1	2	20	42	9	34				
Penicilline																								
	Ampicillin	170	32,9	56						1	2	53	51	7										
Phenicole																								
	Chloramphenicol	170	7,1	12								1	24	114	19	1	1	1	9					
Tetracycline																								
	Tetracyclin	170	25,9	44						1	11	87	25	2	1	1	10	32						

Table 87 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of E. coli in Pigs - at slaughter - monitoring programme - active monitoring - quantitative data [Dilution method]

		<i>E.coli</i>																			
		PIGS																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																				
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	162																				
		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Antimicrobials:		=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
Aminoglykosid AB	N	%R	n																		
Gentamicin	162	1,9				49	88	22				1	1	1							
Streptomycin	162	50,0								3	34	30	14	19	30	17	11	4			
Carbapeneme																					
Imipenem																					
Cephalosporine																					
Cefotaxim	162	0,6			156	5						1									
Folsäureinhibitoren																					
Sulfamethoxazol	162	30,9										20	38	39	9	6					50
Trimethoprim	162	15,4				51	67	19			1			24							
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																					
Ciprofloxacin	162	1,2	19	121	20		2														
Nalidixinsäure	162	1,2								130	30					2					
Penicilline																					
Ampicillin	162	13,6							12	81	44	3		1	1	20					
Phenicol																					
Chloramphenicol	162	4,9								4	45	100	5	1	1	1	5				
Tetracycline																					
Tetracyclin	162	56,2							13	52	5	1		3	17	71					

5.2. Enterococcus Indicators

5.2.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Resistance monitoring of faeces isolates from slaughtered animals was started in Austria in 2004 and continued in 2009.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Nil

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

The Austrian wide monitoring program on the trends of antimicrobial resistance of enterococci in broiler slaughter batches, bovine animals and pigs was implemented according to the directive 2003/99/EC of the European Parliament and the Council of 17 November 2003 in the National Order GZ: BMGF-74600/0092-IV/B/8/2005 (Überwachungsprogramme 2005 zu ausgewählten Zoonosen und Antibiotikaresistenzen). The sampling was carried out from January to December 2008 in slaughterhouses.

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Europe wide harmonized standards for antimicrobial resistance monitoring would be highly welcome.

Additional information

5.2.2. Antimicrobial resistance in Enterococcus spp. isolates

A. Antimicrobial resistance of Enterococcus spp. in animal - All animals - farmed - at slaughterhouse - Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling

Sampling strategy used in monitoring

Frequency of the sampling

A sampling plan was created according to the federal surveillance program „Überwachung ausgewählter Zoonosen und Antibiotikaresistenzen 2009 (GZ BMGFJ GZ 74600/274-IV/B/5/2008)“. The sampling plan for enterococci includes cattle, pigs and broiler slaughter batches.

Type of specimen taken

Enterococci are isolated from the caecum of slaughtered cattle, pigs and broiler. 170 E. faecalis or E. faecium strains per animal species are tested for their antimicrobial susceptibility. The caecum from one cow or pig or the whole intestines from ten slaughtered broilers within a single slaughter batch at each slaughterhouse are collected.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

The intestines were refrigerated to 4 °C and samples were sent to the Institute of Veterinary Disease Control (IVET) in Graz, where each pathogen was isolated and further characterized. The Institute of Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED) in Graz performed the antimicrobial susceptibility testing for all strains.

Procedures for the selection of isolates for antimicrobial testing

The number of samples was calculated by experts of the Division for Data, Statistics and Risk Assessment of the AGES based on the expected prevalence of *Enterococcus faecalis* and *E. faecium* in the different animal species (cattle, pigs, broiler flocks). From each sample up to five enterococci were differentiated. Only *E. faecalis* and *E. faecium* strains were sent to the IMED Graz for antimicrobial susceptibility testing.

Methods used for collecting data

All information concerning the tested animals and the sampled slaughterhouses were recorded in a questionnaire. In the laboratory, the data were entered into a database and later analysed in Microsoft® Excel tables.

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

The samples are injected into the Citrate Azide Tween Carbonate Agar (CATC-AGAR, Merck Art.Nr. 1.10279) and incubated at $37\text{ °C} \pm 1\text{ °C}$ for 24 h. Then, the medium is left at room temperature for another 24 hrs. Potential colonies are subcultivated on blood agar (Oxoid Nr. CM0055, 5% Sheep blood) for 24 h at $37 \pm 1\text{ °C}$ which results in the differentiation of *E. faecalis* and *E. faecium* through Gram's method, Catalase Test, Arabinose- and Pyruvate-breakdown.

Laboratory used for detection for resistance

Antimicrobials included in monitoring

E. faecalis/faecium samples isolated from cattle, pigs and broiler slaughter batches are tested for antimicrobial resistance against gentamicin, streptomycin, vancomycin, ciprofloxacin, erythromycin, nitrofurantoin, avilamycin, ampicillin, chloramphenicol, bacitracin, synercid and tetracycline.

Breakpoints used in testing

See respective tables

Preventive measures in place

None

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

None

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

None

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

None

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

None

Notification system in place

None

Results of the investigation

See respective tables. National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection is not available yet; a census on the use of antimicrobials in veterinary medicine is planned.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Not yet available

Additional information

Nil

Table 88 Breakpoints used for antibiotic resistance testing of *Enterococcus faecalis* in animals

Test method used	Number of reporting laboratory	1
Disc diffusion		
E-test		
Agar dilution		
Broth dilution	x	

Standards used for testing	The methods are used for investigation of isolates f
CLSI	Feedingstuff
other	Animals
EN ISO 20776-1	x
	Food
	Humans

<i>E. faecalis</i>	Standard for breakpoint (NCCLS,...)	Dilution method		
		Breakpoint	Range tested concentration (µg/ml)	
			Resistant >	lowest
Aminoglykosid AB				
Gentamicin	EFSA	> 32	4	2048
Streptomycin	EFSA	> 512	16	2048
Glycopeptide				
Vancomycin	EFSA	> 4	1	64
Quinolone and Quinoxalin				
Ciprofloxacin	EUCAST	> 4	0,25	32
Makrolide				
Erythromycin	EFSA	> 4	0,5	64
Oxacolidinone				
Linezolid	EFSA	> 4	0.5	32
Penicilline				
Ampicillin	EFSA	> 4	0.25	32
Phenicole				
Chloramphenicol	EFSA	> 32	4	256
Streptogramine				
Synercid	EFSA	> 32	0.5	128
Tetracycline				
Tetracyclin	EUCAST	> 4	0.5	64
Tigecyclin	EUCAST	> 0.25	0.032	1
Cyclic Lipopeptides				
Daptomycin	EUCAST	> 4	0.125	16

Table 89 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *E. faecalis* in animals (qualitative tables)

	Gallus Gallus	Cattle	Pigs			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes	yes	yes			
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	30	14	20			
Antimicrobials:	N	n	N	n	N	n
Aminoglykosid AB						
Gentamicin	30	1	14	0	20	0
Streptomycin	30	4	14	2	20	3
Glycopeptide						
Vancomycin	30	1	14	0	20	0
Quinolone and Quinoxalin						
Ciprofloxacin	30	1	14	0	20	0
Makrolide						
Erythromycin	30	14	14	0	20	7
Oxacolidinone						
Linezolid	30	0	14	0	20	0
Penicilline						
Ampicillin	30	0	14	0	20	0
Phenicole						
Chloramphenicol	30	0	14	0	20	1
Streptogramine						
Synercid	30	1	14	0	20	0
Tetracycline						
Tetracyclin	30	18	14	2	20	14
Tigecyclin			14	0		
Cyclic Lipopeptides						
Daptomycin	30	0	14	0	20	0
Number of multiresistant isolates						
fully sensitive	30	7	14	12	20	6
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	30	12	14	0	20	6
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	30	7	14	2	20	5
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	30	3	14	0	20	3
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	30	1	14	0	20	0
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	30	0	14	0	20	0

Number of fully-susceptible and number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 or >4 antimicrobials of different classes, excluding cross-resistance. For enterococci this includes resistance to streptomycin, gentamicin, chloramphenicol, ampicillin, vancomycin, erythromycin, synercid, tetracycline

Table 90 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *E. faecalis* in Cattle (bovine animals) - at slaughter - monitoring programme - active monitoring - quantitative data [Dilution method]

<i>E. faecalis</i> CATTLE																						
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	14	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n	<=0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
Aminoglykosid AB				n																		
Gentamicin	14	0	0										11	3								
Streptomycin	14	14,3	2													7	5					2
Glycopeptide																						
Vancomycin	14	0	0						11	3												
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																						
Ciprofloxacin	14	0	0					2	8	4												
Makrolide																						
Erythromycin	14	0	0					2	3	4	5											
Oxacolidinone																						
Linezolid	14	0	0						2	10	2											
Penicilline																						
Ampicillin	14	0	0						7	7												
Phenicole																						
Chloramphenicol	14	0	0								4	10										
Streptogramine																						
Synercid	14	0	0								2	8	3	1								
Tetracycline																						
Tetracyclin	14	14,3	2					6	6							2						
Tigecyclin	14	0	0		8	5	1															
Cyclic Lipopeptides																						
Daptomycin	14	0	0					2	8	4												

Table 91 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *E. faecalis* in Pigs - at slaughter - monitoring programme - active monitoring - quantitative data [Dilution method]

<i>E. faecalis</i>		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
PIGS																						
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	20																					
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n	<=0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
Aminoglykosid AB				n																		
Gentamicin	20	0	0										18	2								
Streptomycin	20	15	3													10	7					3
Glycopeptide																						
Vancomycin	20	0	0					14	5	1												
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																						
Ciprofloxacin	20	0	0					15	5													
Makrolide																						
Erythromycin	20	35	7				3	4	3	3						7						
Oxacolidinone																						
Linezolid	20	0	0					1	17	2												
Penicilline																						
Ampicillin	20	0	0					17	3													
Phenicole																						
Chloramphenicol	20	5	1							2	10	5	2	1								
Streptogramine																						
Synercid	20	0	0									9	10	1								
Tetracycline																						
Tetracyclin	20	70	14				4	1		1					4	10						
Tigecyclin																						
Cyclic Lipopeptides																						
Daptomycin	20	0	0				1	17	2													

Table 92 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *E. faecalis* in broiler - at slaughter - monitoring programme - active monitoring - quantitative data [Dilution method]

		<i>E. faecalis</i>																			
		GALLUS GALLUS																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																				
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	30	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n	<=0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
Aminoglykosid AB				n																	
Gentamicin	30	3,3	1									5	23	1				1			
Streptomycin	30	13,3	4													22	3	1			4
Glycopeptide																					
Vancomycin	30	3,3	1						19	9	1					1					
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																					
Ciprofloxacin	30	3,3	1					6	20	3				1							
Makrolide																					
Erythromycin	30	46,7	14					5	2	4	5		1			13					
Oxacolidinone																					
Linezolid	30	0,0	0						10	19	1										
Penicilline																					
Ampicillin	30	0,0	0						24	5	1										
Phenicole																					
Chloramphenicol	30	0,0	0								3	21	6								
Streptogramine																					
Synercid	30	3,3	1								1	17	11				1				
Tetracycline																					
Tetracyclin	30	60,0	18					9	1		2			3	10	5					
Tigecyclin																					
Cyclic Lipopeptides																					
Daptomycin	30	0,0	0					5	25												

Table 93 Breakpoints used for antibiotic resistance testing of *Enterococcus faecium* in animals

Test method used	Number of reporting laboratory
Disc diffusion	
E-test	
Agar dilution	
Broth dilution	x

Standards used for testing	The methods are used for investigation of isolates from
CLSI	Feedingstuff
other	Animals x
EN ISO 20776-1	Food
	Humans

<i>E. faecium</i>	Standard for breakpoint (NCCLS,...)	Dilution method		
		Breakpoint	Range tested concentration (µg/ml)	
			Resistant >	lowest
Aminoglykosid AB				
Gentamicin	EFSA	> 32	4	2048
Streptomycin	EFSA	> 128	16	2048
Glycopeptide				
Vancomycin	EFSA	> 4	1	64
Quinolone and Quinoxalin				
Ciprofloxacin	EUCAST	> 4	0,25	32
Makrolide				
Erythromycin	EFSA	> 4	0,5	64
Nitrofurane				
Nitrofurantoin	EUCAST	> 256	8	512
Orthosomycine				
Avilamycin	EUCAST	> 16	1	128
Penicilline				
Ampicillin	EFSA	> 4	0,25	32
Phenicole				
Chloramphenicol	EFSA	> 32	4	256
Polypeptide				
Bacitracin	EUCAST	32	8	256
Streptogramine				
Synercid	EFSA	> 1	0,5	128
Tetracycline				
Tetracyclin	EUCAST	> 4	0,5	64

Table 94 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *E. faecium* in animals (qualitative tables)

	Gallus Gallus			Cattle			Pigs		
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes			yes			yes		
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	132			132			129		
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n
Aminoglykosid AB									
Gentamicin	132	1,5	2	132	0,8	1	129	0,8	1
Streptomycin	132	17,4	23	132	6,1	8	129	3,1	4
Glycopeptide									
Vancomycin	132	1,5	2	132	3,0	4	129	3,9	5
Quinolone and Quinoxalin									
Ciprofloxacin	132	3,0	4	132	3,8	5	129	1,6	2
Makrolide									
Erythromycin	132	54,5	72	132	8,3	11	129	28,7	37
Nitrofurane									
Nitrofurantoin	132	0,0	0	132	0,0	0	129	0,8	1
Orthosomycine									
Avilamycin	132	4,5	6	132	0,8	1	129	2,3	3
Penicilline									
Ampicillin	132	3,8	5	132	1,5	2	129	2,3	3
Phenicole									
Chloramphenicol	132	0,0	0	132	0,0	0	129	0,8	1
Polypeptide									
Bacitracin	132	73,5	97	132	81,1	107	129	87,6	113
Streptogramine									
Synercid	132	77,3	102	132	82,6	109	129	84,5	109
Tetracycline									
Tetracyclin	132	53,8	71	132	15,2	20	129	13,2	17
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n
fully sensitive	132	6,1	8	132	12,9	17	129	14,0	18
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	132	24,2	32	132	65,9	87	129	47,3	61
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	132	31,1	41	132	14,4	19	129	28,7	37
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	132	32,6	43	132	4,5	6	129	7,8	10
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	132	4,5	6	132	2,3	3	129	2,3	3
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	132	1,5	2	132	0,0		129	0	0

Number of fully-susceptible and number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 or >4 antimicrobials of different classes, excluding cross-resistance. For enterococci this includes resistance to streptomycin, gentamicin, chloramphenicol, ampicillin, vancomycin, erythromycin, synercid, tetracyclin

Table 95 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *E. faecium* in Cattle (bovine animals) - at slaughter - monitoring programme - active monitoring - quantitative data [Dilution method]

<i>E. faecium</i>																						
CATTLE																						
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	132	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n	<=0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
Aminoglykosid AB				n																		
Gentamicin	132	0,76	1								46	74	9	2	1							
Streptomycin	132	6,06	8										16	17	84	7		1	5	2		
Glycopeptide																						
Vancomycin	132	3,03	4						98	8	22	4										
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																						
Ciprofloxacin	132	3,79	5				10	23	65	12	17	5										
Makrolide																						
Erythromycin	132	8,33	11					56	6	24	35	11										
Nitrofurane																						
Nitrofurantoin	132	0	0										31	26	14	59	2					
Orthosomycine																						
Avilamycin	132	0,76	1						15	95	21						1					
Penicilline																						
Ampicillin	132	1,52	2													1						
Phenicole																						
Chloramphenicol	132	0	0									68	63	1								
Polypeptide																						
Bacitracin	132	81,1	107										9	3	13	50	45	6	6			
Streptogramine																						
Synercid	132	82,6	109					11	12	29	65	8	6				1					
Tetracycline																						
Tetracyclin	132	15,2	20					92	17	1	2		1	2	9	8						

Table 96 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *E. faecium* in Pigs - at slaughter - monitoring programme - active monitoring - quantitative data [Dilution method]

		<i>E. faecium</i>																				
		PIGS																				
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	129	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n	<=0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
Aminoglykosid AB				n																		
Gentamicin	129	0,8	1								34	86	8								1	
Streptomycin	129	3,1	4										15	22	85	3			1	1		2
Glycopeptide																						
Vancomycin	129	3,9	5						117	6	1	3				2						
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																						
Ciprofloxacin	129	1,6	2				6	24	63	17	17	1		1								
Makrolide																						
Erythromycin	129	28,7	37					32	12	13	35	29	1	1		6						
Nitrofurane																						
Nitrofurantoin	129	0,8	1									11	10	17	88	2				1		
Orthosomycine																						
Avilamycin	129	2,3	3						12	99	14	1				1	2					
Penicilline																						
Ampicillin	129	2,3	3				17	25	66	15	3				3							
Phenicole																						
Chloramphenicol	129	0,8	1								73	55			1							
Polypeptide																						
Bacitracin	129	87,6	113									6	2	8	24	85	1	3				
Streptogramine																						
Synercid	129	84,5	109					11	9	18	74	11	2	1	1	2						
Tetracycline																						
Tetracyclin	129	13,2	17					97	12	2	1	2		3	8	4						

Table 97 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *E. faecium* in broiler - at slaughter - monitoring programme - active monitoring - quantitative data [Dilution method]

		<i>E. faecium</i>																				
		GALLUS GALLUS																				
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	132	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n	<=0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
Aminoglykosid AB				n																		
Gentamicin	132	1,5	2								50	73	7								1	1
Streptomycin	132	17	23										9	41	55	4	3	2	4	5	9	
Glycopeptide																						
Vancomycin	132	1,5	2					126		4	1		1									
Quinolone and Quinoxalin																						
Ciprofloxacin	132	3	4				5	9	46	31	37	4										
Makrolide																						
Erythromycin	132	55	72				20	13	17	10	1	1		2	68							
Nitrofurane																						
Nitrofurantoin	132	0	0									13	19	40	41	17	2					
Orthosomycine																						
Avilamycin	132	4,5	6						45	74	6		1	4			2					
Penicilline																						
Ampicillin	132	3,8	5				21	30	32	21	23	2		1	2							
Phenicole																						
Chloramphenicol	132	0	0								80	36	13	3								
Polypeptide																						
Bacitracin	132	73	97									18	6	11	29	13	13	42				
Streptogramine																						
Synercid	132	77	102					12	18	33	47	12	6	4								
Tetracycline																						
Tetracyclin	132	54	71					51	9		1	4	1	6	38	22						

6. Foodborne outbreaks

Foodborne outbreaks are defined as two or more human cases of the same disease or infection where the cases are linked or are probably linked to the same food source. A situation in which the observed human cases exceed the expected number of cases and where a same food source is suspected, is also indicative of a foodborne outbreak.

A. Foodborne outbreaks

System in place for identification, epidemiological investigations and reporting of food borne outbreaks

Presently, every district (Austria = 98 + Vienna) is responsible for outbreak investigation. However, food borne outbreaks affecting more than one district or even more than one province (Austria = 9 provinces) are regulated by the Federal Zoonoses Act (Zoonosengesetz, BGBl. I, 128/2005 entered into force on 1. January 2006). The Federal Zoonoses Commission was founded to advise the Federal Minister to survey and combat the zoonoses in Austria. One target of the Zoonoses Act is to ensure that food-borne outbreaks receive proper epidemiological investigation. It regulates, in case of food borne outbreaks affecting more than one province that the governors of the affected provinces provide operative units to investigate possible or confirmed food borne outbreaks. Data concerning epidemiological criteria, potential implicated food items and the source of an outbreak must be collected and adequate epidemiological and microbiological examinations must be conducted. Short reports summarize each outbreak and must be communicated to the Federal Commission for Zoonoses and to AGES.

Description of the types of outbreaks covered by the reporting:

Since there has not been a coordinated approach for outbreak investigation in most provinces, the large majority (319 of 351) of food borne outbreaks are classified as household outbreaks. Coordinated investigation of outbreaks affecting more than one province - unhampered by district limits - will drastically decrease the total number of outbreaks.

National evaluation of the reported outbreaks in the country:

In 2009, 351 food borne outbreaks (11 verified and 340 possible) affecting 1,330 persons were reported. 323 persons were hospitalized and 6 persons died. The total number of food borne outbreaks decreased by around 5% compared to 2008. The number of cases affected by an outbreak was 3.8 persons/outbreak. 10% (18% in 2008) of the reported outbreaks were acquired abroad. 34% of all food borne outbreaks acquired in Austria were caused by *Campylobacter* spp. (n=107), 59% by *Salmonella* spp. (n=185) and 70% thereof by serotype Enteritidis (n=130).

Relevance of the different causative agents, food categories and the agent/food category combinations

Salmonella and *Campylobacter* pose the most important agents causing 93% of all food borne outbreaks. The data quality does presently not allow conclusions on the relevance of different food categories.

Relevance of the different type of places of food production and preparation in outbreaks

The data quality does presently not allow conclusions on the relevance of different food categories.

Evaluation of the severity and clinical picture of the human cases

Hospitalized cases or cases that result in death are presently not ascertained in a valid way: Nevertheless, 16.8% of patients affected by these food borne outbreaks are reported as hospitalized (25.6% in 2008); there were 6 deaths (in 2008: no lethal case).

Descriptions of single outbreaks of special interest

Fretz R et al. Listeriosis outbreak caused by acid curd cheese 'Quargel', Austria and Germany 2009. Euro Surveill. 2010;15(5) pii=19477. Available from:

<http://www.eurosurveillance.org/ViewArticle.aspx?ArticleId=19477> ;

Fretz R et al. Update: Multinational listeriosis outbreak due to 'Quargel', a sour milk curd cheese, caused by two different L. monocytogenes serotype 1/2a strains, 2009-2010 . Euro Surveill. 2010;15(16): pii=19543. Available online: <http://www.eurosurveillance.org/ViewArticle.aspx?ArticleId=19543>)

Wassermann-Neuhold M 2009: Ausgewählte Erkrankungen und Ausbrüche im Jahr 2009 in der Steiermark, Jahresbericht zum Steirischen Seuchenplan 2009. Available from:

http://www.verwaltung.steiermark.at/cms/dokumente/10039771_21212/4e02961e/Jahresbericht%20SP2009%20%282%29.pdf

Control measures or other actions taken to improve the situation

Improvement due to the implementation of the Federal Zoonoses Act e.g. the chain of command in terms of investigation of food borne outbreaks affecting more than one province was implemented.

Table 98 Foodborne outbreaks in humans

Causative Agent	Number of outbreaks	Type of outbreak	Foreign outbreak	Number of human cases	Number of hospitalisations	Number of deaths	Foodstuff implicated	Type of evidence linking the outbreak with food	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of foodstuff	Contributory factors
Campylobacter coli	1	household	Italy	2			Unknown		unknown			
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		3	1	0	Other or unspecified poultry meat and products thereof		household	Retail sale outlet		Inadequate heat treatment
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household	Germany	2	0	0	Eggs and egg products		Restaurant/café/pub/bar/hotel	Travel abroad		
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		household	Household / domestic kitchen		
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		3	0		Unknown		household	Household / domestic kitchen		
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	1	0	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus) and products thereof		household	Catering services /restaurant		
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	0	0	Fish and fish products		Restaurant/café/pub/bar/hotel	Catering services /restaurant		
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	2	0	Unknown		household	unknown	Domestic	
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		household	unknown	Domestic	
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	0	0	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus) and products thereof		Restaurant/café/pub/bar/hotel	unknown	Domestic	
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		3	0	0	Unknown		household	unknown	Domestic	

Foodborne Outbreaks

Causative Agent	Number of outbreaks	Type of outbreak	Foreign outbreak	Number of human cases	Number of hospitalisations	Number of deaths	Foodstuff implicated	Type of evidence linking the outbreak with food	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of foodstuff	Contributory factors
Campylobacter jejuni	1	general		2	1	0	Mixed or buffet meals		School, kindergarten	unknown		
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	0	0	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus) and products thereof		household	unknown		
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	2	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	2	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		

Foodborne Outbreaks

Causative Agent	Number of outbreaks	Type of outbreak	Foreign outbreak	Number of human cases	Number of hospitalisations	Number of deaths	Foodstuff implicated	Type of evidence linking the outbreak with food	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of foodstuff	Contributory factors
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	2	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		3	0	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		3	0	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		3	0	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		4	0	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household	Serbia	2	0	0	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus) and products thereof		household		Imported from outside EU	
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown			
Campylobacter jejuni	1	general	Bosnia	3			Unknown		unknown			
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2			Unknown		household			

Foodborne Outbreaks

Causative Agent	Number of outbreaks	Type of outbreak	Foreign outbreak	Number of human cases	Number of hospitalisations	Number of deaths	Foodstuff implicated	Type of evidence linking the outbreak with food	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of foodstuff	Contributory factors
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2			Broiler meat (Gallus gallus) and products thereof		unknown			
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2			Mixed or buffet meals		unknown			
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2			Unknown		unknown			
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2			Unknown		unknown			
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2			Unknown		unknown			
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2			Unknown		unknown			
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2			Unknown		unknown			
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2			Unknown		unknown			
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2			Unknown		unknown			
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2			Unknown		unknown			
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2			Unknown		unknown			
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2			Unknown		unknown			
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	0	0	Other or mixed red meat and products thereof		household			
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	0	0	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus) and products thereof		Restaurant/café/pub/bar/hotel			
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	1	0	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus) and products thereof		Mobile retailer/market/street			

Foodborne Outbreaks

Causative Agent	Number of outbreaks	Type of outbreak	Foreign outbreak	Number of human cases	Number of hospitalisations	Number of deaths	Foodstuff implicated	Type of evidence linking the outbreak with food	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of foodstuff	Contributory factors
									vendor			
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	0		Unknown		unknown			
Campylobacter jejuni	1	general	Germany	3			Unknown		unknown			
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2			Unknown		unknown			
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2			Unknown		unknown			
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2			Unknown		unknown			
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	0	0	Eggs and egg products		household			
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown			
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown			
Campylobacter jejuni	1	general		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown			
Campylobacter jejuni	1	general		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown			
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown			
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown			
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown		unknown			
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown			
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown		unknown			
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown		unknown			
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown			

Foodborne Outbreaks

Causative Agent	Number of outbreaks	Type of outbreak	Foreign outbreak	Number of human cases	Number of hospitalisations	Number of deaths	Foodstuff implicated	Type of evidence linking the outbreak with food	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of foodstuff	Contributory factors
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown			
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown		unknown			
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown			
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household	Croatia	2	0	0	Unknown		unknown			
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown			
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown			
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown			
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown			
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown		unknown			
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown		unknown			
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown			
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown			
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown			
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		3	0	0	Unknown		unknown			
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household		3	0	0	Unknown		unknown			
Campylobacter jejuni	1	general	Turkey	2			Unknown		unknown			
Campylobacter jejuni	1	general	Turkey	2			Unknown		unknown			

Foodborne Outbreaks

Causative Agent	Number of outbreaks	Type of outbreak	Foreign outbreak	Number of human cases	Number of hospitalisations	Number of deaths	Foodstuff implicated	Type of evidence linking the outbreak with food	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of foodstuff	Contributory factors
Campylobacter jejuni	1	household	Hungary	2	0	0	Unknown		unknown			
Campylobacter jejuni/coli	1	household		2	1		Unknown		unknown			
Campylobacter spp.	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		household	Farm (primary production)	Domestic	*Unprocessed contaminated ingredient
Campylobacter spp.	1	household		2	0	0	Other or unspecified poultry meat and products thereof		household			Storage time/temperature abuse
Campylobacter spp.	1	household		2	0	0	Other or mixed red meat and products thereof		Take-away or fast food outlet	Take-away		
Campylobacter spp.	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
Campylobacter spp.	1	household	Hungary	2	0	0	Eggs and egg products		Restaurant/café/pub/bar/hotel		Intra Community trade	
Campylobacter spp.	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown			
Campylobacter spp.	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown			
Campylobacter spp.	1	household		2	0	0	Other or unspecified poultry meat and products thereof		household			
Campylobacter spp.	1	household		2	0	0	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus) and products thereof		household			
Campylobacter spp.	1	household		2	0	0	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus) and products thereof		Restaurant/café/pub/bar/hotel			
Campylobacter spp.	1	household		2	1		Unknown		unknown			
Campylobacter spp.	1	household		2	0	0	Mixed or buffet meals		Restaurant/café/pub/bar/hotel			
Campylobacter spp.	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown			
Campylobacter spp.	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown		unknown			

Foodborne Outbreaks

Causative Agent	Number of outbreaks	Type of outbreak	Foreign outbreak	Number of human cases	Number of hospitalisations	Number of deaths	Foodstuff implicated	Type of evidence linking the outbreak with food	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of foodstuff	Contributory factors
Campylobacter spp.	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown		unknown			
Campylobacter spp.	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown			
Campylobacter spp.	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown			
Campylobacter spp.	1	household		2	0	0	Eggs and egg products		unknown			
Campylobacter spp.	1	household		4	1	0	Unknown		unknown			
Campylobacter spp.	1	household	Poland	2	0	0	Unknown		unknown			
Campylobacter spp.	1	household	Rumani a	3	0	0	Unknown		unknown			
Campylobacter spp.	1	household	Turkey	2	0	0	Unknown		unknown			
EHEC O103:H2	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown	Household / domestic kitchen		
EHEC O103:H2	1	household		3	1	0	Unknown		unknown	Household / domestic kitchen		
EHEC O145:H-	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown			
EHEC O145:H-	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown			
EHEC O146:H28	1	household		3	1	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
EHEC O157	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown		unknown			
EHEC O91:H14	1	household		2	1		Unknown		unknown			
EPEC O128:K67	1	household		2	2		Milk		Restaurant/café/pub/bar /hotel	Farm (primary production)	Domestic	*Unprocessed contaminated ingredient
Hepatitis A	1	household		3	0	0	Mixed or buffet meals		Restaurant/café/pub/bar /hotel			
Histamin	1	general		2			Fish and fish products	Laboratory detection in implicated food	Restaurant/café/pub/bar /hotel	Catering services /restaurant	Domestic	Storage time/temperature abuse
Listeria monocytogenes 1/2a	1	general		25	25	5	Cheese	Laboratory detection in implicated food and Analytical	household	Processing plant	Domestic	Cross-contamination

Foodborne Outbreaks

Causative Agent	Number of outbreaks	Type of outbreak	Foreign outbreak	Number of human cases	Number of hospitalisations	Number of deaths	Foodstuff implicated	Type of evidence linking the outbreak with food	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of foodstuff	Contributory factors
								epidemiological evidence				
Norovirus	1	household		3	3	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
Norovirus	1	general		167	2		Eggs and egg products	Laboratory detection in implicated food and Analytical epidemiological evidence	Hospital/medical care facility	Catering services /restaurant	Domestic	Infected food handler
Norovirus	1	general		12	2	0	Other or mixed red meat and products thereof		unknown	Take-away		Cross-contamination
Norovirus	1	household		2	0	0	Sweets and chocolate		household	unknown		
Norovirus	1	general		5			Unknown		Residential institution			
Norovirus	1	general		10			Unknown		Hospital/medical care facility			
Norovirus	1	general		12			Unknown		Hospital/medical care facility			
Norovirus	1	general		18			Unknown		Residential institution			
Norovirus	1	general		45	0		Mixed or buffet meals		Restaurant/café/pub/bar/hotel	Catering services /restaurant	unknown	Cross-contamination
S. Abony	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown		unknown			
S. Abony	1	household		3	0	0	Unknown		unknown			
S. Agona	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown		unknown			
S. Blockley	1	household		3			Broiler meat (Gallus gallus) and products thereof		household			
S. Enteritidis	1	household		2			Unknown		unknown			
S. Enteritidis	1	household		2			Unknown		unknown			

Foodborne Outbreaks

Causative Agent	Number of outbreaks	Type of outbreak	Foreign outbreak	Number of human cases	Number of hospitalisations	Number of deaths	Foodstuff implicated	Type of evidence linking the outbreak with food	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of foodstuff	Contributory factors
S. Enteritidis	1	household		2			Unknown		unknown			
S. Enteritidis	1	household		2			Unknown		unknown			
S. Enteritidis PT1	1	household		2	2	0	Eggs and egg products		Take-away or fast food outlet	Take-away		
S. Enteritidis PT1	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
S. Enteritidis PT1	1	household		2	0	0	Eggs and egg products		household			
S. Enteritidis PT1	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown		unknown			
S. Enteritidis PT11	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
S. Enteritidis PT13	1	household	Germany	2	0	0	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus) and products thereof		Restaurant/café/pub/bar/hotel	Travel abroad		
S. Enteritidis PT13	1	household		2	0	0	Mixed or buffet meals		Restaurant/café/pub/bar/hotel	Catering services/restaurant		
S. Enteritidis PT13	1	household		3	1	0	Eggs and egg products		Mobile retailer/market/street vendor			
S. Enteritidis PT13a	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown		unknown			
S. Enteritidis PT15a	1	household	Egypt	2	1	0	Unknown		unknown	Travel abroad		
S. Enteritidis PT21	1	household		2	2	0	Eggs and egg products	Laboratory detection in implicated food*	household	Farm (primary production)	Domestic	*pos. Kotproben/eigene Hühner
S. Enteritidis PT21	1	household		4	1	0	Fish and fish products		household	Household / domestic kitchen		
S. Enteritidis PT21	1	general	Croatia	2	0	0	Fish and fish products		Restaurant/café/pub/bar/hotel	Catering services/restaurant		
S. Enteritidis PT21	1	household		3	0	0	Unknown		household	unknown	Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT21	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		

Foodborne Outbreaks

Causative Agent	Number of outbreaks	Type of outbreak	Foreign outbreak	Number of human cases	Number of hospitalisations	Number of deaths	Foodstuff implicated	Type of evidence linking the outbreak with food	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of foodstuff	Contributory factors
S. Enteritidis PT21	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
S. Enteritidis PT21	1	household	Croatia	2			Unknown		unknown			
S. Enteritidis PT21	1	household		2	1		Unknown		unknown			
S. Enteritidis PT21	1	household		2	0	0	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus) and products thereof		Restaurant/café/pub/bar/hotel			
S. Enteritidis PT21	1	household		3	0	0	Eggs and egg products		household			
S. Enteritidis PT21	1	household		3	1	0	Mixed or buffet meals		Restaurant/café/pub/bar/hotel			
S. Enteritidis PT21	1	household	Portugal	2	0	0	Eggs and egg products		unknown			
S. Enteritidis PT21	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown			
S. Enteritidis PT35	1	household	Turkey	2	0	0	Unknown		unknown	Travel abroad		
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	household		3	0	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	household		2	1	0	Other or unspecified poultry meat and products thereof		household			Cross-contamination
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	general		5	0	0	Eggs and egg products		household			Inadequate heat treatment
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	household	Croatia	2	1	0	Unknown		unknown	Travel abroad		
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown	Travel abroad		
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	general		6	1	0	Eggs and egg products	Laboratory detection in implicated food	unknown	Retail sale outlet		
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	household		2	2		Eggs and egg products		household	Retail sale outlet		
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	general		8			Eggs and egg products	Laboratory detection in implicated food	restaurant	Farm (primary production)	Domestic	

Foodborne Outbreaks

Causative Agent	Number of outbreaks	Type of outbreak	Foreign outbreak	Number of human cases	Number of hospitalisations	Number of deaths	Foodstuff implicated	Type of evidence linking the outbreak with food	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of foodstuff	Contributory factors
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	household		3	0	0	Unknown		household	Household / domestic kitchen		
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	household		2	1	0	Eggs and egg products		Restaurant/café/pub/bar/hotel	Catering services /restaurant		
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	household		2	1	0	Eggs and egg products		household	unknown	Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	household		2	2	0	Unknown		household	unknown	Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	household		4	2	0	Unknown		household	unknown	Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown			
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	household		4	1	0	Eggs and egg products		household			
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	household		4	0	0	Unknown		unknown			
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	household		2	1		Unknown		unknown			
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	household		2			Unknown		unknown			
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	household		2	0	0	Other or mixed red meat and products thereof		Restaurant/café/pub/bar/hotel			
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	household	Turkey	3			Unknown		unknown			
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	household		3	0	0	Other or mixed red meat and products thereof		Take-away or fast food outlet			
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	household		3	0	0	Eggs and egg products		household			
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	household	Italy	2	0	0	Eggs and egg products		Restaurant/café/pub/bar/hotel			
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	household	Serbia	2	0	0	Unknown		unknown			
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	household		2			Unknown		unknown			
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	household		2			Unknown		unknown			
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	household		2	0	0	Eggs and egg		household			

Foodborne Outbreaks

Causative Agent	Number of outbreaks	Type of outbreak	Foreign outbreak	Number of human cases	Number of hospitalisations	Number of deaths	Foodstuff implicated	Type of evidence linking the outbreak with food	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of foodstuff	Contributory factors
							products					
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown			
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown			
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown		unknown			
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown		unknown			
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown			
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	household	Turkey	2	0	0	Unknown		unknown			
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	household		3			Unknown		unknown			
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	household		3	0	0	Unknown		unknown			
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	household		3	2	0	Unknown		unknown			
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	household		3	1	0	Unknown		unknown			
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	household		4	1	0	Unknown		unknown			
S. Enteritidis PT4	1	household		4	0	1	Eggs and egg products		Restaurant/café/pub/bar/hotel	Catering services/restaurant		
S. Enteritidis PT4b	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown		unknown			
S. Enteritidis PT5	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
S. Enteritidis PT5	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown			
S. Enteritidis PT6	1	household	Croatia	4	1	0	Unknown		unknown	Travel abroad		
S. Enteritidis PT6	1	household	Slovenia	2	1	0	Mixed or buffet meals		Restaurant/café/pub/bar/hotel	Travel abroad		
S. Enteritidis PT6	1	household		2	0	0	Vegetables and juices and other products thereof		unknown	Travel abroad		
S. Enteritidis PT6	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		household	unknown	Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT6	1	household		3	0	0	Unknown		household	unknown	Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT6	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
S. Enteritidis PT6	1	household	Croatia	2	0	0	Bovine meat and products thereof		household		Imported from	

Foodborne Outbreaks

Causative Agent	Number of outbreaks	Type of outbreak	Foreign outbreak	Number of human cases	Number of hospitalisations	Number of deaths	Foodstuff implicated	Type of evidence linking the outbreak with food	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of foodstuff	Contributory factors
											outside EU	
S. Enteritidis PT6	1	household	Turkey	3	2	0	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus) and products thereof		household		Imported from outside EU	
S. Enteritidis PT6	1	household		2			Unknown		unknown			
S. Enteritidis PT6	1	household		2			Unknown		unknown			
S. Enteritidis PT6	1	household		3			Unknown		unknown			
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		3	0	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		5	1		Eggs and egg products	Laboratory detection in implicated food	household	Farm (primary production)	Domestic	*positive Kotproben/ei gene Enten
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		2	1	0	Other or unspecified poultry meat and products thereof		household	unknown		unknown
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household	Croatia	2	2	0	Unknown		unknown	Travel abroad		
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	general		9	4	0	Eggs and egg products	Laboratory detection in implicated food	Restaurant/café/pub/bar/hotel	Retail sale outlet		
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	general		6	1	0	Eggs and egg products		Canteen or workplace catering	other		
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household	Slovenia	2	1	0	Crustaceans, shellfish, molluscs and products thereof		unknown	Catering services /restaurant		
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		2	2	0	Unknown		household	unknown	Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		3	0	0	Unknown		household	unknown	Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		3	0	0	Unknown		household	unknown	Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		3	1	0	Unknown		household	unknown	Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	general		9	2	0	Eggs and egg products		Canteen or workplace catering	unknown	Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		

Foodborne Outbreaks

Causative Agent	Number of outbreaks	Type of outbreak	Foreign outbreak	Number of human cases	Number of hospitalisations	Number of deaths	Foodstuff implicated	Type of evidence linking the outbreak with food	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of foodstuff	Contributory factors
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	general		3	1	0	Eggs and egg products		household	unknown		
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		3	1	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		3	0	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		3	0	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		3	3	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		3	0	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		3	2	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	general		4	1	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		8	0	0	Eggs and egg products		household		Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown		household		Domestic	
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		2			Eggs and egg products		household			
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		2	1		Unknown		unknown			
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		3	1		Unknown		unknown			
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		3			Unknown		unknown			
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		4	3		Eggs and egg products		household			
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		8	1		Eggs and egg		household			

Foodborne Outbreaks

Causative Agent	Number of outbreaks	Type of outbreak	Foreign outbreak	Number of human cases	Number of hospitalisations	Number of deaths	Foodstuff implicated	Type of evidence linking the outbreak with food	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of foodstuff	Contributory factors
							products					
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		2	2		Unknown		unknown			
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		2			Unknown		unknown			
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		2	0	0	Eggs and egg products		household			
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		2	0	0	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus) and products thereof		household			
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown			
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown		unknown			
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown		unknown			
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown			
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown			
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown			
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	general		3	0	0	Unknown		unknown			
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		3	1		Unknown		Residential institution			
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		3	1	0	Unknown		unknown			
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		3	1	0	Unknown		unknown			
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		4	1	0	Unknown		unknown			
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		4	2	0	Unknown		unknown			
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		5	1	0	Unknown		unknown			
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		7	5	0	Eggs and egg products		household			
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		3	1		Eggs and egg products		household			
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		4	0		Other or mixed red meat and products thereof		household			

Foodborne Outbreaks

Causative Agent	Number of outbreaks	Type of outbreak	Foreign outbreak	Number of human cases	Number of hospitalisations	Number of deaths	Foodstuff implicated	Type of evidence linking the outbreak with food	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of foodstuff	Contributory factors
S. Enteritidis RDNC	1	household	Greece	3	0	0	Unknown		Restaurant/café/pub/bar/hotel	unknown	Intra Community trade	
S. Enteritidis RDNC	1	household	Serbia	3	0	0	Unknown		unknown			
S. Enteritidis RDNC	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown		unknown			
S. Enteritidis U	1	household	Montenegro	2	0	0	Unknown		unknown			
S. Enteritidis U	1	general	Turkey	3			Unknown		Restaurant/café/pub/bar/hotel			
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	general		9	3		Eggs and egg products	Laboratory detection in implicated food*	household	Farm (primary production)		*Hühnersammelkotproben und Staubproben vom Hühnerstall
S. Enteritidis PT8	1	household		2			Other or mixed red meat and products thereof		household			
S. Infantis	1	household		2	1	0	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus) and products thereof		Take-away or fast food outlet	Take-away		
S. Infantis	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
S. Infantis	1	household		3	1	0	Unknown		unknown			
S. Javiana	1	household	Turkey	3	0	0	Cheese		household		Imported from outside EU	
S. Kottbus	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown		unknown			
S. Lichtfield	1	household		2			Unknown		unknown			
S. Monoph. Stamm der B-Gruppe	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown		household	unknown	Domestic	
S. Monoph. Stamm der B-Gruppe	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
S. Monoph. Stamm	1	household		3	1	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		

Foodborne Outbreaks

Causative Agent	Number of outbreaks	Type of outbreak	Foreign outbreak	Number of human cases	Number of hospitalisations	Number of deaths	Foodstuff implicated	Type of evidence linking the outbreak with food	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of foodstuff	Contributory factors
der B-Gruppe												
S. Monoph. Stamm der B-Gruppe	1	household		4	1	0	Unknown		unknown			
S. Oranienburg	1	household	Slovakia	2	1	0	Eggs and egg products		unknown	unknown	Intra Community trade	
S. Paratyphi B Dundee	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
S. Stanley	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown			
S. Typhimurium U311	1	household		2	1		Eggs and egg products		household	unknown	Domestic	
S. Typhimurium U311	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown		household	unknown	Domestic	
S. Typhimurium U311	1	household		3	0	0	Eggs and egg products		household	unknown		
S. Typhimurium U311	1	household		3	0	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
S. Typhimurium DT104H	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown			
S. Typhimurium DT104L	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown		unknown			
S. Typhimurium DT104L	1	household		3	1		Unknown		unknown			
S. Typhimurium DT120	1	household		2	2		Dairy products (other than cheeses)		Restaurant/café/pub/bar/hotel	Farm (primary production)	Domestic	*Unprocessed contaminated ingredient
S. Typhimurium DT120	1	general		6	3		Other or mixed red meat and products thereof	Laboratory detection in implicated food*	Take-away or fast food outlet		Domestic	*Cross-contamination
S. Typhimurium DT120	1	household		5	0	0	Unknown		household	unknown	Domestic	
S. Typhimurium DT120	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
S. Typhimurium DT120	1	household		2	1	0	Sweets and chocolate		household			

Foodborne Outbreaks

Causative Agent	Number of outbreaks	Type of outbreak	Foreign outbreak	Number of human cases	Number of hospitalisations	Number of deaths	Foodstuff implicated	Type of evidence linking the outbreak with food	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of foodstuff	Contributory factors
S. Typhimurium DT120	1	household		2			Unknown		unknown			
S. Typhimurium DT193	1	general		183	23	0	Unknown	Analytical epidemiological evidence	Canteen or workplace catering	other	Domestic	Cross-contamination
S. Typhimurium DT193	1	household		2	1	0	Eggs and egg products		household	Retail sale outlet		Unprocessed contaminated ingredient
S. Typhimurium DT41	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown		household	Household / domestic kitchen		
S. Typhimurium DT41	1	general		6	0	0	Eggs and egg products		Restaurant/café/pub/bar /hotel		Domestic	
S. Typhimurium DT46	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
S. Typhimurium DT8	1	household		3	1		Pig meat and products thereof		household	Household / domestic kitchen	Domestic	
S. Typhimurium RDNC	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
S. Typhimurium RDNC	1	household		3			Unknown		unknown			
S. Typhimurium RDNC	1	household		4			Unknown		unknown			
S. Typhimurium U310	2	household		2	1	0	Unknown		unknown			
S. Typhimurium U310	1	household		2	1	0	Unknown		unknown			
S. Typhimurium U311	1	household		2	0	0	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus) and products thereof		household			Storage time/temperature abuse
S. Typhimurium U311	1	household		2	0	0	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus) and products thereof		Restaurant/café/pub/bar /hotel	Catering services /restaurant		
S. Typhimurium	1	household		2	0	0	Eggs and egg		household	unknown		

Foodborne Outbreaks

Causative Agent	Number of outbreaks	Type of outbreak	Foreign outbreak	Number of human cases	Number of hospitalisations	Number of deaths	Foodstuff implicated	Type of evidence linking the outbreak with food	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of foodstuff	Contributory factors
U311							products					
S. Virchow	1	general		2	2	0	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus) and products thereof		household	Retail sale outlet		
Salmonella group B	1	household		2	1		Unknown		household			
Salmonella group C	1	household		2			Unknown		unknown			
Salmonella group C	1	household		3			Unknown		unknown			
Salmonella group D	1	household		2			Eggs and egg products		unknown			
Salmonella group D	1	household		2			Unknown		unknown			
Salmonella group D	1	household		2			Unknown		unknown			
Salmonella group D	1	household		2	1		Unknown		unknown			
Salmonella group D	1	household		2			Unknown		unknown			
Salmonella group D	1	household		4			Broiler meat (Gallus gallus) and products thereof		household			
Salmonella group D	1	household		4			Unknown		unknown			
Salmonella group D	1	household		2	2		Unknown		unknown			
Y. enterocolitica O:3	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
Y. enterocolitica O:3	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
Y. enterocolitica O:9	1	household		2	0	0	Unknown		unknown	unknown		
Total	351			1330	223	6						

7. Information on specific microbiological agents

7.1. Staphylococcal Enterotoxins

7.1.1. Staphylococcal enterotoxins general evaluation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Not available

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Not available

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Not available

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Not available

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Not available

Additional information

Not available

7.1.2. Staphylococcal enterotoxins in foodstuff

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Not available

Frequency of the sampling

Not available

Type of specimen taken

Not available

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Not available

Definition of positive finding

Not available

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Not available

Preventive measures in place

Not available

Control program/mechanisms**The control program/strategies in place**

Not available

Recent actions taken to control the hazard

Not available

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Not available

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Not available

Notification system in place

Not available

Results of the investigation

See table below

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Not available

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Not available

Additional information

Not available

Table 99 Staphylococcal enterotoxins in food

Food	Sampling Stage	Sample weight	nicht nachweisbar	Units tested	Total units positive for Staphylococcal enterotoxins
Cheeses made from cows' milk - unspecified - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at processing plant - domestic production		1	1	0
	at retail - domestic production		2	2	0
	at catering		1	1	0
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - unspecified - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at processing plant - domestic production		2	2	0
	at retail - domestic production		1	1	0
Fishery products - unspecified - ready-to-eat chilled	at catering	25g	1	1	0
Meat from pig - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	at retail - domestic production		1	1	0
Meat, mixed meat - meat products - cooked - ready-to-eat chilled	at catering	25g	1	1	0
Mushrooms	at catering	25g	1	1	0
Other food	at retail - domestic production		1	1	0
	at catering		2	2	0
Other food of non-animal origin	at retail - domestic production		1	1	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - pasta	at processing plant - domestic production		14	14	0
	at catering	25g	1	1	0
	at retail - domestic production		2	2	0

7.2. Enterobacter sakazakii

7.2.1. Enterobacter sakazakii general evaluation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Not available

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Not available

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Not available

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Not available

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Not available

Additional information

Not available

7.2.2. Enterobacter sakazakii in foodstuff

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Not available

Frequency of the sampling

Not available

Type of specimen taken

Not available

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Not available

Definition of positive finding

Not available

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Not available

Preventive measures in place

Not available

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Not available

Recent actions taken to control the hazard

Not available

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Not available

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Not available

Notification system in place

Not available

Results of the investigation

Not available

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

See table below

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Not available

Additional information

Not available

Campaign A-004-09: Cronobacter in food – Infant formula - at retail - Surveillance - official controls - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: January – March

Type of specimen taken

Infant formulas

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of Cronobacter in 25g

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up surveillance programs

Results of the investigation

43 samples tested, 0-times positive for Cronobacter

Additional information

Samples were also tested for Salmonella spp.

Table 100 Enterobacter sakazakii in food

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Units tested	Total units positive for E. sakazakii
Infant formula - (Campaign A-002-09)	at retail	single	25g	43	0
Units tested				43	0

7.3. Histamine

7.3.1. Histamine general evaluation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Not available

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Not available

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Not available

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Not available

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Not available

Additional information

Not available

7.3.2. Histamine in foodstuff

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Not available

Frequency of the sampling

Not available

Type of specimen taken

Not available

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Not available

Definition of positive finding

Not available

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Not available

Preventive measures in place

Not available

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Not available

Recent actions taken to control the hazard

Not available

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Not available

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Not available

Notification system in place

Not available

Results of the investigation

See table below

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Not available

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Not available

Additional information

Not available

Table 101 Histamine in food

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling unit	Sample weight	Units tested	Total units in non-conformity			
					<= 100 mg/kg	>100 - <= 200 mg/kg	>200 - <= 400 mg/kg	>400 mg/kg
Cheeses made from cows' milk - unspecified - made from pasteurised milk	at retail - imported	single		1	0	1		
Cheeses made from cows' milk - unspecified - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at processing plant - domestic production	single		2	0	2		
	at retail - imported	single		1	1			1
Fish - raw	at retail - domestic production	single		5	0	5		
Fishery products, unspecified	at retail - imported	single		29	0	29		
	at catering	single		2	0	2		
Fishery products from fish species associated with a high amount of histidine* - not enzyme matured		single	10g	30	2	28	2	
	at retail	single	25g	114	3	111	2	1
Fishery products from fish species associated with a high amount of histidine* which have undergone enzyme maturation treatment in brine		single	5g	4	0	4		
Meat from bovine animals - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw	at retail - domestic production	single		1	0	1		
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - fermented sausages	at processing plant - domestic production	single		1	0	1		
Other food	at processing plant - domestic production	single		1	0	1		
	at retail - imported	single		1	0	1		
Spices and herbs	at retail - imported	single		1	0	1		

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